

UNIVERSITY OF THE WEST OF SCOTLAND

DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY THESIS

**AI-Enabled IoT Framework for DevOps-Driven
Tiny Machine Learning**

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All praise and thanks are due to Allah, the Lord of the worlds, whose guidance, blessings, and mercy have enabled me to undertake and complete this journey of knowledge. It is through His infinite wisdom and grace that I have found strength and perseverance during the challenging moments of this endeavor.

To my beloved mother and father, whose endless prayers, sacrifices, and unwavering support have been my anchor throughout my life, I owe every achievement to you. Your love, encouragement, and belief in me have been the light that guided me through every obstacle. To my dearest wife, Bushra, who has been my companion, my support, and my source of comfort. Your patience, understanding, and encouragement have been invaluable, and I am deeply grateful for your presence in my life.

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Declaration

I hereby declare that except where specific references that are made to the work of others, the contents of this dissertation are original and have not been submitted in whole or in part for consideration for any other degree or qualification in this, or any other university. This dissertation is my own work and contains nothing which is the outcome of work done in collaboration with others, except as specified in the text and acknowledgements. This dissertation contains more than 10,000 and less than 25,000 words excluding appendices, bibliography, footnotes.

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Acronyms

AI Artificial Intelligence.

AIoT Artificial Intelligence of Things.

AMQP Advanced Message Queuing Protocol.

ANN Artificial Neural Network.

CAN Controller Area Network.

CD Continuous Deployment.

CI Continuous Integration.

CI/CD Continuous Integration/Continuous Deployment.

IaC Infrastructure as Code.

IoT Internet of Things.

IPR Intellectual Property Rights.

LoRa Long Range.

LPWAN Low Power, Wide-Area Network.

LSTM Long Short-term Memory.

MC Metric Collector.

MCU Microcontroller Unit.

ML Machine Learning.

NN Neural Network.

OBDDIIML On-Board Diagnostics II.

ODBC Open Database Connectivity.

OTA Over-the-Air.

RAM Random Access Memory.

REPL Read-Evaluate-Print Loop.

SotA State-of-the-Art.

TC Topology Collector.

TFLM TensorFlow Lite Micro.

TL Transfer Learning.

Abstract

The rapid advancement of the Internet of Things (IoT) and Artificial Intelligence (AI) presents unprecedented opportunities for integrating intelligent capabilities within resource-constrained devices. This PhD thesis introduces a comprehensive dynamic AI-IoT framework to address the limitations of current ML model deployment in IoT environments, such as high latency, static model updates, and energy inefficiency. Our framework enhances adaptability, scalability, and efficiency of IoT systems by leveraging advanced ML algorithms, ultra-low-power IoT devices, and DevOps mechanisms. The framework enables firmware and ML model updates across distributed IoT devices, ensuring continuous integration and deployment (CI/CD) through an innovative architecture that integrates Kubernetes, GitLab runners, and optimized ML models.

At the core of this research is the development of AI-enabled firmware for the ESP32 microcontroller, featuring a dynamic Micropython component tailored for resource-constrained devices. The framework supports continuous data acquisition, real-time ML model training, and deployment, with transfer learning employed to improve model accuracy and computational efficiency. Specifically, Long Short-term Memory (LSTM) networks are utilized to process sequential IoT data, allowing the framework to adaptively learn from device data in real-time. By leveraging TensorFlow Lite for model optimization, the system enables the deployment of these complex ML models on ultra-low-power devices, maintaining efficient operation within the constraints of embedded hardware. This dynamic, edge-focused approach enhances the real-time responsiveness and energy efficiency of IoT systems, positioning them for advanced applications in smart environments.

Empirical experiments were conducted to evaluate the proposed framework, demonstrating significant improvements in scalability, resource utilization, and deployment efficiency. Results indicate that the dynamic AI-IoT framework can effectively support various applications, including industrial IoT, agriculture, smart cities, healthcare, and environmental monitoring. Furthermore, the framework's ability to dynamically update ML models and firmware Over-the-Air (OTA) minimizes downtime and enhances operational efficiency. It was demonstrated that an ML model with 130 KB in size can be deployed from the edge to an IoT device in approximately 6.2 minutes. Notably, the majority of this time, approximately 5.5 minutes, is allocated to the building of the ML model's Docker container.

This research addresses critical challenges in IoT, such as resource constraints, energy efficiency, and interoperability, providing a robust solution for the dynamic integration of ML in IoT environments. The proposed framework sets a foundation for future advancements, including the integration of federated and transfer learning, dynamic switching among connection technologies, and real-world deployment validation, paving the way for more intelligent, flexible, and efficient IoT systems.

Part I

Summary

Chapter 1

Introduction

The rapid integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Internet of Things (IoT) technologies marks a critical milestone in the ongoing digital transformation of industries and societies. The convergence of these technologies holds transformative potential across various domains, enabling smarter, more efficient, and more resilient systems. The IoT market is projected to surpass 30 billion devices by 2030, fueled by a compound annual growth rate (CAGR) of 14.7% between 2024 and 2030 [2], while the ML market is expected to grow at a similar pace of 15.83% [3]. One of the key enablers of this convergence is Tiny Machine Learning (TinyML), which focuses on executing ML models directly on resource-constrained devices at the edge. The TinyML market is expected to experience a high CAGR of 38.1%, expanding from \$1.5 billion in 2023 to \$10.2 billion by 2030 [4], driven by the demand for real-time, low-power ML applications in IoT systems. This unprecedented fusion of IoT, AI, and TinyML offers vast opportunities for innovation, particularly in areas such as healthcare, transportation, and environmental monitoring.

The widespread use of low-powered IoT devices, characterized by limited computational resources and energy constraints, is a key factor in enabling pervasive connectivity and real-time data collection in various environments. By embedding ML capabilities within these devices, IoT systems can become more intelligent and autonomous. ML algorithms enable predictive analytics, anomaly detection, and adaptive control, optimizing resource utilization and enhancing energy efficiency in the process. However, existing IoT devices often lack the

necessary flexibility to support dynamic ML capabilities, limiting their potential to evolve in response to changing environmental conditions or new data. This rigidity restricts their scalability and adaptability in dynamic, real-time applications such as industrial automation, smart cities, and environmental monitoring.

Central to the success of these IoT systems is the ability to process data at the edge, close to where it is generated. Traditional approaches that rely on cloud-based ML processing face challenges such as high latency, bandwidth limitations, and privacy concerns. By executing ML algorithms directly on low-powered IoT devices, edge computing minimizes data transmission, reduces latency, and offers more secure and private data handling. Despite the advantages, the integration of dynamic, updatable ML models within resource-constrained IoT devices remains a significant challenge, particularly when dealing with real-time, adaptive decision-making in diverse and unpredictable environments.

1.1 Research Problem and Scientific Question

The main problem addressed in this research is the lack of a scalable and dynamic framework for integrating ML capabilities within low-powered IoT devices. While ML has the potential to significantly enhance IoT systems, current models and deployment strategies fail to account for the dynamic nature of real-world applications. Most existing IoT devices are static, unable to adapt or update their ML models in response to changing conditions. This limitation hinders the ability of IoT systems to continuously improve, optimize, and respond to new data.

This research seeks to solve the following central scientific question:

How can we design and implement a dynamic, scalable, and updatable AI-IoT framework that empowers low-powered IoT devices to autonomously update their ML models, enabling real-time decision-making and continuous system adaptation in diverse applications?

1.2 Research Aim and Objectives

To address the central scientific question, the overarching goal of this thesis is to develop and validate an AI-IoT framework that enables resource-constrained devices to execute and dynamically update ML models. This framework will support real-time decision-making and adaptability in IoT systems, offering significant improvements in scalability, flexibility, and efficiency.

The specific research objectives include:

- Objective 1: Conduct a comprehensive review of state-of-the-art (SOTA) architectures and methodologies for integrating ML with IoT devices, establishing a foundational understanding for the design of the proposed framework. This review will inform the development of dynamic ML capabilities for use cases such as aquaponics monitoring, gesture recognition, and CO₂ concentration prediction.
- Objective 2: Develop and prototype an infrastructure for dataset collection, integrated with IoT devices running Micropython firmware. This infrastructure will support the acquisition of data across multiple use cases, including environmental sensing, gesture recognition, and CO₂ concentration, with data managed through an MQTT server.
- Objective 3: Design and implement an ML firmware extension for ESP32-based IoT devices that enables on-device TinyML inference. This extension will allow the devices to perform AI-based analytics for various applications such as aquaponics monitoring, gesture recognition, and environmental sensing.
- Objective 4: Develop and implement a framework for updating ML models on ESP32 devices using TensorFlow Lite Micro, facilitating dynamic and scalable updates in response to changing environmental conditions and new data.
- Objective 5: Create a pipeline for generating optimized TinyML models using transfer learning, tailored to specific applications, such as environmental monitoring and gesture recognition.

- Objective 6: Integrate the dataset collection infrastructure with the Tiny Machine Learning model generation pipeline to develop predictive models for specific use cases, such as CO2 concentration and gesture recognition.
- Objective 7: Investigate and implement a DevOps framework to automate the model update process across distributed IoT devices, enhancing the efficiency of model updates and facilitating scalability.
- Objective 8: Develop an integrated Edge-to-IoT solution combining dataset collection, predictive modeling, and DevOps frameworks, enabling continuous, real-time, and autonomous updates to TinyML models across distributed IoT devices.

1.3 Contributions

This research makes several important contributions:

- The introduction of a novel AI-IoT framework that supports dynamic, scalable, and updatable ML capabilities on low-powered IoT devices.
- The development of a robust infrastructure for data collection and ML model management, enabling the practical deployment of TinyML models in real-world applications.
- The creation of a pipeline for generating optimized ML models tailored to specific use cases, which can be dynamically updated and deployed in distributed environments.
- The proposal and validation of a DevOps framework to automate the deployment and updating of ML models across a network of resource-constrained IoT devices.

This prospective portfolio-based PhD thesis is based on research publications. It has produced 10 outcomes composed by four scientific publications, four software programs, one dataset and one system.

Different international conferences, international journals and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) compose this research work. The main contributor of this work is the candidate who

declares that has performed a major contribution to every work exposed. In the following list, several works are gathered, providing a list of the names of every publication accepted and published in international journals and conferences. In addition, other physical and logical outcomes developed to validate this research work are specified.

Outcome 1 (Journal):

Authors:	Mohammad Alselek , Jose M. Alcaraz-Calero, Qi Wang, Jaume Segura-Garcia
Title:	Water IoT monitoring system for Aquaponics Health and Fishery applications [5]
Journal:	Sensors
Publisher:	MDPI
IF ¹ :	3.576
Pages, Year:	20, 2022
DOI:	10.3390/s22197679

¹ Impact Factor.

Outcome 2 (Journal):

Authors:	Mohammad Alselek , Jose M. Alcaraz-Calero, Qi Wang
Title:	Dynamic AI-IoT: Enabling Updatable ML Models in Ultra-Low-Power 5G IoT Devices [6]
Journal:	IEEE Internet of Things Journal
Publisher:	Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE)
IF:	10.6
Pages, Year:	14, 2023
DOI:	10.1109/JIOT.2023.3340858

Outcome 3 (Conference):

Authors:	Mohammad Alselek , David Tena-Gago, Jose M. Alcaraz-Calero, Qi Wang
Title:	Transfer Learning-Enabled IoT System for Continuous Prediction of Vehicle CO2 Concentration [7]
Conference:	2023 IEEE International Smart Cities Conference (ISC2)
Publisher:	IEEE
Pages, Year:	7, 2023
DOI:	10.1109/ISC257844.2023.10293394

Outcome 4 (Conference):

Authors:	Mohammad Alselek , Jose M. Alcaraz-Calero, Qi Wang
Title:	Agile ML and firmware management in IoT: DevOps for low-power microcontroller-based platforms [8]
Conference:	SpliTech 2024: International Conference on Smart and Sustainable Technologies 2024
Publisher:	IEEE
Pages, Year:	6, 2024
DOI:	10.23919/SpliTech61897.2024.10612585

Outcome 5 (Software):

Author:	Mohammad Alselek
Title:	Edge-based Data Collector
Description:	This software initially designed for water quality monitoring, then adapted for CO2 concentration data collection. IoT devices with sensors like pH, temperature, and CO2, running on Micropython firmware, collect and transmit data via the MQTT protocol to RabbitMQ. Data is processed by the Metrics Collector and stored in a MySQL database.
GitLab:	https://gitavcn.uws.ac.uk/Malselek/edge-data-collector

Outcome 6 (System):

Author:	Mohammad Alselek
Title:	Edge-based IoT Monitoring System for Aquaponics
Description:	This software is a modular solution designed to enhance aquaponic system management by automating the monitoring of key parameters. It uses sensors to track water quality, air quality, soil moisture, and water flow, employing communication protocols like LoRa, LTE-M, and WiFi for data transmission. Edge computing devices process data to reduce latency, which is then analyzed and visualized in real-time using Grafana. This system enables farmers to make informed decisions to maintain optimal conditions, thereby improving fish and plant health and promoting sustainable agriculture.
GitLab:	https://gitavcn.uws.ac.uk/Malselek/iot-monitoring-system-for-aquaponics

Outcome 7 (Software):

Author:	Mohammad Alselek
Title:	ML Enabler Extension for IoT Firmware
Description:	This software adds ML capabilities to ESP32 microprocessors using ESP-IDF and TensorFlow Lite Micro. It allows IoT devices to run pre-loaded TinyML models.
GitLab:	https://gitavcn.uws.ac.uk/Malselek/ai-enabled-pycom-esp-idf

Outcome 8 (Software):

Author:	Mohammad Alselek
Title:	Updatable ML Enabler Extension for IoT Firmware
Description:	This software adds ML capabilities to ESP32 microprocessors using MicroPython and TensorFlow Lite Micro. It allows IoT devices to run and update TinyML models dynamically without needing re-flashing. The firmware supports real-time data collection, processing, and AI-driven actions, ensuring devices can adapt quickly to new data and requirements. This makes IoT devices more flexible and capable of handling evolving ML tasks efficiently.
GitLab:	https://gitavcn.uws.ac.uk/Malselek/pycom-micropython-ai/-/tree/All-in-One

Outcome 9 (Dataset):

Author:	Mohammad Alselek, David Tena-Gago
Title:	Transfer Learning-based CO2 dataset
Description:	This dataset was created to develop a predictive model for vehicle CO2 emissions using an LSTM neural network. It includes eight vehicle parameters as inputs and supports a transfer learning approach, allowing the pre-trained model to be adapted for real-time CO2 prediction on individual vehicles. This process involves collecting vehicle data, training with pre-trained weights, and deploying the model on IoT devices.
GitLab:	https://gitavcn.uws.ac.uk/Malselek/transfer-learning-co2

Outcome 10 (Software):

Author:	Mohammad Alselek
Title:	Remote Updater API for Transfer Learning TinyML Models
Description:	This Software facilitates continuous model updates between an edge server and FiPy board using the REST protocol. This system employs HTTP methods for data exchange, allowing the FiPy device to send collected data to the server for model training and receive updated models. The RESTful API simplifies architecture, reduces communication overhead, and ensures efficient, real-time model improvements with minimal bandwidth usage.
GitLab:	https://gitavcn.uws.ac.uk/Malselek/ai-model-updater-api

This thesis has been made possible through the support of the following research projects funded by UK Research and Innovation and the European Commission:

Project 1 (National Edge ML Hub):

Project Title:	National Edge ML Hub
Description:	The EPSRC National Edge Artificial Intelligence Hub will deliver world class fundamental research, co-created with stakeholders from other disciplines and regions, to protect the quality of data and quality of learning associated with Artificial Intelligence (AI) algorithms when they are subjected to cyber attacks in the Edge Computing (EC) environments.
Website:	https://edgeaihub.co.uk/

Project 2 (6G-BRAINS):

Project Title:	6G-BRAINS (Bring Reinforcement-learning Into Radio Light Network for Massive Connections)
Description:	6G BRAINS aims to bring AI-driven multi-agent deep reinforcement learning (DRL) to perform resource allocation over and beyond massive machine-type communications with new spectrum links including THz and optical wireless communications to enhance the performance with regard to capacity, reliability and latency for future industrial networks.
Website:	https://6g-brains.eu/

Project 3 (INCODE):

Project Title:	INCODE (Intelligent Collaborative Deployments)
Description:	The INCODE project aims at innovating and creating a wide-open, secure, and trusted IoT-to-edge-to-cloud compute continuum that will realize the true potentials of edge intelligence.
Website:	https://www.incode-project.eu/

This thesis is divided into two parts, as illustrated in the flowchart Fig. 1.1. Part I includes: Chapter 2, covering key concepts and technologies such as Edge AI, TinyML, Transfer Learning, DevOps, and MicroPython; Chapter 3, reviewing existing literature on AI-IoT integration and identifying research gaps; Chapter 4, presenting the methodology; Chapter 5, detailing proposed architectures; Chapter 6, discussing the integrated AI-IoT framework; Chapter 7, conducting performance evaluation with empirical data; Chapter 8, identifying limitations and challenges; and Chapter 9, summarizing findings and future research directions. Part II contains accepted papers that provide detailed methodologies, results, and discussions, corresponding to specific chapters in Part I.

Figure 1.1: Thesis structur overview.

Chapter 2

Background and Fundamental Definitions

Chapter 2 provides the foundational understanding required for developing the proposed dynamic AI-IoT framework. It begins with an overview of computing paradigms (Cloud to TinyML), emphasizing their relevance to IoT applications. The chapter then explores the critical technologies and their roles in realizing the objectives of this research.

2.1 From Cloud to TinyML

In the modern world, technology weaves through almost every aspect of our lives, from the smartphones we hold to the sensors that keep our cities connected. To understand this digital transformation, let's start with the core concept of Cloud Computing.

2.1.1 Cloud Computing: The Foundation of Data-Driven Solutions

Cloud computing emerged as a way to store, manage, and process massive amounts of data on remote servers. Instead of relying on local computers, companies could now leverage distant data centers to store information and run applications, scaling resources up or down as needed. This ability to access shared resources over the internet enabled services like streaming, real-time analytics, and global connectivity.

The cloud unlocked possibilities across many sectors, but it presented a challenge when dealing with data generated at the "edge" of networks, such as in homes, cities, and vehicles.

Processing data in centralized cloud servers could introduce latency issues due to the distance data had to travel.

2.1.2 Internet of Things (IoT)

As cloud computing grew, another revolution was taking place—IoT, or the Internet of Things. IoT connects physical devices (sensors, cameras, appliances) to the internet, allowing them to collect and exchange data. Imagine a smart thermostat gathering information on home temperature or a factory sensor monitoring equipment. These devices continuously generate data, requiring fast processing to enable real-time actions.

To support these demands, specialized microcontrollers like the ESP32 have become integral in IoT applications. The ESP32, known for its low power consumption, Wi-Fi and Bluetooth connectivity, and sufficient processing power, enables even resource-constrained IoT devices to handle complex data processing and edge computing tasks. Its compatibility with frameworks like TensorFlow Lite Micro makes it possible to run lightweight ML models directly on the device, allowing for real-time inference without relying on the cloud. This advancement is crucial in scenarios where fast decision-making and reduced latency are needed, as in smart homes, environmental monitoring, and industrial IoT systems.

With countless IoT devices across various industries, a new challenge emerged: how to handle the vast data they generate without burdening the central cloud with every small interaction.

2.1.3 Fog Computing: Bringing the Cloud Closer

To address this, Fog Computing was introduced. Think of fog as an extension of the cloud, positioned closer to where data is generated. Fog computing places intermediary resources between IoT devices and the cloud, allowing data to be processed locally within the network. By filtering and processing data closer to the source, fog computing reduces the strain on cloud resources, lowers latency, and allows real-time responsiveness.

For applications like autonomous vehicles or smart city management, this setup significantly improves performance, as fog nodes can handle critical data on-site and only forward essential information to the cloud.

2.1.4 Edge Computing: Real-Time Intelligence at the Device Level

As technology advanced, there was a push to bring processing capabilities even closer to the source, at the very “edge” of the network—thus, Edge Computing was born. Edge computing means data is processed directly on IoT devices or on hardware close to these devices, rather than sending it to fog nodes or the cloud.

For example, a security camera with edge computing capabilities can analyze video footage in real-time and only send alerts or summaries to the cloud. This approach minimizes latency, reduces the need for constant internet connectivity, and optimizes data privacy since sensitive information can be processed locally.

2.1.5 Artificial Intelligence (AI)

At this point, we have devices generating data and methods to process it closer to the source. But raw data alone is not useful unless we can analyze and understand it. This is where Artificial Intelligence (AI) comes into play. ML enables machines to recognize patterns, make decisions, and even predict future events.

Traditional ML models were often large and required immense processing power, typically only available in powerful data centers or the cloud. ML allows companies to use data not just to react, but to make predictions and automate processes, giving rise to applications like recommendation engines, voice assistants, and predictive maintenance.

2.1.6 Cloud AI: Power and Scale in the Cloud

Since ML can be resource-intensive, the cloud often remains the go-to environment for running large ML models. This Cloud AI approach allows companies to train and deploy complex models that require powerful hardware and enormous datasets. Cloud AI is ideal

for applications that need significant computational power, like natural language processing or complex image recognition.

However, cloud-based ML isn't always optimal for time-sensitive tasks, as it requires data to be sent to the cloud, processed, and then returned. This led to the need for ML solutions at the edge.

2.1.7 Edge AI: Bringing Intelligence to the Edge

Edge AI represents a transformative shift in the deployment of ML models, bringing computational intelligence closer to the data source. Unlike traditional cloud-based AI, Edge AI processes data on local devices such as smartphones, IoT devices, and edge servers. This proximity to data sources significantly reduces latency, enhances privacy, and minimizes bandwidth usage. It also allows for real-time decision-making, which is critical for applications like autonomous vehicles and industrial automation [9, 10]. Fig. 2.1 demonstrates the main concept of the Edge AI architecture, where the Edge, equipped with computational units, processes data directly on IoT devices.

Edge AI involves several key technologies and methodologies designed to optimize ML performance on edge devices. These include edge inference and learning, model optimization, and the integration of advanced hardware accelerators.

Edge inference involves running ML models directly on edge devices to make real-time predictions. This reduces the need for data to be sent to centralized servers, thus lowering latency and improving responsiveness. Edge learning refers to training ML models at the edge, often using techniques like federated learning, where multiple edge devices collaboratively learn a model while keeping data locally [11–13].

To ensure efficient operation on edge devices, ML models undergo various optimization techniques in order to make them suitable for resource-constrained devices:

- **Model Pruning:** Reducing the size of neural networks by removing unnecessary weights and neurons, which helps in minimizing the computational load and memory usage [14].

Figure 2.1: Edge AI Conceptual Architecture.

- **Model Quantization:** Converting high-precision weights and activations into lower precision, often from 32-bit floating-point to 8-bit integers, significantly reducing the model size and inference time, often with minimal loss in accuracy [15].
- **Knowledge Distillation:** Transferring knowledge from a large, complex model to a smaller, simpler model to maintain performance while reducing complexity [14].

Edge AI benefits significantly from specialized hardware accelerators that enhance the performance of ML computations. These include:

- **TPUs:** Tensor Processing Units designed specifically for accelerating machine learning tasks on edge devices. Google’s Edge TPU is an example, optimized for running lightweight models efficiently [16, 17].
- **GPUs and VPUs:** Graphics Processing Units and Vision Processing Units that provide significant parallel computing power, making them highly suitable for handling complex ML computations on edge devices [18].

- **FPGAs and ASICs:** Field-Programmable Gate Arrays and Application-Specific Integrated Circuits offer customizable hardware solutions tailored to specific ML workloads, providing a balance between flexibility and efficiency [19].

2.1.8 Taxonomy of Edge AI

The taxonomy proposed in this work is inspired by and builds upon prior research efforts, particularly the comprehensive framework outlined in [1]. In their study, the authors systematically examined 60 relevant papers, categorizing the research into a well-defined taxonomy. Their methodology involved summarizing the research findings, as detailed in Section 4 of their work, and organizing them into meaningful subcategories. This structured approach provides valuable insights into the key dimensions of Edge AI.

Fig. 2.2 illustrates the taxonomy proposed in [1], which classifies Edge AI research into key subcategories. This thesis explores several of these subcategories, including infrastructure, application architectures, IoT use cases, resource management, AI model sizing, and scheduling. For instance, it lays a foundation for enabling AI on resource-constrained devices, providing a scalable architecture for real-world IoT applications like aquaponics monitoring. Techniques such as model quantization, dynamic memory allocation, and adaptive task scheduling were employed to optimize computational efficiency and energy use.

Partially, this work addresses methods by applying transfer learning and optimizing pre-trained models for edge deployment rather than developing entirely new algorithms. However, areas like managing hardware heterogeneity, ensuring advanced data security, container migration, and dynamic container scaling were outside the scope of this research.

This focus aligns the thesis with significant challenges in Edge AI while leaving opportunities for future work in underexplored areas.

Figure 2.2: Taxonomy of Edge AI, as proposed in [1].

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2.1.9 TinyML: ML on Ultra-Constrained Devices

TinyML is a subset of Edge AI that intersects Machine Learning (ML) and embedded systems. It aims to deploy ML models on resource-constrained devices like microcontrollers (MCUs) and IoT devices. The primary goal is to enable ML capabilities on these devices with minimal power consumption and low latency, thus broadening the scope of ML applications [20, 21]. Moreover, TinyML has expanded its scope to include on-device learning capabilities, allowing for continuous adaptation of models without relying on cloud-based resources [22]

In addition, TinyML involves several key techniques and processes to ensure efficient model deployment on edge devices. The main process includes:

1. **Model Training:** Models are typically trained in the cloud or on powerful hardware, utilizing specialized frameworks and tools [14, 23, 20].
2. **Model Optimization and Compression:** Post-training, models undergo one or more optimization and compression levels, such as pruning, quantization and knowledge distillation to reduce their size and make them compatible with the arithmetic used in MCUs [15, 23].
3. **Compilation and Deployment:** After compression, the model is compiled into C or C++ code and deployed on the device. Lightweight interpreters such as TensorFlow Lite Micro (TFLM) can be used to execute the models on the device [21].

TinyML is applicable in various domains due to its ability to perform on-device inference. Notable applications include environmental monitoring where TinyML can be used in ecological and agricultural settings to monitor environmental conditions and wildlife. For instance, it helps in detecting mosquito species to control malaria and monitoring water quality in aquaculture [24, 25]. In industrial settings, TinyML facilitates predictive maintenance by analyzing sensor data to predict equipment failures. Consumer applications include smart home devices, wearables, and personalized customer experiences through context-aware advertising [21, 24].

While TinyML presents numerous advantages, it also faces significant challenges. The primary challenge is the limited computational and memory resources of MCUs, which makes it difficult to run complex ML models. Innovative compression and optimization techniques are critical to address this issue [23]. Additionally, ensuring energy efficiency is crucial as many TinyML applications run on battery-powered devices. Therefore, techniques like model quantization and efficient runtime systems are essential for reducing power consumption [25]. Moreover, processing data locally on devices helps enhance privacy and security. However, ensuring that these devices are secure from physical and cyber attacks remains a challenge [24].

TinyML brings intelligence to low-power devices that can operate on battery for years, allowing them to perform simple yet powerful ML tasks without requiring internet connectivity. TinyML enables a new class of intelligent applications for the smallest devices, completing our journey from the cloud to the tiniest edge device.

Detailed methodologies for model optimization and compression can be found in Part II, Section 2 and 3.

2.2 Micropython for TinyML

TinyML relies on lightweight frameworks to execute ML models on constrained devices. Micropython emerges as a key enabler, offering a versatile platform for integrating ML capabilities with IoT systems. It allows developers to leverage the simplicity and readability of Python for resource-constrained environments [26].

MicroPython offers a subset of the Python standard library along with additional modules tailored for microcontroller functionalities, such as "machine" and "network". It supports various hardware platforms including ESP32, STM32, and Raspberry Pi Pico, making it versatile for a wide range of applications. Key features of MicroPython include:

- **Compact Footprint:** Designed to fit in small memory spaces, MicroPython typically requires less than 256KB of code space and 16KB of RAM.

- **Interactive Prompt:** The Read-Evaluate-Print Loop (REPL) provides an interactive interface for live testing and debugging.
- **Ease of Use:** Python's simple syntax and dynamic typing make rapid prototyping and development accessible, even for those with minimal programming experience.
- **Extensibility:** Developers can extend functionality through custom modules written in C, providing the flexibility to optimize performance-critical parts of their applications.

MicroPython did not support TinyML out of the box, which limited its direct applicability for running ML models on microcontrollers. However, recent advancements, including our work published in the IEEE IoT Journal [6], have demonstrated innovative methods to integrate TensorFlow ML capabilities into MicroPython firmware.

Our approach enables the deployment of TensorFlow Lite Micro models directly on microcontrollers running MicroPython. This integration is particularly significant for AI-enabled IoT systems, where processing data at the edge reduces latency and bandwidth usage by handling computations locally rather than relying on cloud services.

Here's how this integration enhances MicroPython's capabilities:

- **ML Model Deployment:** By incorporating TensorFlow Lite Micro, developers can now deploy and run ML models on microcontrollers using MicroPython. This is crucial for edge computing scenarios where real-time data processing is needed.
- **Dynamic Updates:** Our methodology allows for the dynamic updating of ML models on-the-fly, which is essential for evolving ML applications that require continuous learning and adaptation.
- **Optimized Performance:** Although MicroPython is a high-level language, our integration maintains efficiency in terms of memory and processing power, making it suitable for low-power IoT devices. The ability to run ML models on such constrained devices expands the potential for TinyML applications across various IoT use cases.

MicroPython represents a significant advancement in bringing the power of Python to embedded systems, particularly within AI-enabled IoT applications. Its ease of use,

combined with recent innovations that enable the integration of TensorFlow Lite Micro, positions MicroPython as a valuable tool for developers working on cutting-edge AI-powered IoT projects. Detailed methodologies and implementation strategies for this integration can be found in Part II, Section 2.

2.3 Data Collection

Data collection serves as a fundamental component in AI-enabled IoT systems, acting as the source of information required for model training, validation, and inference. Within the IoT landscape, devices equipped with diverse sensors continuously gather data specific to their deployment context. For example, environmental monitoring systems collect data such as temperature, humidity, and CO₂ levels, while gesture recognition systems leverage accelerometers or cameras to capture user interactions.

A critical aspect of data collection in edge-based IoT applications is ensuring the quality and relevance of the data. Preprocessing steps, often conducted locally on IoT devices, play an essential role in this process. Techniques such as noise reduction enhance the fidelity of collected data, while feature extraction focuses on isolating meaningful attributes, thus reducing the computational burden for subsequent ML processing.

Scalability and adaptability are key considerations when designing data collection systems for IoT applications. The architecture must handle varying data volumes and types across diverse use cases, ensuring seamless integration regardless of the target domain. This adaptability is particularly crucial for applications like aquaponics, gesture recognition, and air quality monitoring, where sensor inputs and environmental conditions can vary significantly. By addressing these challenges, data collection establishes a robust foundation for the effective deployment of ML models on edge devices.

2.4 Updateable IoT Firmware

Updateable firmware is a cornerstone of modern IoT systems, enabling devices to evolve dynamically in response to new requirements, operational challenges, or technological advancements. This capability ensures that IoT systems remain adaptable and relevant over extended periods without the need for physical intervention.

A major advantage of updateable firmware lies in its ability to support dynamic updates to ML models deployed on edge devices. These updates may involve refining existing models, incorporating new datasets, or addressing performance bottlenecks identified during real-world operations. By enabling seamless model replacements or enhancements, updateable firmware ensures that the ML components of IoT systems remain accurate and effective over time.

Over-the-Air (OTA) update mechanisms are a widely adopted approach for delivering firmware updates in IoT environments. OTA systems allow updates to be deployed remotely, minimizing device downtime and eliminating the logistical challenges associated with manual updates. Secure transmission protocols further ensure that only authorized changes are applied, safeguarding the integrity of the system.

The applicability of updateable firmware extends across various IoT domains. For instance, in environmental monitoring, it allows devices to adapt their ML models to account for seasonal variations or operational changes. Similarly, in gesture recognition systems, updates enable the integration of new gestures or refinements tailored to specific users. By maintaining the relevance and functionality of IoT devices, updateable firmware plays a critical role in supporting sustainable and scalable AI-enabled systems.

2.5 Transfer Learning

With the advancements in the development of IoT systems, the amount of data generated has increased dramatically. Analyzing this data often involves deep learning techniques, but labeling and training models for specific tasks can be very resource-intensive, requiring a lot

of human effort and computational power. Transfer learning offers a practical solution to these challenges by enabling models trained on one task to be adapted for related tasks [27].

In transfer learning, the focus has shifted from transferring raw data and simple features to more abstract deep features and model-based approaches. Each method has its own balance between data detail, transfer cost, and privacy. Transferring raw data retains the most detailed information but poses significant privacy risks. Transferring features reduces some of these risks but might still expose sensitive data. Model-based transfer, which involves sharing model parameters, enhances privacy while maintaining utility.

Traditional transfer learning often relies on central servers for data processing and model training. This approach gathers all source and target domain data on a single server to train initial models, which are then fine-tuned with target domain data. While effective, this method has drawbacks such as network latency, limited scalability, and privacy concerns.

To address these issues, edge computing has emerged as a powerful solution, allowing complex computations to be performed directly on edge devices. This shift forms the basis of the Artificial Intelligence of Things (AIoT), enhancing scalability, reducing latency, and improving data privacy by minimizing dependence on central servers [28].

By leveraging transfer learning and edge computing, the system in Part II, Section 3, allows the IoT devices to perform continuous CO₂ concentration prediction, adapting and improving accuracy over time, and providing a scalable and cost-effective solution for monitoring vehicle CO₂ emissions.

2.6 DevOps for Edge AI and IoT

DevOps, a portmanteau of "development" and "operations" is a set of practices, tools, and cultural philosophies that aim to enhance the efficiency and quality of software development and IT operations. It focuses on unifying development and operations teams, automating processes, and improving the speed and reliability of software delivery. The core principles of DevOps include Continuous Integration/Continuous Deployment (CI/CD), Infrastructure as Code (IaC), monitoring, logging, and fostering collaboration and communication across

teams. These practices help organizations deploy software faster, with fewer errors, and adapt quickly to changing market demands [29, 30].

DevOps techniques are essential for managing the development and deployment of AI-enabled IoT systems. CI/CD pipelines automate the processes of building, testing, and deploying ML models and IoT firmware, ensuring rapid and reliable updates. This automation is crucial for maintaining the functionality and performance of IoT systems, which often consist of numerous distributed devices [31]. CI/CD pipelines facilitate the version control of code and models, making it easier to track changes and collaborate with other developers. Automated testing ensures that updates do not introduce new bugs or degrade system performance, which is particularly important in IoT systems deployed in critical applications such as healthcare, industrial automation, and transportation [29, 32].

OTA updates enable the remote updating of firmware and ML models on IoT devices, minimizing downtime and ensuring devices are always running the latest versions. OTA updates are essential for maintaining the security and performance of IoT systems, as they allow for the timely deployment of patches and improvements without the need for physical access to the devices. Security considerations are paramount in DevOps practices for AI-enabled IoT systems. Ensuring the security of CI/CD pipelines and OTA updates is critical to prevent unauthorized access and tampering. Robust authentication mechanisms ensure that only authorized users can trigger updates, while encryption protects data transmitted during updates and ensures the integrity of firmware and ML models [31, 30].

DevOps practices also address the challenges of deploying and updating ML models on distributed IoT devices. By automating the deployment process, DevOps practices reduce the complexity and resource requirements associated with manual updates. This automation is particularly valuable in large-scale IoT deployments, where managing updates manually would be impractical. The adoption of DevOps practices in AI-enabled IoT systems offers several benefits, including improved efficiency, reliability, and security. By streamlining the development and deployment processes, DevOps practices enable organizations to respond quickly to changing requirements and emerging threats. This agility is crucial in the IoT world, where new applications and technologies are constantly being developed [30, 29].

In conclusion, DevOps represents a significant shift in how software is developed and delivered, emphasizing automation, collaboration, and continuous improvement. While there are challenges to its implementation, the benefits of faster delivery, improved quality, and greater scalability make it an essential practice for modern software development. The future of DevOps will likely be influenced by advancements in AI, serverless computing, and edge computing, continuing to evolve and improve the software development lifecycle.

To achieve this automation, tools like GitLab Runner play a vital role. GitLab Runner is an open-source application that integrates seamlessly with GitLab's CI/CD pipelines, automating processes like building, testing, and deploying software updates. By executing tasks defined in the **.gitlab-ci.yml** file, GitLab Runner ensures consistency across delivery pipelines, which is particularly beneficial for distributed systems. In AI-enabled IoT environments, it facilitates the rapid deployment of firmware updates or new ML models, enabling devices to maintain peak performance. This approach significantly reduces manual intervention, accelerates development cycles, and ensures that updates are tested and reliable before deployment [33, 34].

The flexibility of GitLab Runner lies in its ability to operate across diverse environments, using executors such as Docker containers or Kubernetes clusters. These executors provide isolated environments that prevent conflicts and ensure consistency, even in complex projects with numerous dependencies. For AI-enabled IoT systems, this flexibility is essential as it supports diverse deployment needs, from updating models on resource-constrained edge devices to scaling across vast IoT networks. Once validated, updates are deployed automatically, and post-deployment monitoring ensures continuous improvement [35].

Another critical component in DevOps for AI-enabled IoT is Kubernetes, which provides a robust platform for managing containerized applications. Kubernetes automates deployment, scaling, and resource management, making it particularly valuable for handling the complexities of ML models deployed across distributed IoT devices. By packaging ML models into containers, Kubernetes ensures consistency in deployment across various environments, whether on local edge servers or in the cloud. This consistency is critical for

maintaining performance and reliability, especially as IoT systems scale to accommodate more devices or computationally intensive tasks.

Kubernetes excels at managing resources efficiently, which is essential for IoT devices with limited processing power or memory. It schedules workloads intelligently, preventing individual devices from becoming overloaded and ensuring the optimal use of available resources. In addition, its fault-tolerant design minimizes downtime by redistributing workloads if a node fails, ensuring the uninterrupted operation of AI-enabled IoT systems. With capabilities such as rolling updates, Kubernetes facilitates the smooth deployment of new ML models or firmware without service interruptions, and it can quickly revert to previous versions if issues arise, making it a cornerstone for scalable and reliable IoT deployments.

By integrating tools like GitLab Runner and Kubernetes into a DevOps framework, AI-enabled IoT systems can achieve a high degree of automation, scalability, and reliability. These tools streamline the complex process of deploying and managing ML models and firmware across distributed devices, enabling organizations to respond swiftly to new requirements or emerging challenges. As a result, they form the backbone of an efficient, secure, and adaptable DevOps pipeline, aligning with the dynamic needs of AI-enabled IoT environments.

Chapter 3

Literature Review

The integration of AI and IoT has emerged as a prominent research area, driven by the increasing availability of data and the advancements in machine learning algorithms. This chapter provides a comprehensive review of the existing literature, organized thematically to explore key trends, challenges, and opportunities in AI-IoT integration. Specific focus is given to areas such as AI-IoT data collection, ML model deployment on IoT devices, transfer learning in IoT, and DevOps for AI-IoT systems.

3.1 Data Collection

A primary area of focus is the development of dataset collection infrastructures. Despite the progress in IoT technology, many systems struggle with scalable and reliable data collection methods, particularly in diverse environments. Studies have shown that IoT devices often face data integrity and availability issues, which are critical for ML applications. Traditional approaches, which heavily rely on centralized servers, lack the flexibility required for dynamic IoT settings [29, 36]. We have addressed these challenges by validating the integrating IoT devices with Micropython firmware and MQTT servers for data collection, demonstrating efficient data collection and processing necessary for ML model training. More details can be found in [5], Section 1 in Part II.

3.2 Updateable AI-enabled IoT Firmware

TinyML is a critical technology for bringing artificial intelligence to the edge layer of IoT systems, enabling real-time decision-making on resource-constrained devices [14]. It draws inspiration from Mobile Machine Learning (Mobile ML), which focuses on optimizing ML algorithms to run efficiently on mobile devices with limited computing resources and power. TinyML further extends this concept to ultra-low-power devices like microcontrollers, enabling applications in healthcare, agriculture, industrial IoT, and environmental sensing, where traditional ML models would be too power-hungry. The development of TinyML has been facilitated by advances in IoT and microcontroller technology, making it possible to deploy compressed and optimized models that meet the demands of real-time applications with minimal computational overhead [37].

Enhancing ML capabilities in IoT devices is another significant research area. Current solutions often lack the flexibility and robustness needed to handle varying operational conditions and workload fluctuations. Authors in [29, 38] have highlighted the limitations of traditional ML firmware, which are not well-suited for dynamic IoT environments and often require manual updates and extensive computational resources. To bridge this gap, the development and empirical validation of ML firmware extensions for ESP32-based devices in Part II, Section 2, have enabled efficient execution of ML algorithms on resource-constrained devices. This advancement allows IoT devices to perform complex data analysis and decision-making tasks, enhancing their functionality and autonomy [6].

In addition, enabling updateable ML capabilities in IoT devices is a critical area of research. Existing methodologies often involve significant manual intervention or downtime, which can be impractical for real-world applications. Researchers in [30], have demonstrated that static ML models quickly become outdated in rapidly changing environments, resulting in performance degradation and necessitating frequent manual updates. Our contribution addresses this challenge by integrating Micropython firmware with dynamic ML functionalities, facilitating ML model updates directly on IoT devices. This capability ensures continuous improvement and adaptability, crucial for maintaining ML

model performance and relevance through iterative enhancements in a dynamic environment [6].

Moreover, the literature points out the importance of comprehensive connectivity options such as WiFi and LoRa/Sigfox, which are important for AI-enabled IoT applications. Studies by the authors in [39, 40] highlight the feasibility of running ML models on low-power IoT devices but still fall short in providing dynamic ML model configuration and real-time updates. Contributions by Spresense in [41] and OpenMV in [42] show progress in using dynamic ML functionalities and low-power consumption; however, they still lack comprehensive ML support features. Our contribution addresses these gaps by providing programmability, full ML support, extensive connectivity options, and optimal power consumption, thereby setting a new benchmark in the development of AI-enabled IoT systems. For further details, refer to this paper in Part II, Section 2.

3.3 Transfer Learning

On the other hand, establishing a comprehensive IoT pipeline for generating ML models is another important research focus. Current practices lack standardization in data processing and model training pipelines, often leading to inefficiencies and inconsistencies in ML model performance. Studies have highlighted the challenges in creating unified frameworks that can be adapted across various IoT use cases, which hampers the development of reliable predictive models [36]. By transforming collected metrics into predictive ML models, we have been able to provide valuable insights and predictions for various applications. For instance, focusing on CO₂ concentration metrics from digital sensors has resulted in ML models that provide accurate and timely predictions, crucial for environmental monitoring and management [7]. More information about how we have designed, implemented, and validated the system can be found in Part II, Section 3.

The integration of developed monitoring infrastructure with ML models for continuous prediction applications has also been explored. However, the application of transfer learning in IoT contexts still faces several challenges, including the need for extensive labeled datasets

and the computational overhead associated with model adaptation. Traditional transfer learning techniques are not fully optimized for resource-constrained IoT devices, limiting their efficiency and scalability [30]. We have addressed this challenge by employing an innovative algorithm that utilizes transfer learning techniques with IoT devices to ensure accurate and efficient predictions in vehicle emissions scenarios. This approach leverages pre-trained models and fine-tunes them for specific tasks, reducing the amount of data and computational resources required for training [7].

3.4 DevOps for Edge ML and IoT

Furthermore, automating ML model deployments in IoT devices has been extensively studied. Integration complexities and compatibility issues with existing IoT infrastructures often hinder the full realization of automated ML model updates. Studies have shown that traditional DevOps practices, particularly CI/CD pipelines, are not fully adaptable to the unique requirements of distributed IoT environments, leading to inefficiencies and increased resource demands [38]. The design and implementation of CI/CD pipelines tailored for a distributed IoT environment can enhance the ML model updating process, reducing complexity and resource requirements. This automation is particularly valuable in large-scale IoT deployments, where managing updates manually would be impractical [30]. This thesis proposes a framework that integrates DevOps practices to automate these processes, ensuring continuous and efficient model updates. The challenges are addressed in Part II, Section 4.

Overall, the literature highlights significant advancements and ongoing challenges in integrating AI and IoT, including the development of dataset collection infrastructures, enhancement of ML capabilities in IoT devices, implementation of updatable ML models, predictive ML model pipelines, and DevOps practices. These advancements provide a solid foundation for further research and development. Despite the promise of intelligent systems, challenges related to scalability, energy efficiency, interoperability, and security persist. This PhD thesis addresses these issues by proposing a dynamic AI-IoT framework that leverages advanced DevOps mechanisms for efficient and continuous updates of ML

models and firmware on resource-constrained IoT devices. Through comprehensive empirical evaluations and real-world deployments, this research aims to advance AI-IoT integration, paving the way for more intelligent, flexible, and efficient IoT systems.

Chapter 4

Methodology

The methodology is structured into five distinct phases, each corresponding to specific tasks aimed at achieving the main research goal. The main goal is to design, develop, integrate, deploy, evaluate, and optimize an AI system for IoT devices that can run and update ML models even on resource-constrained devices. The organization and chronology of the tasks and objectives pursued during the thesis are illustrated in Fig. 4.1. The phases may contain tasks from other phases. For instance, in phase 2, the IoT firmware task has migrated from phase 1 to represent it has been used. Below is a detailed explanation of each phase and task based on the provided diagram and objectives.

- **Phase 1: Literature Review and Initial Development** This initial phase establishes the theoretical foundation and technical infrastructure required for the research. It involves reviewing the current state of ML and IoT architecture to identify essential features for integrating machine learning and data processing capabilities on IoT devices. Additionally, it includes the development of a functional IoT device and validation in a real-world use case.
 - **Task 1 (Literature Review):** Conduct a comprehensive study and analysis of the SotA works to define ML and IoT architectures. This task is essential to outline the core ML and IoT requirements.

- **Task 2 (IoT Board):** Design and prototype an IoT device integrated with Micropython firmware and monitoring logic to meet the identified requirements.
 - **Task 3 (IoT Firmware):** Develop and test firmware for the IoT device, enabling robust data collection necessary for future AI-driven use cases.
 - **Task 4 (Edge-based Data Collector):** Implement a data collector on the IoT device to gather real-time data, facilitating initial data collection for various use cases.
 - **Task 5 (Edge-based IoT Monitoring System for Aquaponics):** Develop a monitoring system within an aquaponics use case to validate the IoT device’s effectiveness in a real-world scenario.
 - **Task 6 (Aquaponics Use-Case Validation):** Conduct validation experiments in an aquaponics environment to ensure the system meets functional requirements.
- **Phase 2: AI Firmware Extension** In this phase, the focus shifts towards enabling on-device ML capabilities, empowering the IoT device to perform local inferences. This involves designing a firmware extension that makes ML functionality feasible on resource-constrained ESP32 devices and testing these capabilities through a gesture recognition use case.
 - **Task 7 (AI Enabler Extension for IoT Firmware):** Investigate and design an AI firmware extension that enables ML capabilities on ESP32-based IoT devices.
 - **Task 8 (Updatable AI Enabler Extension for IoT Firmware):** Implement and validate an updatable AI extension using the Micropython framework with TensorFlow Lite Micro, allowing dynamic ML model updates.
 - **Task 9 (Gesture Recognition Use-Case Validation):** Validate the AI extension’s effectiveness through a gesture recognition use case, demonstrating the ESP32’s on-device ML capabilities.

Figure 4.1: Organisation and chronology of the tasks and objectives pursued during the thesis.

- **Phase 3: Transfer Learning Pipeline Development** This phase develops a transfer learning pipeline to produce TinyML models optimized for the IoT context. The models are created to predict outcomes based on real-world data, and a CO2 concentration prediction use case is implemented for validation.
 - **Task 10 (Transfer Learning Dataset):** Establish a dataset for transfer learning, focusing on CO2 sensor metrics as a foundational use case.
 - **Task 11 (Edge-based AI Training Pipeline):** Develop a comprehensive pipeline for training IoT TinyML models using transfer learning, tailored for the specific metrics collected from edge devices.
 - **Task 12 (Transfer Learning TinyML IoT Model):** Design and implement predictive TinyML models that leverage the transfer learning dataset, focusing on efficient model generation for edge deployment.
 - **Task 13 (Remote Updater API for Transfer Learning TinyML Models):** Develop an API to enable remote updates of TinyML models, ensuring continuous improvement of predictive models on IoT devices.
 - **Task 14 (Transfer Learning-based CO2 Use-Case Validation):** Validate the TinyML models in a CO2 concentration prediction use case, demonstrating the pipeline's effectiveness for real-time environmental monitoring.
- **Phase 4: DevOps Framework Implementation** The purpose of this phase is to build a DevOps framework that automates the continuous integration and deployment of model updates for distributed IoT devices. This ensures that TinyML models and firmware can be seamlessly updated across devices in a scalable manner.
 - **Task 15 (DevOps Framework):** Investigate, design, and implement a DevOps framework to automate the updating process of TinyML models on IoT devices, enabling scalability in distributed environments.

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- **Task 16 (Automated CI/CD Pipeline for ML Model Updates):** Establish a CI/CD pipeline to streamline ML model updates on edge devices, reducing the time and complexity associated with manual deployments.
 - **Task 17 (Automated CI/CD Pipeline for OTA Firmware Updates):** Develop and validate a CI/CD pipeline for OTA firmware updates, enabling the efficient deployment of firmware improvements across all connected devices.
- **Phase 5: Integration and Continuous Updates** In this final phase, the previously developed components are integrated to form a comprehensive Edge-to-IoT solution that supports continuous TinyML updates. By connecting the dataset collection infrastructure, predictive models, and DevOps framework, this phase ensures the system's adaptability to evolving needs.
 - Integrate the developed dataset collection infrastructure from Objective 2 with the transfer learning-based CO2 concentration prediction use case (Objective 6) and the DevOps framework (Objective 7). This integration enables continuous TinyML updates from Edge-to-IoT, ensuring adaptability and scalability in diverse applications.

The methodology outlined above encompasses a systematic approach to achieve the research goal. Each phase is designed to address specific objectives, ensuring the development of a robust and adaptable AI system for IoT devices. The integration of these phases culminates in a comprehensive solution that meets the high standards of accuracy, speed, scalability, and portability required for effective real-world application.

Table 4.1 shows a scheme which associate each objective pursued with its outcome. Some objectives have relation with several outcomes, and conversely, some outcomes are connected with the same objective. The relation between these two concepts is coloured green.

Finally, table 4.2 shows the time dedicated during these three years to each one of the objectives. Each year is divided into four quartiles. A coloured box indicates that during that time, the focus has been allocated to achieve that goal. In some scenarios, many objectives

Chapter 5

Proposed Architectures

This chapter presents the key architectures developed throughout the research, providing foundational structures and infrastructure for the integration of ML capabilities and updatable ML models on IoT devices. These architectures serve as the basis for the subsequent development of the integrated system in Chapter 6. Each of the architectures presented in this chapter is designed to meet specific objectives outlined in the thesis, such as enabling ML inference (Objective 3), supporting model updates (Objective 4), and implementing predictive use cases (Objective 6).

It is recommended that readers refer to the individual outcomes presented in Part 2 of this manuscript in tandem with this chapter to better understand the evolution of these architectural solutions. The architectures discussed here logically build upon each other, from the IoT monitoring system for aquaponics (Objective 1 and 2), to updatable AI-enabled IoT solutions (Objective 3 and 4), and transfer learning systems (Objective 5), culminating in the DevOps-based architecture for model updates (Objective 7).

In this context, the chapter explores:

- The IoT monitoring system architecture for aquaponics, which provides the groundwork for data collection and monitoring.
- The updatable AI-enabled IoT architecture, which integrates ML capabilities on IoT devices.
- The transfer learning IoT system architecture that supports model training and adaptation.

- The DevOps-based AI-IoT system that automates the updating process of TinyML models and IoT firmware.

These foundational components set the stage for the unified framework introduced in Chapter 6.

5.1 IoT Monitoring System Architecture for Aquaponics

Aquaponics combines aquaculture and hydroponics to create a symbiotic environment for fish and plant cultivation. This system is crucial for sustainable agriculture, as it reuses nutrients from fish waste to nourish plants, reducing the need for agrochemicals and conserving water. Our proposed solution presents a comprehensive IoT-based monitoring system designed to automate and optimize aquaponic system management, enhancing both fish and plant health while improving operational efficiency.

The IoT monitoring system for aquaponics, as shown in Fig. 5.1, consists of several key components: sensors, communication technologies, edge computing units, cloud computing resources, and user interfaces. The architecture is modular, scalable, and cost-effective, addressing existing solutions' limitations in terms of cost, coverage, and functionality.

The system employs a variety of sensors to monitor critical parameters, including:

- **Water Quality:** pH, temperature, dissolved oxygen (DO), oxidation-reduction potential (ORP), electrical conductivity (EC), total dissolved solids (TDS), water level (WL), and specific ions (ammonium, nitrite, nitrate).
- **Air Quality:** Light intensity, air temperature, air humidity.
- **Soil Quality:** Soil moisture.
- **Water Flow (WF):** Speed of water through the system.

Details on how these sensors are strategically deployed within the aquaponic setup, including fish ponds, plant grow beds, bio-filters, and water circulation systems, are provided in Part II, Section 1.

Figure 5.1: IoT Monitoring System.

The system utilizes multiple communication protocols to ensure reliable data transmission over various distances and environmental conditions:

- LoRa/LoRaWAN: For Low Power, Wide-Area Network (LPWAN) communications, providing coverage up to 1 km².
- LTE-M/NB-IoT: For cellular communications, enabling connectivity over broader areas with higher data rates.
- WiFi: For local communication within the farmhouse.

The collected data is processed using a combination of edge computing and cloud computing. Edge devices, such as Raspberry Pi units, handle initial data processing and filtering to reduce latency and bandwidth usage. The processed data are then transmitted to cloud servers for further analysis, storage, and visualization.

The collected data is processed using a combination of edge computing and cloud computing. At the edge layer, devices such as Raspberry Pi units perform initial data processing, filtering, and aggregation to reduce latency and bandwidth usage. Key

Figure 5.2: Metrics Visualization.

components at the edge include the Topology Collector and Metrics Collector, the detailed explanation of the Data collection process is in the following subsection.

After initial processing at the edge, the data is transmitted to cloud servers for advanced analysis, long-term storage, and visualization.

A user-friendly interface developed using Grafana provides real-time monitoring and control capabilities. Farmers can access this interface through a computer or mobile device, enabling them to make informed decisions about system adjustments, such as regulating water flow, adjusting pH levels, or controlling lighting and feeding schedules. Some of the collected metrics are shown in Fig. 5.2.

The IoT monitoring system follows a systematic process to collect, process, and transmit data from the IoT devices to the central system:

1. **Data Collection:** Sensors are strategically placed within the aquaponic setup to capture a wide range of environmental parameters. Each sensor periodically collects data based on the parameter it monitors, such as pH, temperature, or dissolved oxygen. Additionally, the time of data collection ('startSamplingTime') and the time of data reporting ('reportedTime') are recorded. Further details can be found in Section 5.1.1.

2. **Data Pre-processing:** The collected data is initially processed at the edge by the Metrics Collector to ensure accuracy and reliability. This involves verifying the integrity of each data point and filtering out any anomalous readings.
3. **Data Aggregation:** The Metrics Collector aggregates data from multiple sensors, combining these data points for comprehensive analysis. Each parameter from the different sensors is extracted and processed individually, providing a holistic view of the environmental conditions.
4. **Data Transmission:** The preprocessed and aggregated data is formatted and transmitted to the central database using the selected communication protocol, such as Wi-Fi, 5G, or Long Range (LoRa). The data is sent in structured messages containing all relevant metrics and their timestamps.
5. **Data Storage and Visualization:** Upon receiving the data, the central database stores it, making it available for real-time and historical analysis. Grafana then visualizes this data on customizable dashboards, providing users with intuitive insights into the system's health.
6. **Network Monitoring and Management:** The Topology Collector continuously monitors the network status and the connectivity of IoT devices. It identifies any devices that have gone offline or are malfunctioning and sends alerts for maintenance or reconfiguration.

By leveraging modern IoT technologies, edge computing components, and robust communication protocols, the proposed system provides a comprehensive solution for real-time monitoring and control of aquaponic systems, ensuring optimal conditions for both fish and plants. This approach not only enhances productivity and efficiency but also contributes to sustainable and eco-friendly farming practices. More detailed explanations can be found in Part II, Section 1.

5.1.1 Data Collection Process

The data collection process and infrastructure presented in this work were initially developed for an IoT water quality monitoring system and later adapted to gather data for creating a dataset for a CO₂ concentration ML model. This process leverages IoT devices, the MQTT protocol, and various data processing and storage tools, each performing specific roles in the data collection and processing pipeline.

The process includes multiple IoT devices equipped with various sensors. The Pycom FiPy development board is used as the main IoT device. For water quality monitoring, sensors such as pH, temperature, and turbidity sensors are used, while for CO₂ sensing, CO₂ concentration sensors are deployed. The FiPy IoT devices run Micropython firmware, which facilitates interaction with the sensors and the collection of data. The firmware includes advanced monitoring logic that periodically reads sensor values and prepares them for transmission.

The collected data from the FiPy IoT devices are transmitted to the server using the MQTT protocol, chosen for its lightweight nature and suitability for resource-constrained devices. The MQTT server (RabbitMQ) acts as a message broker, receiving data from multiple FiPy IoT devices and ensuring reliable delivery to the backend components. RabbitMQ serves as the message bus server that facilitates communication between FiPy IoT devices and data collectors. It supports Advanced Message Queuing Protocol (AMQP) for message queuing and delivery.

RabbitMQ routes the incoming data to two main collectors:

- **Topology Collector (TC):** Manages the network topology and the status of the connected devices. The Topology Collector receives network status data from RabbitMQ and stores the information about the network topology and device status in a MySQL database.
- **Metric Collector (MC):** Gathers and processes the actual sensor data. The Metrics Collector receives sensor data from RabbitMQ, performs necessary data

transformations such as filtering and aggregation, and stores the processed data in the MySQL database.

The processed data are stored in a MySQL database, structured to hold different types of sensor data, including water quality metrics and CO₂ concentration levels. The Topology Collector also stores data related to network topology and the status of connected devices in the MySQL database. Grafana is used for data visualization and monitoring, pulling data from the MySQL database and presenting it in an easily interpretable graphical format. The Grafana engine interfaces with the MySQL database using Open Database Connectivity (ODBC).

The metrics collector aggregates the data, which can be used for various analytical purposes. For instance, in the water quality monitoring system, it helps in real-time analysis and historical data trend visualization. The collected CO₂ data is used to create a comprehensive dataset, which is then utilized to train ML models using transfer learning. The existing ML training pipeline was adapted to include steps specific to CO₂ data, such as labeling and model fine-tuning.

The data collection process can be summarized by the following logical sequence diagram, Fig. 5.3.

This sequence diagram, shown in Fig. 5.3, outlines the data collection process within the IoT infrastructure, demonstrating the flow from data acquisition to visualization. This process involves multiple components working together to ensure continuous data collection, processing, storage, and visualization.

Initially, the user initializes the FiPy IoT devices with Micropython firmware. These devices are equipped with sensors that collect various environmental metrics such as temperature, humidity, pH levels, or CO₂ concentrations.

In the data acquisition loop, the FiPy IoT devices periodically collect sensor data, which is then transmitted to the MQTT server using the lightweight MQTT protocol. The MQTT server forwards the data to the RabbitMQ server, acting as a message broker to ensure reliable delivery.

Figure 5.3: Data collection Sequence Diagram.

RabbitMQ routes the incoming data to both the Topology Collector and the Metrics Collector. The Topology Collector manages the network topology and the status of connected devices, storing this information in the MySQL database. Meanwhile, the Metrics Collector processes the sensor data by performing necessary transformations such as filtering and aggregation. The processed data is then stored in the MySQL database for persistent storage and future analysis.

For visualization, Grafana fetches the processed data from the MySQL database and displays it in a graphical format to the user. This allows for real-time monitoring and historical analysis of the collected data.

This process repeats continuously, ensuring ongoing data collection, processing, and monitoring. The infrastructure's design ensures reliability and scalability, making it suitable for dynamic and time-sensitive IoT applications.

As mentioned above, the data collection process and infrastructure were initially developed for IoT water quality monitoring and later adapted for CO2 sensing, showcasing its versatility and robustness. The adaptation process included:

- Replacing water quality sensors with CO2 concentration sensors.
- Updating the monitoring logic in the Micropython firmware to read and process CO2 sensor data.
- Extending the metrics collector to handle the new type of data.
- Using the CO2 data to form a comprehensive dataset for training ML models.

5.2 Updatable AI-enabled IoT Architecture

This section summarizes the work presented in [6]. The aim is to provide a clear understanding of the architecture and the main steps involved in developing the Updatable AI Enabler Extension. For a more comprehensive understanding, it is recommended to read the referenced paper. This paper can be found in Part II, Chapter 2.

The AI-IoT architecture integrates ML capabilities with IoT systems, enabling real-time data processing, efficient communication, and intelligent decision-making on ultra-low-power devices. The architecture comprises three primary layers: Cloud, Edge Devices, and Smart MCU-based IoT Devices, each playing a crucial role in the system's functionality, as illustrated in Fig. 5.4.

The architecture workflow begins with data collection and transmission. Smart MCU-based IoT devices, equipped with sensors and actuators, collect environmental data. These devices can handle initial data acquisition. The collected data is then transmitted to edge devices where TinyML models are designed, trained, compressed, converted, tested, and validated. Edge devices also perform essential preprocessing tasks such as noise reduction, data normalization, and preliminary analysis, reducing the data volume sent to the cloud and optimizing bandwidth usage. The edge devices ensure models are continuously updated and optimized based on new data. Updated TinyML models are then deployed back to the IoT devices for local inference and real-time decisions. Finally, preprocessed data from the edge devices is sent to the cloud for extensive processing.

Figure 5.4: Basic architecture of the proposed Dynamic AI-IoT system.

The development made to the IoT firmware to integrate ML capabilities aligns with the outcome **Outcome 7** of this thesis.

On the other hand, the Updatable AI-enabled IoT architecture integrates dynamic ML capabilities with IoT systems. This architecture, illustrated in Fig. 5.5, consists of three layers:

Within the IoT layer, there are three sub-layers: Hardware, AI-enabled Firmware, and Application. The hardware sub-layer consists of the Microcontroller Unit (MCU), Random Access Memory (RAM), flash memory, and networking. The AI-enabled firmware sub-layer integrates dynamic ML capabilities into the device firmware, supporting dynamic model updates, loading, and memory optimization. The application sub-layer includes software that uses the ML models to perform specific tasks and make data-driven decisions.

In the AI layer, significant computational resources are devoted to creating TinyML models. The TinyML Development Engine operates through several phases, including data generation, splitting, model definition, training, compression, and conversion. This process ensures that predictive models are accurate, lightweight, and optimized for deployment on IoT devices. Techniques such as MobileNets, SqueezeNet, quantization, and pruning can be used to reduce model size and improve efficiency. The models are then converted into formats suitable for MCU-based IoT applications, such as C arrays or serialized files, making them easy to integrate into resource-limited environments.

Figure 5.5: Updatable AI-enabled IoT Architecture.

The AI-IoT layer acts as a bridge between the AI and IoT layers logically, focusing on dynamic Tiny Machine Learning model updates, loading, and memory optimization. MicroPython is employed in this layer due to its compatibility with various microcontrollers. Our custom MicroPython firmware, explained in the following section, facilitates real-time model updates, dynamic loading and execution of multiple TinyML models, and efficient memory usage without requiring firmware re-flashing. This layer ensures that IoT devices always have up-to-date models and can make accurate predictions while efficiently managing memory and processing resources.

The architecture eliminates the need for traditional firmware updates through several key features:

- **Dynamic Execution and Updating:** ML models can be executed, updated, and reconfigured dynamically without the need to re-flash the IoT devices, enabling ongoing development and adaptation.

- **Efficient Memory Management:** It employs sophisticated memory management techniques to handle ML tasks efficiently, ensuring optimal performance despite limited resources.
- **Connectivity and Versatility:** The architecture supports connectivity with various networks such as LoRa, LTE-M, and NB-IoT.
- **Prototyping and Validation:** The system has been prototyped and empirically validated using use cases such as gesture recognition and sine wave recognition, demonstrating its practicality and effectiveness.

The proposed architecture ensures that IoT devices, FiPy devices in our case, can dynamically interact with and adapt to new TinyML models, providing a robust framework for implementing AI-driven IoT solutions. Next subsection demonstrates the main steps toward the development of dynamic AI-enabled IoT firmware.

5.2.1 Dynamic AI-enabled IoT Firmware

The dynamic AI-IoT firmware development, which is our **Outcome 8**, focuses on extending traditional IoT firmware with an AI enabler extension to create a flexible and dynamic firmware for IoT devices, specifically the ESP32 microprocessor using MicroPython. This development process, as shown in Fig. 5.6, includes the following steps:

1. **Firmware Integration:** The firmware integrates Micropython with TFLM, enabling the execution of TinyML models on resource-constrained IoT devices. This integration allows for dynamic loading, updating, and execution of TinyML models.
2. **Dynamic Model Handling:** The firmware supports dynamic model updates, loading, and memory optimization without the need for re-flashing. This capability is crucial for maintaining and upgrading TinyML models in real-time.
3. **Model Management Functions:** Key functionalities include initialization, loading, resolving, interpreting, and inference. These functions ensure that models are efficiently managed and executed, optimizing memory usage and performance.
4. **Micropython Interface:** A new Micropython module, `microAIoT`, is created to expose

these functionalities to the user, enabling easy interaction with TinyML models through Micropython scripts. This module includes methods for initializing tensor arenas, loading models, resolving operations, setting input values, and performing inferences. 5. Compilation

Figure 5.6: Dynamic AI-enabled IoT Firmware Architecture.

and Deployment: The TFLM C++ library is compiled and integrated into the ESP-IDF framework, then linked to the Micropython framework. The resulting binary firmware is flashed onto the IoT devices, equipping them with the necessary ML capabilities.

By developing this dynamic firmware, the IoT system facilitates continuous ML model updates and optimizations, ensuring IoT devices remain flexible and capable of handling evolving ML tasks without significant downtime or manual intervention.

Fig. 5.7 illustrates the sequence of interactions and data flow in the dynamic update and utilization of TinyML models on an IoT device, the Pycom Fipy. This process ensures that the IoT device can efficiently and smoothly update its TinyML models, enabling it to adapt dynamically to new data and requirements. The diagram includes the Administrator, TinyML Development Engine, AI-enabled IoT device (Fipy), Sensors, and Actuators.

- **Model Transfer:** The process begins with the Model Transfer phase, where the TinyML Development Engine transfers a Tiny Machine Learning model to the AI-enabled IoT device, referred to as Fipy. This initial step ensures that the Fipy is equipped with the necessary ML model to perform its designated tasks.
- **Data Collection:** This phase operates in a continuous loop, indicating that data collection is an ongoing process. The Fipy device continuously interacts with the

Figure 5.7: Sequence diagram of the dynamic AI-IoT process.

Sensors to collect environmental or situational data. This collected data is then used to form the input of the ML model.

- **Model Initialization:** In this phase, the Fipy loads the ML model into its RAM and configures it, ensuring all parameters and settings are correctly applied. This step is crucial as it prepares the model for efficient and accurate inference operations.
- **Inference and Actions:** The next phase is the Inference and Actions phase, depicted as a loop. Within this loop, the Fipy prepares inputs from the collected data, runs inferences using the ML model, and performs actions via Actuators based on predictions. Feedback from the Actuators is sent back to the Fipy, verifying the actions and ensuring alignment with the inference results. This loop highlights the core functionality of the IoT device to continuously make predictions and take real-time actions.
- **Data Transmission:** This phase operates in a loop, the Fipy periodically sends performance data and updates to the TinyML Development Engine. This occurs every N inferences, where N is a predefined interval. The transmitted data includes performance metrics and any observed anomalies, which are essential for monitoring and identifying the need for updates.
- **Model Update:** The Model Update phase maintains the ML model's relevance and accuracy on the Fipy device. This phase uses an alternative construct to handle partial and full updates:
 - **Partial Update:** The Fipy requests a partial update from the Administrator. Upon approval, the Fipy requests the update from the TinyML Development Engine, which sends updated components to the Fipy.
 - **Full Update:** The Fipy requests a full update from the Administrator. After approval, the Fipy requests the update from the TinyML Development Engine, which sends a complete updated model.

- **Model Re-initialization:** Following the reception of an updated model, the Model Re-initialization phase begins. The Fipy loads the updated model into its RAM, replacing the previous version, and reconfigures it for optimal performance. This re-initialization integrates the latest model updates, ensuring the device operates with the most current and effective ML capabilities.

This detailed sequence ensures that IoT devices can dynamically adapt to new data and requirements efficiently, maintaining high performance and relevance of the ML models.

5.3 Transfer Learning IoT System Architecture

This section presents an IoT-based system designed for the continuous prediction of CO₂ exhaust concentrations in road vehicles using transfer learning. The system is a scalable and cost-effective solution aimed at monitoring and predicting CO₂ emissions, specifically designed to be installed on low-powered MCUs. The system utilizes a combination of hardware and software technologies to provide real-time monitoring and prediction capabilities. This system represents our **Outcome 3**. More details can be read in Part II, Chapter 3 of this thesis.

The architecture, as shown in Fig. 5.8, consists of several key components: a main ML model, a transfer learning dataset, transfer learning training, model optimization, model conversion, and the final Tiny Machine Learning model deployed on IoT devices. Each component plays a crucial role in ensuring the system's effectiveness and efficiency in predicting CO₂ concentrations.

Transfer Learning process:

The transfer learning process begins with a pre-trained ML model developed using extensive datasets collected from CO₂ sensors installed in vehicles. This model forms the foundation for subsequent models created through transfer learning. The process, depicted in Fig. 5.8, involves the following steps:

1. **Steps 1, 2, and 3 - Data Collection and Labeling:** Data is collected from an IoT device within the vehicle, specifically from the Controller Area Network (CAN) bus.

Figure 5.8: Transfer Learning IoT System.

This initial dataset includes various vehicle operational metrics. The main ML model generates labels by predicting CO₂ concentrations based on these parameters.

2. **Steps 4 and 5 - Weight Transfer and Training:** The labeled dataset is used to train a new model via transfer learning. Pre-trained weights from the main ML model are transferred to this new model, allowing it to leverage previously learned features and patterns, thus reducing the amount of data and time required for training.
3. **Step 6 - Model Optimization:** Post-training, the model undergoes optimization to enhance performance and reduce its size. Techniques like pruning are employed to increase sparsity, reduce overfitting, and improve generalization, making the model suitable for deployment on resource-constrained IoT devices.
4. **Steps 7 and 8 - Model Conversion:** The optimized model is converted into a format compatible with the target MCU, such as TensorFlow Lite (TFLite). This step is crucial for deploying the model on devices with limited computational resources, like the FiPy development board.

5. **Step 9 - Deployment on IoT Devices:** The final Tiny Machine Learning model is deployed on IoT devices installed in vehicles. These devices use the model to predict CO₂ concentrations in real-time.

5.3.1 Transfer Learning CO₂ Dataset and Model Development

The data flow in the system is designed to iteratively refine the transfer learning model for effective deployment on edge devices like the FiPy board. Illustrated in Fig. 5.9, the process includes data collection, preprocessing, model training, optimization, and deployment, ensuring continuous improvement in the model's accuracy and efficiency.

The CO₂ dataset was utilized to develop a predictive model for vehicle CO₂ emissions using a recurrent Long Short-term Memory (LSTM)-based Artificial Neural Network (ANN). The dataset was collected from vehicle operational data via the On-Board Diagnostics II (OBDIIIML) port, including parameters such as vehicle acceleration, engine exhaust flow rate, engine mode, engine speed, vehicle speed, mass air flow, engine coolant temperature, and hybrid battery state of charge.

The collected data was then normalized to rescale values between 0 and 1, which facilitates the model's convergence during training. The main model was trained with this normalized dataset using a batch size of 32 for 50 epochs. The architecture includes an input layer with dimensions 32x8, two stacked LSTM layers with 128 and 64 neurons respectively, and a final dense layer that outputs the predicted CO₂ as a single value. The model achieved an R² score of 97.22%, and if necessary, the model parameters were adjusted to improve accuracy.

To enhance the model further, transfer learning was employed. This process involved adapting pre-trained weights from the main model to new vehicle-specific data, thereby reducing training time and data requirements. The transfer learning model was trained for 15 epochs, achieving an improved accuracy of 97.62%. If the accuracy was not sufficient, adjustments were made to the transfer learning parameters, and the training process was repeated.

Figure 5.9: Transfer Learning-based CO2 Digital Sensor activity Diagram.

For deployment on resource-constrained edge devices, the model underwent pruning to reduce its size, increase sparsity, and enhance generalization. The pruned model was then converted to TensorFlow Lite format and further to a C array format, allowing it to run efficiently on the FiPy board for real-time CO₂ prediction.

In summary, the transfer learning dataset was utilized to develop a predictive deployment-ready Tiny Machine Learning model with enhanced performance and computational efficiency.

5.4 DevOps-Based AI-IoT System

This section presents a DevOps-based IoT system designed for the dynamic management of firmware and ML models across distributed IoT environments. The system emphasizes scalability, resource efficiency, and cost-effectiveness, ensuring smooth updates of ML models and firmware on IoT devices without requiring human intervention. This architecture leverages continuous integration and continuous deployment (CI/CD) pipelines operating across multiple platforms, utilizing technologies such as Kubernetes and GitLab-Runner. The system is tailored for microcontroller-based low-power devices capable of running TinyML models.

The architecture of the system, illustrated in Fig. 5.10, includes only key components such as Developer Environment, GitLab, CI/CD pipelines, and IoT devices such as the Pycom FiPy. Each component contributes to the system's ability to continuously and efficiently update firmware and AI models. The comprehensive architecture, including all components, is detailed in Part II, Chapter 4 of this thesis.

The system components include the following essential parts and modules that ensure the system's functionality and performance:

1. **Developer Environment:** The development process starts with the developer, who uses Git for version control. Code changes, including firmware updates and AI model improvements, are committed to a Git repository hosted on GitLab.

Figure 5.10: DevOps-based AI-IoT System.

2. **GitLab:** GitLab serves as the central platform for managing the repositories and CI/CD pipelines. It hosts multiple repositories, including Firmware Development, Data Collection,

AI Model Development. Each repository can trigger its own pipeline, facilitating independent development and deployment workflows.

3. **CI/CD Pipelines:** CI/CD pipelines automate the process of building, testing, and deploying applications. For example, the firmware pipeline compiles the firmware, packages it into a Docker container, and deploys it to the target IoT device. Similarly, the AI model pipeline involves training the model, optimizing it, converting it to a suitable format, and deploying it to the IoT devices.

4. **Kubernetes Cluster:** The Kubernetes cluster, composed of a master node and several worker nodes, orchestrates the deployment of containers. The master node manages the deployments, while the worker nodes execute the tasks. For instance, Raspberry Pi devices are used as worker nodes to handle data collection, AI model deployment, and firmware updates.

5. **IoT Devices:** The IoT devices, primarily Pycom FiPy boards, are equipped with ESP32 microcontrollers. These devices connect to the internet and request firmware and AI model updates via HTTP REST APIs. The updated firmware or AI model is downloaded, verified, and applied using Over-The-Air (OTA) mechanisms.

The data flow within the system is designed to ensure the integration and updates across all components. The process includes:

1. **Code Commit:** Developers commit code changes to the GitLab repository, triggering the CI/CD pipeline.

2. **Pipeline Execution:** The CI/CD pipeline executes various jobs, including building the application, running tests, packaging the application into a Docker container, and pushing the container to the registry.

3. **Deployment:** Kubernetes handles the deployment of the containerized application to the appropriate worker nodes. The deployment configuration specifies details such as the deployment name, image URL, container name, and port.

4. **OTA Updates:** IoT devices request updates from the Kubernetes worker nodes. The REST API application on the worker node responds with the updated firmware or AI model.

The IoT device downloads the update, verifies its integrity using hash functions, and applies the update.

The deployment process consists of the following steps:

1. **Firmware Update process:** The firmware update process involves fetching the latest firmware updates, building the firmware image, storing it in the registry, deploying it to the Kubernetes cluster, and updating the IoT devices via OTA. The IoT devices restart to apply the new firmware.

2. **AI Model Update process:** The AI model update process includes fetching the latest TensorFlow model, optimizing the model, converting it to TensorFlow Lite (TFLite) format, converting the TFLite model to a C array format, and deploying the updated model to the IoT devices.

By integrating DevOps mechanisms with modern software technologies, the system ensures efficient, scalable, and automated updates, significantly enhancing operational efficiency and resource utilization. This approach offers a practical and scalable solution for the dynamic and continuous improvement of AI models and firmware in IoT ecosystems.

Chapter 6

Integrated Dynamic AI-IoT Framework

Building upon the architectural foundations presented in Chapter 5, this chapter introduces the Integrated Dynamic AI-IoT Framework. Chapter 5 laid the groundwork with individual architectures, focusing on the IoT monitoring system, AI-enabled capabilities, transfer learning, and DevOps automation. This chapter integrates these elements into a cohesive system designed to facilitate the continuous deployment and updating of ML models across IoT devices.

The integrated framework described in this chapter consolidates the outcomes presented in Chapter 5 into a single, scalable solution, ensuring the real-time deployment of ML models and updates. This framework is structured to address Objective 8 by integrating the diverse components discussed previously, including ML inference, data collection, and model updates, into a single, operational system.

By achieving this integration, the framework ensures that the various components, such as data collection infrastructure, predictive models, and DevOps pipelines, work together seamlessly to support continuous updates and model training across multiple use cases, including CO₂ concentration prediction, gesture recognition, and other real-time applications.

This unified framework represents the culmination of the work presented throughout the thesis, demonstrating how these components can be applied collectively to enable a robust and adaptive Edge-to-IoT solution.

6.1 Overview of the Framework

The Integrated Dynamic AI-IoT Framework establishes a structured approach for managing the whole life-cycle of Tiny Machine Learning model updates, facilitating efficient ML capability integration within IoT devices. It comprises four main architectural network segments: Edge, Kubernetes Cluster, IoT Devices, and Sensors. Each segment plays a crucial role in the AI-IoT life-cycle:

Figure 6.1: Integrated Dynamic AI-IoT Framework for Tiny Machine Learning model Updates.

1. **Edge Network Segment:** The central edge computing server responsible for design, development, validation, and deployment activities, i.e. managing the whole life-cycle of model updates. This component includes:
 - **GitLab Repositories:** Four primary repositories for Firmware, Data Acquisition, ML Training, and ML Model Optimization & Conversion. See number 1, 2, 3, and 4 in Fig. 6.1.
 - **GitLab Runner:** CI/CD pipelines that build, test, package, and deploy components from the repositories. See number 5, 6, and 7 in Fig. 6.1.
2. **Kubernetes Cluster:** Manages deployments, orchestrating the distribution of firmware and TinyML models to various IoT devices. See number 8 and 9 in Fig. 6.1.
3. **IoT Devices:** Receives updates and performs data collection and processing tasks. See number 10 in Fig. 6.1.
4. **Sensors:** Collects data relevant to specific applications, such as environmental monitoring and gesture recognition. See number 11 in Fig. 6.1.

6.2 Component Description

6.2.1 GitLab Repositories

Within the GitLab environment, separate repositories are created for distinct development activities, as shown in Fig. 6.1. Each repository is dedicated to a specific function:

1. Firmware Repository (Number 1)

This repository maintains the latest versions of two compiled firmware packages, both updated and ready for deployment, described as follows:

- **AI-enabled ESP Firmware:** Specifically designed for ESP microcontrollers, this firmware supports ML functionalities (**Outcome 7**).

- **Dynamic AI-enabled MicroPython Firmware:** A flexible firmware leveraging MicroPython, an optimized Python interpreter for microcontrollers, to enable dynamic ML capabilities (**Outcome 8**).

The development of these firmware solutions is summarized in Chapters 5 and 5.2. For a detailed version, refer to the published paper (**Outcome 2**) in Part II, Chapter 11.

2. Data Acquisition Repository (Number 2)

The data acquisition repository contains custom data collectors tailored for various sensors integrated into IoT devices, designed to gather data for specific applications:

- **Aquaponics Data Collector:** Gathers data on water quality, temperature, pH levels, and other metrics related to aquaponics systems.
- **Gesture Recognition Data Collector:** Captures data for recognizing gestures using sensors like accelerometers.
- **CO2 Data Collector:** Monitors CO2 levels, which is essential for applications in environmental monitoring and indoor air quality assessment.
- **Grafana:** Provides visualization and monitoring capabilities, allowing real-time insights into data collection and model performance.

For detailed insights into data acquisition, refer to Part II, Chapter 10 and Chapter 12.

3. AI Training Repository (Number 3)

This repository focuses on the training and re-training of ML models using the data collected by various sensors. It supports a comprehensive ML training process involving several phases:

- **TensorFlow AI Model:** The primary AI model developed using TensorFlow, a widely utilized deep learning framework.
- **AI Training:** Collected datasets (e.g., CO2 datasets) for model training.

- **Transfer Learning (TL) TensorFlow AI Model:** Applies transfer learning techniques, where a pre-trained model is adapted to new tasks using domain-specific datasets, such as the TL-based CO2 dataset.

For example, the CO2 dataset collected by the CO2 data collectors is used to train models specifically for CO2 concentration prediction. Transfer learning is employed to improve the model's accuracy and efficiency. This approach led to a significant outcome in this thesis (**Outcome 9**), demonstrating that transfer learning-based TinyML models outperform conventional CO2 models in terms of accuracy.

4. AI Model Optimization & Conversion Repository (Number 4)

This repository handles the conversion of trained TensorFlow AI models into TinyML models suitable for deployment on resource-constrained IoT devices. It includes three key components:

- **TensorFlow Lite AI Model:** A lightweight version of the TensorFlow model, optimized for edge devices with limited computational resources.
- **C Array Model Conversion:** Converts AI models into C arrays, a common format for microcontroller deployment.
- **TL-based CO2 TinyML Model:** The final optimized AI model specifically designed for TinyML platforms.

It is important to note that each repository is associated with a CI/CD pipeline. This allows readers to follow the deployment steps, which are described in detail in Section 6.2.3.

6.2.2 GitLab Runner

The GitLab Runner plays a pivotal role in automating the CI/CD pipelines within the dynamic AI-IoT framework. Its key functions include:

- **Continuous Integration (CI):** Automatically triggers the build process upon code commits or updates, compiling, testing, and packaging applications into Docker containers.

- **Continuous Deployment (CD):** Deploys the packaged Docker containers to the container registry and orchestrates their deployment onto the Kubernetes cluster, ensuring firmware and AI model updates are promptly delivered to IoT devices.
- **Pipeline Management:** Manages multiple pipelines for firmware development, AI model training, and data acquisition, executing jobs in a predefined sequence for efficient workflow.
- **Monitoring and Logging:** Provides real-time feedback on job status, with logs and updates enabling developers to quickly address issues.
- **Scalability and Resource Allocation:** Distributes workloads across multiple machines to handle large-scale deployments, accommodating an increasing number of IoT devices and growing data volumes.

6.2.3 CI/CD Pipelines

-Firmware CI/CD Pipeline (Number 5)

This pipeline builds the firmware, tests it for errors and vulnerabilities, and packages it for deployment. After packaging, the firmware image is released and deployed through a container registry to the Kubernetes cluster and subsequently to the IoT devices. The integration process includes an OTA Firmware Updater that enables remote updates, allowing IoT devices to receive new AI models and firmware dynamically without manual intervention.

-Data Collector CI/CD Pipeline (Number 6)

This pipeline is responsible for building, testing, and deploying data collectors. Once a data collector is developed, the CI/CD pipeline is triggered. The GitLab Runner containerizes the application, pushes it to the registry, and, upon request, deploys it to the IoT device via the REST API application. This pipeline facilitates the implementation of the Edge-based data collector (**Outcome 5**).

-TinyML Model CI/CD Pipeline (Number 7)

This pipeline is dedicated to the TinyML models. It handles the processes of building, testing, and deploying ML models that are optimized for execution on IoT devices. The

models are designed to be lightweight and efficient, suitable for deployment in environments with constrained computational resources.

Within the CI/CD pipeline, TensorFlow Lite ML models are converted into C array models, which are optimized for execution on microcontrollers. The deployment process follows a systematic data flow, beginning with the Docker containerization of the Tiny Machine Learning model and culminating in its deployment to the target IoT devices.

6.2.4 Kubernetes Cluster

The Kubernetes Cluster is a vital component for managing the deployment and orchestration of ML models, firmware, and data collectors across the IoT ecosystem. It comprises:

- **Master Node (Number 8):** The central controller responsible for managing deployments across various worker nodes. It orchestrates the deployment processes and ensures efficient resource allocation.
- **Worker Nodes (Number 9):** Execute deployment instructions from the master node. Each worker node manages local deployments, including firmware updates, data collectors, and TinyML models, thereby supporting scalability and facilitating large-scale deployments.

6.2.5 IoT Devices

Within the AI-IoT Framework, several IoT devices, Number 10 in Fig. 6.1, are managed to perform specific functions and adapt dynamically to changing conditions. For example, in order to predict CO₂ concentration dynamically, IoT device should contain and/or support the following:

-**OTA Firmware Updater:** Provides over-the-air updates to the IoT devices, ensuring that the firmware and TinyML models are kept up to date without needing manual intervention.

-**CO₂ Data Collector:** Represents the firmware and data collection logic running on the IoT devices, specifically handling CO₂ data collection in this example.

-**Dynamic AI-enabled MicroPython Firmware:** A flexible framework running on the device that allows for dynamic updates and modifications to the AI logic.

6.2.6 Sensors

Complementing the IoT devices, the AI-IoT Framework also incorporates a diverse range of sensors, Number 11 in Fig. 6.1, that provide the necessary data inputs for AI-driven processes. For example:

-**Water Quality Sensors:** Sensors that measure various parameters related to water quality, like temperature, pH, dissolved oxygen, etc., useful for aquaponics systems.

-**Accelerometer Sensor:** Used for gesture recognition and movement detection, often in applications like wearables or robotics.

-**Vehicle Sensors:** Sensors installed in vehicles for monitoring various environmental and mechanical parameters, possibly including CO2 levels, speed, acceleration, etc.

6.3 End-to-End Integrated Sequence Diagram

The following sequence diagram outlines the step-by-step flow of data and operations between various components of the framework.

The sequence diagram in Fig. 6.2 illustrates the comprehensive data flow and interaction among the components involved in the framework:

Figure 6.2: Sequence Diagram of the General Data Flow in the Integrated Dynamic AI-IoT Framework.

1. Code Commit and Pipeline Trigger:

The process begins when the *Developer* commits code changes to one or more of the following repositories: Firmware Repository, Data Acquisition Repository, AI Training Repository, or AI Model Optimization & Conversion Repository (Steps 1, 3, 5, 7). Each commit triggers a Continuous Integration/Continuous Deployment (CI/CD) pipeline managed by the *GitLab Runner* (Steps 2, 4, 6, 8).

2. Build, Test, and Containerization:

The *GitLab Runner* starts the CI/CD pipeline for each repository. It builds the applications, executes tests, and packages them into Docker containers. The Docker containers are then pushed to the *Container Registry* (Step 9).

3. Deployment of Applications:

The *GitLab Runner* coordinates with the *Kubernetes Cluster* to deploy the containerized applications (Step 10). The *Kubernetes Cluster* distributes the containers (such as firmware, data collectors, and TinyML models) to the appropriate *IoT Devices* through its worker nodes (Step 11), ensuring that each device has the latest software and model updates.

4. Data Collection and Publishing:

Once the deployment is complete, the *IoT Devices* start collecting data using the deployed data collectors. This data is then published to the *MQTT Server* (Step 12), which acts as a central hub for aggregating all sensor data.

5. Data Utilization for AI Training:

The collected data is forwarded from the *MQTT Server* to the *AI Training Repository* (Step 13). Here, it is utilized to train or retrain AI models, which can then be optimized and converted for TinyML deployment.

6. Request for Updates (AI Models/Firmware):

The *IoT Devices* periodically request updates such as new AI models or OTA firmware

updates from the *REST API Application* (Step 14). The *REST API Application* checks with the *GitLab Runner* for the latest updates (Step 15).

7. Provision of Updates:

The *GitLab Runner* confirms and provides the necessary updates to the *REST API Application* (Step 16), which then sends them to the requesting *IoT Devices* (Step 17). The devices download, verify, and apply the updates, ensuring they always run the latest versions.

8. Application of Updates:

The *IoT Devices* apply the updates received (AI models, firmware, etc.) and integrate them into their operational workflows (Step 18).

The Integrated Dynamic AI-IoT Framework presented in this chapter demonstrates a robust and scalable approach to managing AI model and firmware updates within an IoT ecosystem. By integrating various components—Edge, Kubernetes Cluster, IoT Devices, and Sensors—this framework facilitates a smooth flow of data, code, and models, enabling efficient deployment and management of AI capabilities across IoT devices. Through automated CI/CD pipelines, dynamic model updating, and continuous monitoring, this framework ensures that IoT devices remain up-to-date and capable of performing complex AI tasks, thus driving forward the capabilities of AI-integrated IoT systems.

Chapter 7

Performance Evaluation

This chapter is aimed to assess the performance of the presented dynamic AI-IoT framework. To do that, first a performance evaluation of different models accuracy is carried out. Later on, an evaluation of the performance of the AI-enabled CO₂ sensor data acquisition is analyzed. Finally, the overall average time for Tiny Machine Learning model deployment is discussed. The evaluation experiments were conducted in alignment with the system architecture depicted in Fig. 6.1.

Furthermore, it is noted that individual performance evaluations of several of the components involved in the execution of the presented dynamic AI-IoT framework have been addressed in the outcomes that conform Part II, and that therefore, this information has either been ignored or briefly referenced in this chapter. Nonetheless, this performance evaluation chapter has focused on other relevant aspects worth evaluating for the completeness of the presented work.

7.1 Evaluation of CO₂ Prediction Models

This section provides an overview of the ground truth data, the validation and verification cycle, and the comparison of model performance across different configurations. The primary aim is to present a clear and structured evaluation of how different models—specifically a full neural network (NN) model, a TinyML NN model, and a Transfer Learning-based

Figure 7.1: Comparison of Transfer Learning model with Neural Network (NN) model before and after TensorFlow-Lite conversion.

model—perform in predicting CO₂ concentration levels, which are essential for assessing vehicle exhaust emissions.

1. Ground Truth Data:

The ground truth in this study represents actual CO₂ concentration levels, measured in parts per million (PPM), collected using a physical sensor. These measurements reflect real-world variations in CO₂ levels, capturing fluctuations caused by dynamic changes in vehicle exhaust emissions. The ground truth data serves as the benchmark against which all model predictions are evaluated.

The sensor used for measuring CO₂ levels was calibrated and verified prior to data collection to ensure that the data was accurate and reliable. Calibration procedures included comparing the sensor's readings to those of a known reference sensor, and any discrepancies were addressed by recalibrating the sensor according to the manufacturer's standards. Only after successful verification was the sensor used to gather data for model training and evaluation.

In the results presented here, the blue line in Fig. 7.1 represents the ground truth values. It showcases the dynamic nature of CO₂ concentration, including both gradual and rapid

changes, which are essential for assessing the effectiveness of the models in predicting real-world emissions.

2. Validation and Verification Cycle:

Before beginning the experimentation phase, a rigorous validation and verification cycle was employed to ensure the reliability and accuracy of the sensor data used in training and testing the models. The verification process was carried out by cross-checking the sensor's measurements against a reference standard. This step was crucial to ensure that any potential errors in the sensor's readings would not compromise the validity of the results.

If any calibration issues were identified during this verification cycle, the sensor was recalibrated before data collection. This ensured that only high-quality, accurate data was used for training the ML models. Additionally, to further validate the sensor's readings, multiple iterations of data were collected to capture a wide range of CO₂ fluctuations, making the dataset robust and representative of real-world conditions.

3. Model Performance Comparison:

Once the sensor data was verified and validated, several models were trained to predict CO₂ concentration levels. These models were evaluated by comparing their predictions against the ground truth data.

- **Ground Truth (Blue Line):**

This line represents the actual CO₂ concentration data collected from the sensor. It serves as the benchmark for evaluating the predictive accuracy of the models.

- **Full NN-Based Model Before TF-Lite Conversion (Orange Line):**

The orange line shows the performance of the full neural network (NN) model trained using TensorFlow on a conventional computing platform. This model achieved an accuracy of 97.22% before being converted for deployment on constrained hardware. The orange line closely follows the blue ground truth line, demonstrating the high predictive accuracy of the model.

- **TinyML NN-Based Model After TF-Lite Conversion (Green Dashed Line):**

The green dashed line represents the predictions of the same NN model after it was

converted to TensorFlow Lite (TF-Lite) format for deployment on a microcontroller unit (MCU). The conversion process optimized the model for resource-constrained environments but led to a reduction in accuracy to 87.15%. This drop in performance is visible in the deviations of the green line from the ground truth, particularly during rapid fluctuations in CO₂ levels.

- **Transfer Learning Model After TF-Lite Conversion (Purple Dotted Line):**

The purple dotted line represents the predictions of the Transfer Learning model after it was also converted to TF-Lite format. Despite the conversion to a constrained environment, the Transfer Learning approach allowed the model to retain much of its accuracy, achieving an impressive 97.77% accuracy. The purple line closely follows the blue ground truth line, indicating that Transfer Learning preserved the model's performance even with the reduced resources of the target hardware.

4. Data Source and Model Contributions:

The dataset used for training and evaluation in this study was sourced from a physical CO₂ sensor deployed in a real-world setting. The sensor captured data on vehicle exhaust emissions over multiple iterations, providing a robust dataset for model training and testing. The sensor readings were validated for accuracy, ensuring that they served as reliable ground truth for comparison.

The primary contribution of this work lies in the application of Transfer Learning to enhance the performance of a CO₂ concentration prediction model, especially when deployed in resource-constrained environments such as IoT devices. This approach allowed the model to retain its predictive capabilities after being converted to a more efficient format (TF-Lite), overcoming the performance degradation typically seen in models deployed on IoT hardware.

This study builds on the work of Tena et al. (2023) [43], which developed a recurrent LSTM-based model to predict CO₂ concentrations based on vehicle operational parameters. While their model was trained on a conventional computing platform, the current work adapts this model for deployment on an ESP32-based processor, demonstrating how Transfer

Learning can help mitigate performance losses when converting models for deployment on resource-constrained devices.

5. Model Training and Optimization:

- **Initial Model Training:** The NN model was initially trained on a conventional computing platform using TensorFlow. This model achieved a high accuracy of 97.22%, demonstrating its ability to capture the variations in CO₂ concentration accurately.
- **TF-Lite Conversion:** To deploy the model on an ESP32-based microcontroller, the model was converted to TensorFlow Lite (TF-Lite). This conversion reduced the model's complexity to fit the constraints of the target hardware, but it also resulted in a drop in accuracy to 87.15%, primarily due to limitations in supported operations on the TF-Lite platform.
- **Transfer Learning Optimization:** To address this loss in accuracy, a Transfer Learning approach was employed. By leveraging pre-trained weights and biases, Transfer Learning allowed the model to retain much of its performance even after the TF-Lite conversion. The resulting model achieved an accuracy of 97.77%, outperforming the initial NN model before conversion.

The findings of this study highlight the effectiveness of Transfer Learning in preserving the performance of ML models deployed on resource-constrained devices.

7.2 TinyML Transfer Learning Model Deployment Time

The deployment of ML models into microcontroller-based IoT devices, such as the FiPy board, involves a multi-stage process that is both critical and complex. This process is essential for ensuring the seamless and automated updating of ML models on edge devices, especially in resource-constrained environments. The activity diagram in Fig. 7.2 provides a detailed overview of the TinyML Transfer Learning model deployment process, which is managed through a DevOps-based framework utilizing CI/CD pipelines powered by GitLab-Runner and Kubernetes.

The deployment process is designed to efficiently transition ML models from development to deployment on edge devices, such as the FiPy board. The workflow is divided into several key stages:

Figure 7.2: TinyML Transfer Learning Model Deployment Activity Diagram.

1. Initiation of the Deployment Process:

The deployment process is triggered by the DevOps framework, which uses CI/CD pipelines to automate and streamline the flow. The process begins by preparing the model for deployment, ensuring that all pre-deployment conditions are met.

2. Model Preparation:

The first critical stage involves building the ML model's Docker image. This step is the most time-consuming, taking approximately 338.24 seconds. During this phase, the Transfer Learning model is compiled and packaged into a Docker image, which is necessary for portability and consistency across different environments. The time taken for this stage can be denoted as

$$T_{\text{Docker_Build}} = 338.24 \text{ seconds.}$$

This step introduces overhead, as the time taken for image creation can significantly impact the overall deployment pipeline.

Advantages:

Building Docker images during deployment allows for dynamic updates to the model and its dependencies, ensuring the latest versions are always used. This flexibility is crucial for environments where updates are frequent.

Challenges:

If a pre-built image is not readily available, the time spent building a new Docker image may delay the deployment process, especially in time-critical applications. For example, in industrial IoT systems monitoring environmental parameters, such delays could hinder timely responses to changes.

For instance, consider a company like Tesla deploying a software update for its self-driving system. The Docker image for the update would need to be prepared, tested, and deployed across thousands of vehicles. If the image-building process is delayed, it could postpone the release, impacting customer experience and system reliability. To address this, pre-building and storing Docker images for commonly deployed configurations could significantly reduce deployment times in future updates.

Therefore, by pre-building Docker images during non-critical periods, the deployment process can bypass this step, saving 338.24 seconds on average. This optimization would be particularly impactful for systems requiring frequent model updates or real-time responses.

3. Deployment to Kubernetes Worker:

Once the Docker image is ready, the model is deployed to a Kubernetes worker node. This stage takes 31.41 seconds and involves distributing the model within the Kubernetes cluster to orchestrate the deployment process. Kubernetes provides a scalable and efficient environment to handle multiple deployments and updates seamlessly. The time taken for this stage can be represented as

$$T_{\text{K8S_Deployment}} = 31.41 \text{ seconds.}$$

4. Transfer to Edge Device:

After successful deployment to the Kubernetes worker, the next step is to transfer the ML model to the FiPy board. This transfer is crucial for bringing the model closer to the data source for real-time processing. This step takes 5.05 seconds. The time for this transfer

process is given by

$$T_{\text{Transfer_FiPy}} = 5.05 \text{ seconds.}$$

5. Real-Time Model Update:

In many cases, the model on the FiPy board may need updates to reflect new data or improved algorithms. This step is designed to be swift, taking only 2 seconds. The fast update time is significant for applications that require real-time data processing and quick adaptation to changing environments. The time for this update is denoted as

$$T_{\text{Model_Update}} = 2.00 \text{ seconds.}$$

6. Error Handling and Decision Points:

The diagram also highlights decision points where checks are made to determine if the model is ready for deployment on the edge device or if an update is needed. In case of deployment errors, a handling mechanism is in place to manage and resolve any issues effectively, ensuring reliability and robustness in the deployment process.

7. Discussion of Total Deployment Time

The total time taken for the complete deployment process, from the initial model preparation to the final model update on the FiPy board, can be calculated by summing the times of all individual stages. The total deployment time, T_{Total} , is given by:

$$T_{\text{Total}} = T_{\text{Docker_Build}} + T_{\text{K8S_Deployment}} + T_{\text{Transfer_FiPy}} + T_{\text{Model_Update}}$$

Substituting the values:

$$T_{\text{Total}} = 338.24 + 31.41 + 5.05 + 2.00 = 376.70 \text{ seconds}$$

Therefore, the overall average deployment time for deploying a TinyML Transfer Learning model from development to an edge device like the FiPy board, based on 10 deployments, is approximately 376.70 seconds.

While this time is reasonable for many applications, the Docker image-building stage represents the most significant portion of this duration, accounting for approximately 89.7

Implications:

- In scenarios where time is critical, optimizing or bypassing the Docker image-building step can drastically reduce deployment times.
- Leveraging pre-built Docker images or container registries can eliminate the need for image-building during deployment, reducing latency and improving efficiency.

Future Recommendations:

- **Pre-Built Images:** Organizations can maintain a repository of pre-built Docker images for commonly deployed configurations, significantly decreasing deployment times.
- **Automated Optimization:** Tools like Docker layer caching and incremental builds can further reduce the image-building duration.

Real-World Relevance: Companies such as Google and Microsoft, which frequently deploy ML updates to cloud and edge systems, optimize their CI/CD pipelines by caching and reusing Docker images. This practice minimizes downtime, ensuring rapid delivery of updates to end-users.

Measuring Transfer Learning deployment time is essential to validate the efficiency of the DevOps-based framework and its suitability for frequent model updates or customizations. It benchmarks the framework's capability to handle complex workflows efficiently, ensuring scalability and practicality. The results also guide future optimizations, highlighting areas where latency can be reduced to enhance deployment efficiency and adaptability. This performance evaluation provides crucial insights into the feasibility of deploying ML models in resource-constrained environments like microcontroller-based IoT devices.

7.3 AI-enabled IoT Firmware Update Time

Efficient firmware updates are critical in AI-enabled IoT systems to ensure devices are secure, functional, and up-to-date, particularly in large-scale or remote deployments. The proposed

framework integrates an OTA firmware update mechanism that allows dynamic updates with minimal downtime.

To assess the efficiency of this update mechanism, we measured the time required to update the firmware on IoT devices over 10 iterations. The average time for these updates was 33.29 seconds, indicating the framework's ability to perform timely updates in realistic deployment scenarios. This result demonstrates that the AI-enabled system can handle frequent firmware updates efficiently, an essential capability for maintaining the performance and security of connected IoT devices.

Chapter 8

Limitations

The proposed dynamic AI-IoT framework, which integrates various components such as the IoD Water Environment System, graphical monitoring tools, AI-enabled microbiome frameworks, transfer learning approaches, and DevOps methodologies, faces several key limitations that span across resource constraints, interoperability, energy efficiency, scalability, security, and the handling of large ML models. Additionally, limitations arise from the specific implementations and experiments conducted throughout this research, which have implications for future development and deployment in real-world environments.

1. IoT Water Environment System Limitations

The IoT water environment system encountered several limitations that impacted the performance and scalability of its ML models. The restricted access to the testing environment limited the ability to collect comprehensive datasets necessary for training robust ML models, thereby affecting their accuracy and effectiveness and as a result, the system's ability to adapt dynamically to varying scenarios is diminished. Moreover, the system's reliance on multiple communication technologies—such as Wi-Fi, MQTT, LoRa, and LoRaWAN—introduced complexities. Specifically, the LoRa technology, with a maximum payload size of 128 bytes, required specialized encoding to fit sensor measurements within the limited packet size. This limitation poses challenges for transmitting more complex data or supporting a higher number of sensors.

The sensors used in the system also presented durability issues, needing replacement and recalibration annually, which is a labor-intensive process involving specialized equipment. This restriction could increase maintenance efforts and costs, limiting the system's long-term viability and ease of deployment at scale. Furthermore, as the system was designed to support multiple farms and sensors, it faced potential network congestion and packet collisions, particularly with LoRa technology, which shares the same frequency. This raised concerns about the scalability and robustness of the system in handling an increasing number of sensors and farms, which was not fully tested in this study.

The Grafana-based graphical monitoring tool, while effective for real-time data visualization and basic statistical analysis, lacked advanced analytical capabilities and sophisticated alerting mechanisms. This limitation reduced the system's ability to proactively detect and respond to significant changes in the water environment, which is critical for dynamic and adaptive management. Additionally, the system's scope was primarily limited to data collection and visualization without capabilities for taking automated actions, such as opening or closing water pipes. This narrowed the potential impact and functionality of the system in real-world water management scenarios.

2. Limitations in Deploying ML on Resource-Constrained IoT Devices

Deploying ML models on resource-constrained IoT devices presents several challenges, particularly related to computational power, memory, energy efficiency, and handling of large ML models. The AI-enabled MicroPython framework, utilized in this research, faced significant limitations due to the restricted hardware capabilities of target devices such as FiPy, which can accommodate ML models only up to 2.4 MB in size. These devices require the use of TensorFlow Lite, a lightweight version of the full TensorFlow library specifically designed for low-power devices. However, TensorFlow Lite supports a reduced set of operators, limiting the expressiveness and functionality of the ML models that can be deployed on these devices. This limitation restricts the deployment of complex ML models, reducing the system's capacity to handle sophisticated analytics and decision-making.

The limited memory and processing power of devices like FiPy further constrain the deployment of more complex ML models. For instance, deploying models larger than

500 KB poses significant challenges due to memory constraints, necessitating the use of model optimization techniques such as compression, quantization, and pruning. While these techniques effectively reduce model size and make deployment feasible, they often introduce trade-offs between model complexity, accuracy, and performance which could compromise model effectiveness, particularly in critical, real-time applications. Therefore, balancing these factors to achieve optimal performance without exceeding device capabilities is a key challenge that requires ongoing refinement of optimization methods.

Another major limitation is energy efficiency. Continuous operation of ML pipelines on IoT devices can lead to high energy consumption, adversely impacting battery life, especially for ultra-low-power devices intended for long-term deployment in remote or inaccessible locations. Frequent updates to ML models and firmware, which are necessary for maintaining model accuracy and relevance, can exacerbate energy consumption issues. This high energy consumption limits the practicality of deploying the framework in remote, long-term scenarios where battery life is critical. This impacts the system's sustainability and reliability in field conditions. Optimizing for energy efficiency while maintaining low latency for real-time applications is a complex task that demands innovative solutions to ensure sustainable operation.

The handling of large ML models on these resource-constrained devices requires further advancements in optimization techniques. While current methods like model pruning, quantization, and neural architecture search (NAS) have enabled the deployment of moderately sized models, the need to continually refine these techniques remains critical to balance accuracy, performance, and resource utilization effectively. This limitation remains inadequate, restricting the framework's scalability and reducing its flexibility to address diverse applications beyond the tested scenarios. Achieving this balance is essential for enhancing the capabilities of ML models on constrained devices without compromising on computational load, energy efficiency, or real-time responsiveness.

3. Transfer Learning Approach Limitations

The transfer learning approach employed in this system also had several notable limitations. The primary concern was the cost and resource requirements associated with

deploying edge-based ML training for each new data provider. As the number of data providers scales up, the computational resources and associated costs increase significantly, making the approach less feasible for large-scale deployment. Additionally, the approach was only tested with a single model architecture for both source and destination models, limiting the exploration of alternative architectures or partial transfer learning techniques that could potentially offer better performance or versatility. This limitation restricts adaptability to diverse datasets or tasks, reducing the framework's generalization capabilities. Moreover, the dataset used for the CO₂ concentration task was collected under standardized conditions, and the system's performance in more diverse, real-world conditions remains unvalidated. On top of that, advanced transfer learning techniques have not been explored such as knowledge distillation.

4. DevOps Approach and Future Validations

The AI-enabled DevOps framework designed for this system demonstrated limitations in terms of integration, automation, and generalizability. The framework was validated only on a single IoT device and specific ML frameworks, such as TensorFlow, necessitating further validation with other IoT devices and ML frameworks to prove its generic applicability. This limited validation scope undermines the framework's claim of generalizability, reducing confidence in its broader applicability across different devices and ML frameworks. The conversion process between TensorFlow and TensorFlow Lite also explored only a limited set of techniques, such as quantization and neuron pruning, without investigating alternative methods that could potentially improve accuracy and model efficiency. The limited exploration of model conversion techniques limits opportunities to enhance model accuracy and efficiency.

5. Interoperability and Security Concerns

The dynamic AI-IoT framework also faced interoperability challenges due to the heterogeneous nature of IoT environments. Devices from different manufacturers often use diverse communication protocols and standards, complicating reliable communication and data exchange. Middleware solutions are needed to bridge these gaps, but the fragmented IoT ecosystem further complicates integration and the deployment of scalable, unified solutions.

These interoperability issues create barriers to integrating the framework across diverse IoT ecosystems. Integrating ML with IoT devices also raises significant security and privacy concerns, particularly given that many IoT devices collect sensitive data. Implementing robust security measures, such as encryption and secure boot processes, is essential but can introduce additional computational overhead, further impacting device performance and energy efficiency.

The identified limitations, including data collection constraints, resource limitations, and scalability issues, significantly impact the effectiveness of the dynamic AI-IoT framework. Restricted access to diverse datasets limits the robustness of ML models, while the limited computational power and memory of IoT devices, like FiPy, hinder the deployment of complex models. Optimization techniques such as pruning and quantization help mitigate these limitations but may reduce model accuracy. Additionally, network congestion and transfer learning costs limit scalability, while security and interoperability challenges further complicate real-world deployment.

In conclusion, while the proposed dynamic AI-IoT framework presents significant advancements in integrating ML with IoT environments, the above limitations highlight areas that require further research and development. Future work should focus on optimizing resource utilization, enhancing energy efficiency, ensuring seamless interoperability, strengthening security and privacy measures, and improving the handling of large ML models. Addressing these challenges is crucial for realizing the full potential of dynamic ML in IoT applications and ensuring their successful deployment in diverse, real-world scenarios.

Chapter 9

Conclusions and Future Work

In this thesis, significant progress has been made in developing a dynamic AI-IoT system capable of efficiently managing and deploying TinyML models on resource-constrained IoT devices. The research aim and objectives were successfully achieved, resulting in a system that demonstrates the potential for advanced ML functionalities in constrained environments. This chapter summarizes the key achievements, contributions, and results obtained and outlines future work for each major component.

This PhD research focused on developing advanced IoT systems for various applications, including aquaponics monitoring, dynamic ML model deployment on ultra-low-power devices, CO₂ prediction in vehicles, and AI-IoT DevOps frameworks. The outcomes demonstrate significant advancements in enhancing the intelligence, efficiency, and sustainability of IoT ecosystems through innovative AI integration, optimized resource management, and scalable deployment strategies.

The research achieved the following:

- 1. IoT-Based Aquaponics Monitoring System:** The proposed IoT-based aquaponics system addresses key gaps in the current state-of-the-art by enabling comprehensive monitoring of aquaponic environments, particularly for the fishery industry. The system demonstrated effective performance for both local and networked environments, leveraging LoRa for long-range communication between nodes and gateways and 5G (LTE-M/NB-IoT) for internet connectivity. Performance evaluations revealed that the most time-consuming

sensing processes are related to digital sensors requiring compensation, with times ranging from 0.9 to 1.5 seconds. Meanwhile, analog sensors exhibited faster performance, with an average time of 0.3 seconds. Overall, the average cycle time for collecting data from 9 sensors was around 7.5 seconds. The average time for transmitting sensor data from a node to the central server (CORE) was approximately 463 ms. To improve energy efficiency, the system incorporated a switching IC (74HC237) for sensors connected to the I2C line, resulting in a 70% extension in battery life. These enhancements make the proposed solution a robust, low-power, and scalable choice for real-time monitoring in aquaculture.

Moreover, this research assisted to create a data collection infrastructure for real-time water quality monitoring and CO₂ concentration predictions, which demonstrated the system's ability to handle real-world environmental data with high accuracy.

2. Dynamic AI-IoT Framework for Ultra-Low-Power Devices: This research also introduced a novel architecture that integrates Dynamic ML capabilities into ultra-low-power IoT devices using a Micropython-based framework. The proposed system demonstrated excellent performance in loading and executing TinyML models, achieving 136,000 model loads and over 2,000 executions of a 20 KB model in less than a second. This framework provides significant advancements, including dynamic loading and execution of multiple ML models, autonomous memory management, and remote updates with minimal impact on system performance. The Dynamic AI-IoT system achieved near real-time inference capabilities with power consumption below 0.5 Watts, underscoring its suitability for various domains, including industrial IoT, agriculture, smart cities, and environmental monitoring.

The deployment of TinyML models in these contexts showed the potential for practical applications in environmental monitoring, enabling dynamic ML functionalities, self-configuration of ML models, memory management optimization, and dynamic loading and execution on ultra-low-power devices. The dynamic AI-enabled MicroPython firmware provided a flexible platform for IoT applications, effectively executing TinyML models on devices with limited resources. Advanced techniques such as model pruning and quantization allowed ML models to fit within the memory constraints of devices like FiPy while maintaining high performance.

3. Transfer Learning for CO₂ Prediction in Vehicles: Another key contribution was the development of an AI-IoT solution for predicting CO₂ concentrations in vehicles using transfer learning. This system leverages a pre-trained model and transfer learning to dynamically update ML models on distributed, low-power microcontrollers. Experimental results highlighted that the accuracy of transfer learning models is closely linked to the quality of the generated labels, with the model's accuracy deviation not exceeding 2% from the ground truth. The complete transfer learning loop, from data collection to model deployment, took approximately 600 seconds. The system was designed to operate with real-time model updates, ensuring minimal interruption during the update process.

The use of TensorFlow Lite and its optimization techniques enabled efficient deployment on devices with limited resources, showing the potential for integrating more complex models in future implementations. The CO₂ concentration prediction model, which achieved an accuracy of 97.77%, highlighted the practical applications of the proposed ML pipeline, providing a scalable and efficient solution for real-time data processing and decision-making.

4. AI-IoT DevOps Framework for Scalable Deployment and Management: The research also explored a DevOps-based approach for managing ML models and firmware updates across distributed IoT devices. Utilizing Kubernetes for orchestrating containerized applications, the system demonstrated scalability and efficient resource allocation. Deployment scaling experiments indicated that Kubernetes effectively managed deployments up to 110 pods (docker containers) on a single worker node, while stress tests highlighted the impact of workload on response times and resource utilization. The framework includes CI/CD pipelines to facilitate continuous integration and delivery, ensuring minimal downtime and efficient updates for ML models and firmware. The DevOps framework established for this system automated the update process for TinyML models, enhancing the adaptability of IoT networks and reducing maintenance overhead.

Despite these successes, the research also identified several limitations related to resource constraints, scalability, energy efficiency, and interoperability, which guide future research directions.

Future Work

Expanded Testing and Sensor Fusion: Future research should expand testing environments to include diverse geographical locations and water bodies to enhance the robustness and reliability of water quality models. Investigating sensor fusion techniques to combine data from multiple sensors (e.g., temperature, pH, turbidity) could provide a more comprehensive assessment of water quality.

On-Device Learning and Hardware Upgrades: Future efforts should explore methods for enabling on-device learning through more efficient model updates and incremental learning techniques, reducing dependency on edge computing. Deploying the dynamic AI-IoT framework on more advanced hardware, such as the ESP32-S3, with better capabilities (e.g., 8MB RAM and 32MB Flash memory), could support more complex ML models and efficient processing.

Improved Memory Management and Advanced Optimization: There is a need to develop improved memory management techniques to optimize the allocation of TensorFlow Lite Micro operations within the available RAM, maximizing the use of hardware resources for more sophisticated models. Additionally, further refinement of model optimization techniques, including neural architecture search (NAS) and advanced quantization methods, is essential to manage even more complex models on resource-constrained devices.

Federated Learning and Dynamic Connectivity: Integrating federated learning techniques can enable decentralized model training and continuous improvement without centralized data storage, enhancing privacy and robustness. Investigating dynamic switching among various connectivity technologies (e.g., Wi-Fi, LoRa, Sigfox) could optimize connectivity and performance in varying environmental conditions.

Infrastructure as Code (IaC) and Model Scalability: Adopting Infrastructure as Code principles using tools like Kubernetes and Terraform can streamline deployment and management, improving scalability and reducing manual configuration errors. Future research should explore the scalability of the transfer learning approach for other environmental metrics beyond CO₂ concentration, such as predicting pollutants and other

gases, and develop methods for real-time model updates based on new data inputs to improve prediction accuracy and adaptability.

Hybrid Transfer Learning and Federated Learning Frameworks: Future research could explore the development of hybrid frameworks that combine transfer learning and federated learning for IoT applications. This approach would enable models to leverage pre-trained knowledge from centralized datasets while adapting dynamically to local data through federated learning. Research could focus on optimizing communication efficiency and model synchronization across devices to minimize resource consumption while maintaining model accuracy and privacy. Such a framework would advance the theoretical understanding of collaborative learning techniques in distributed, resource-constrained environments.

The dynamic AI-IoT framework has potential to be extended to a wide range of real-world applications, opening up new avenues for research and innovation. Some notable areas for future application include:

1. Environmental Disaster Prediction and Management:

The framework can be used in monitoring environmental conditions such as forest fires, floods, and earthquakes. By integrating IoT sensors (e.g., smoke detectors, water level sensors, seismic sensors) and ML models for early detection and prediction, the system could provide real-time alerts and mitigation strategies. In disaster management, rapid response is critical. This system could offer predictive insights that help governments, rescue teams, and communities prepare, reduce the risk of loss, and save lives.

2. AI-Driven Waste Management:

In smart cities, the framework could optimize waste collection by monitoring waste levels in bins across urban areas. ML models could predict when bins will be full and optimize collection routes and schedules using IoT sensors and dynamic models. This application would improve resource allocation, reduce operational costs, and contribute to environmental sustainability by ensuring timely and efficient waste management.

3. Wildlife Conservation and Monitoring:

IoT sensors placed in wildlife reserves or marine environments could monitor animal health,

migration patterns, or ecosystem changes (e.g., temperature, humidity). ML models could analyze this data to provide early warnings about endangered species, habitat destruction, or ecosystem imbalances. This would support wildlife conservation efforts, enabling more informed decisions about interventions and helping preserve biodiversity.

4. Predictive Maintenance for Industrial Equipment:

In manufacturing or critical infrastructure sectors, IoT sensors attached to machines could track performance metrics (vibration, temperature, usage) in real-time. ML models would analyze the data to predict when equipment is likely to fail and recommend preventive maintenance actions. This would minimize downtime, reduce repair costs, and enhance operational efficiency, saving businesses money and preventing critical failures.

5. Personalized Smart Learning Environments:

In education, IoT-enabled wearables (e.g., smart glasses or wristbands) could monitor student engagement, attention, and physiological indicators. ML models could then adapt learning materials and teaching strategies in real-time, providing personalized learning experiences. This would revolutionize education by making it more personalized, efficient, and responsive to the needs of individual students.

This research makes significant contributions to the field of AI-IoT integration, advancing the deployment and management of TinyML models on resource-constrained devices. The theoretical advancements provide new frameworks and methodologies, while the practical implementations demonstrate scalable solutions for real-time data processing and decision-making in environmental monitoring and predictive analytics.

The outlined future directions aim to build upon the current achievements, addressing existing limitations and exploring new avenues for enhancing the robustness, flexibility, and efficiency of AI-driven IoT applications. By pursuing these future work areas, the dynamic AI-IoT framework can continue to evolve and meet the growing demands of intelligent, connected systems.

Part II

Accepted Publications

Chapter 10

Water IoT Monitoring System for Aquaponics Health and Fishery Applications

This chapter contains an exact copy of content present in the research paper [5], where Mohammad Alselek is the leading author and main contributor. It has already been peer-reviewed, accepted, and published.

Abstract

Aquaponic health is a very important care in the food industry field, as currently there is a huge amount of fishing farms, and the demands are growing in the whole world. This work examines the process of developing an innovative aquaponics health monitoring system that incorporates high-tech back-end innovation sensors to examine fish and crop health and a data analytics framework with a low-tech front-end approach to feedback actions to farmers. The developed system improves the state of the art in terms of aquaponics life cycle monitoring metrics, communication technologies and the energy consumption has been reduced to make a sustainable system.

10.1 Introduction

Aquaponics and aquaculture has received growing concern in modern times, and this reinforces its increasing impact on society as an innovative response for food security [44]. Technological advancement in agriculture has opened a path for modern agricultural practices like aquaponics which is an eco-friendly system for cultivating fish and plants without soil [45]. Aquaponics is a symbiotic system which combines aquaculture with hydroponics in fish and plant cultivation to save water and utilize dissolved nutrients more efficiently, without the use of agrochemicals [46]. This advancement has also opened a new era for the design and development of both fish and plant health monitoring system [45].

Time consumed in monitoring and resetting parameters to prerequisite levels is a major shortcoming in aquaponics system [44]. Fish conserves flings, and it is tedious to replenish oxygen, maintain temperature, and water levels or fertilize plants frequently, hence these metrics need to be frequently monitored to ensure fish and plant health or growth [46]. To overcome this complex and time-consuming process of manually monitoring plants and fish health in an aquaponic system, an automatic health monitoring sensor has been proposed. This study designs a smart health monitoring system which makes it easy for deployed sensors to accurately measure and transmit data on a variety of metrics such as pH, temperature, water level, and dissolved oxygen etc, to remote farmhouse monitor in real-time.

The competitiveness of several developed aquaponics monitoring systems depends on technological advances, the number of metrics the system can monitor, the flexibility of design, cost-effectiveness and differences in geographic environments which cannot be generalized [44]. A lot of studies have been conducted on the design of aquaponics monitoring system which can measure and display parameters like pH level, water level, humidity, temperature, etc, to the user [47, 48] , and a few sensors such as Libelium smart water ions exist in the market. However, there is no cost-effective aquaponics monitoring system designed to detect selective ions in an industrially relevant aquaponics system. Existing designs are expensive and are mostly useful for laboratory use and not production or industrial use, and this has motivated the effort of this work.

10.1.1 Contributions

In this paper, the main contributions are related to the development of a complete 5G-enabled IoT system for fully aquaculture monitoring the performance of fishery farms. Specifically, this IoT-based system improves the state of the art and contributes to the improvement of the existing systems in the following aspects:

1. Wide-Area Enabled communications
($> 1Km^2$ - using NB-IoT, LTE-M and LoRa/LoRaWAN).
2. The system combines a higher number of sensors, compared to the state of the art, in order to better characterize the studied environment
3. The system allows real-time monitoring and low-power consumption, as a sensor switching protocol (I2C-based) has been improved to perform more efficiently.
4. The system is cost-efficient and allows a high modularity, as it has been implemented with a Docker-based system to install and update firmware (with OTA updating) in each node and in the farmhouse

10.1.2 Paper Organization

The paper is developed as follows: The introductory section motivates the paper and the aim of the work. Section 2 (materials and methods) explains the context of our problem and the metrics needed. It also establishes the requirements and the architecture. Section 3 (results) exposes the final design and some results in some fishery, discussing the results according to the initial planning. The conclusion section summarises the main achievements and the results.

10.2 Related Work

The state of the art in automated aquaculture systems is somehow limited to the last years, when the capabilities of the IoT systems and the increasing power of AI have allowed the

creation of system capable to monitor, to predict states and to control the whole processes described in the cycle between the fishes and the plants.

In [49], the authors developed a system to monitor water quality, through Potential of Hydrogen (pH), sending the information with GSM in an Arduino-based architecture. Also in [50], the authors focused their efforts in the development of a low-cost, low-power, wireless sensor network and Arduino-based IoT system for groundwater monitoring. This system used LoRa for communications.

In [51], authors oriented their efforts to develop a system for water quality monitoring in remote locations (with Total Dissolved Solids, Electrical Conductivity (EC), pH, and Temperature sensors, with LoRa-enabled communications and GPS). They also used LoRa for localization purposes and performed consumption measurements of their system.

In [52], the authors developed a interdigital FR4-based capacitive sensor, together with the whole IoT Arduino-based system (with LoRa and WiFy communications), to monitor nitrate concentration in water-monitoring studies.

In [53], authors show an IoT system similar to the purpose of this project, applying the architecture for aquaculture purposes. This work shows a number of parameters lower than in our application and their connectivity is based on WiFi (with ESP8266).

Also, the on-going H2020 project FutureEUAqua [54] is developing tools oriented to monitor, control and manage conventional aquaculture of major fish farming industries, promoting innovations in different productive areas. This project has a monitoring part, with wireless sensors in the fish farm, but the number of sensors is limited to Dissolved Oxygen (DO), salinity, chlorophyll, blue-green algae and Turbidity (based on a Real-Time monitoring devices by InnovaSEA company [55]).

10.2.1 Analysis of Existing Remote IoT Sensors Systems

According to one of our studies, the current state-of-the-art in the market shows a diverse wide panorama. At first glance, there is a clear market separation between self-contained devices which provide monitoring information on the screen of the device about the sensors attached to such devices, and the devices with wireless capabilities that are sending information to a

central system. In the self-contained device category, there is a significant market clearly differentiated between those that support the measurement of concrete ions (e.g., NH_4^+ , NO_2^- , NO_3^-) and those that provide more standardized values (pH , ORP , $Temp$, EC). Table 10.1 is a comparison table of the existing sensors under this category and their market price. Note that the DO feature pushed the prices up significantly.

Table 10.1: Existing Remote IoT Sensor Models.

Model	pH	EC	DO	TDS	$Temp$	NH_4^+	ORP	NO_2^-	NO_3^-	Price (GBP)
TEKCOPLUS 6 in 1 Multi-Parameter [56]	X* ¹			X			X* ¹			80
GAIN EXPRESS 6-in-1 [57]	X			X	X		X			117
Bluelab Guardian Monitor [58]	X			X	X					265
Atlas Scientific Industrial Monitoring Kit [59]	X	X	X				X			1700
Hanna HI98194 [60]	X	X	X		X		X			2398
Nico 2000 ELIT Aqualiser [61]	X	X	X		X	X	X	X	X	3780

* Either pH or ORP not at the same time.

On the wireless category, the state-of-the-art is significantly reduced as shown in Table 10.2 below. From the state-of-the-art analysis, it can be concluded that there is no water monitoring solution from the analysed ones above specifically designed for aquaponics, and prices are completely prohibitive when wireless connectivity is required for centralized monitoring. Also, the number of solutions for detecting selective ions are incredibly scarce (Libelium Smart Water Ions) if we consider those with wireless capabilities.

The implementation of this research work using cost-off-the-shelve solutions to demonstrate the concept would require a price per sensor unit of £3800 for the minimally viable solution, provided by Libelium Smart Water, and £9918 for the optimal solution provided by the combination of Libelium Smart Water and Smart Water Ions. The prices available in Tables 10.1 and 10.2 have been collected in June/2022.

Table 10.2: Existing Wireless Sensor Models.

Model	<i>pH</i>	<i>EC</i>	<i>DO</i>	<i>TDS</i>	<i>Temp</i>	NH_4^+	<i>ORP</i>	NO_2^-	NO_3^-	Connect.	Price (GBP)
Bilinli PH-803W 2-in-1 PH ORP Controller [62]	X						X			WI-FI	100
Atlas Scientific Hydroponics Kit [63]	X	X			X					WI-FI	568
Libelium Smart Water [64]	X	X	X				X			Multiple	3800
Libelium Smart Water Extreme [64]	X	X	X		X		X			Multiple	5754
Libelium Smart Water Ions [64]						X		X	X	Multiple	4164

This high cost has motivated the efforts of this work. The efforts in terms of research, development and innovation has been focused on providing a new cost-effective competitive solution:

1. specifically designed for aquaponics,
2. designed with flexibility to allow accommodation to different range of market and use cases (cheaper but less accurate versions and more expensive but more accurate versions).
3. more cost-effective than any of the existing competitors.

Meanwhile, the ready to buy sensors have been acquired to deliver the demonstration part of the project while efforts have been put into developing an alternative to those sensors' boughs. In terms of design and demonstration purposes for the health monitoring system,

only one of the plant growing beds and growing fish areas has been instrumented in order to deal with complexity and costing. The final cost of our proposal for the complete node is £1500 (considering all the sensor probes, the electronics and the communications).

10.3 Materials and Methods

Aquaponics system comprises of the dynamic interaction of fish, plants, bacteria, and their aqueous environment [44]. The main intention of an aquaponic system is to reuse nutrients been pulled out of fishes which are necessary for growing plants [44]. Fish is grown in a fishpond and they are regularly fed. Along their vital cycle, they produce decompositions that are rich in ammonium (NH_4^+). Such decompositions will travel along the pipeline system into the growing bed with plants and bacteria in the soil as shown in Figure 10.1 below, which depicts the basic principles of an aquaponic system. The bacteria in the soil transforms ammonium ion (NH_4^+) firstly into nitrites (NO_2^-) then nitrates (NO_3^-). Nitrates (NO_3^-) are absorbed by the plants as part of their vital cycle, then water is oxygenated (H_2O) and filtered off. To close the loop, the oxygenated water can be reverted into the fishponds, and depending on the size of the fishpond and the growing beds, 1 or 2 additional filters may need to be inserted along the cycle. First, a biofilter could be in the segment between fish decomposition and plants. This filter is not habitable by bacteria to plan transformation from ammonium (NH_4^+) to nitrates (NO_3^-), hence, it could be inserted to help control the population of bacteria in the system. Second, a Swirl filter could be in the segment between the plan evacuation and fish intake of water. The purpose of this filter is to purify the water by getting rid of solid materials thereby making it suitable for fish life. This solid material is usually present when the plants cannot provide sufficient filtering (i.e., due to different parameters, e.g. size of the bed, number of fish, etc).

Figure 10.1: Aquaponics cycle.

10.3.1 Water Monitoring Parameters

There is a set of water probes which can be used to build a digital health monitoring system. Most probes are used for detection of one or more water metrics such as pH, temperature, and ammonia etc. These probes consist of two interfaces; the first interface reacts with water, based on physical or chemical principles to produce the values of the metric(s). The second interface is an electrical interface used to allow a digital system to retrieve the measured metrics. The key aspect to consider in the selection of water probes are:

1. Time elapsed between each required calibration.
2. Accuracy of the measured metric.

3. Duration until water probe is not functional (Lasting period).

These aspects directly influence the operational aspects of the deployed system. Other aspects such as the electrical interface have more engineering requirements which will directly affect the final cost of the system. The number of metrics to be monitored will also have an impact on the quality and cost of the developed monitoring system since each monitored metrics/parameter will have an associated direct cost. There is a non-exhaustive list of water probes in the market which can be used to enhance the capabilities of the digital health monitoring system for aquaponics.

The following are parameters or metrics for monitoring water, soil and air quality. For Water quality monitoring:

1. Potential of Hydrogen (*pH*): This is a scale used to specify the acidity or basicity of an aqueous solution [65].
2. Water Temperature: Temperature of the water
3. Dissolved Oxygen (*DO*): This is the amount of gaseous oxygen (O_2) dissolved in the water. [66]
4. Oxidation-Reduction Potential (*ORP*): This is a measure of the tendency of a chemical specie to acquire electrons from or lose electrons to an electrode thereby reduced or oxidised, respectively [67].
5. Electrical Conductivity (*EC*): This is the measure of the amount of electrical current a material can carry or its ability to carry a current [68].
6. Total Dissolved Solids (*TDS*): This is a measure of the dissolved combined content of all inorganic and organic substances present in a liquid in molecular, ionized, or micro-granular (colloidal sol) suspended form.[69].
7. Total suspended solids (*TSS*): This is the dry weight of suspended particles, that are not dissolved in a sample of water that can be trapped by a filter that is analysed using a filtration apparatus [70].

8. Water Level (*WL*): This is the level of water along a given surface (e.g fishpond).
9. Water Flow (*WF*): This is the speed of the water across the pipeline circuit.
10. Ion Selective Ammonia (NH_4^+): This is the concentration of NH_4^+ in aqueous solutions.
11. Ion Selective Nitrite (NO_2^-): This is the concentration of NO_2^- in aqueous solutions.
12. Ion Selective Nitrate (NO_3^-): This is the concentration of NO_3^- in aqueous solutions.

Here, it is worthy to emphasize that the hidroponics metrics (i.e. ORP, pH, EC, Temp) and the aquaponics metrics (i.e. NH_4^+ , NO_2^- and NO_3^-) are the main metrics to control the aquaponic cycle.

Also, we have considered other metrics for soil and air quality monitoring:

1. Light Intensity (*LI*): It measures the number of lux to determine suitability to carry out photosynthesis processes in plants.
2. Air Temperature (*AT*): It is the temperature of the air
3. Air Humidity (*AH*): It is the humidity of the air
4. Wind Direction and Speed (*WDS*): It is the speed of winds
5. Soil Moisture (*SM*): It is the level of water in-between soil particles

10.3.2 Analysis of Requirements for Aquaponics System

The analysis of requirements for the aquaponics system has followed a two-fold methodology. The identification of the minimal requirements an aquaponics monitoring system should possess when optimizing for a low-cost monitoring system available for all markets; and the identification of requirements needed to create an internationally competitive monitoring system. This methodology allows us to maximize the exploitative aspects of the outcomes generated in the project and optimize for the concrete system being addressed in the demonstration phase of the project. In this report, the two-fold methodology will be referred to as an “ideal scenario” and a “minimal suitable scenario” respectively.

Figure 10.2 shows a conceptual simplified version of a floorplan representing a aquaponics system. It is composed by fish ponds, grow beds for vegetables, bio-filters, and swirl filters and pumps and pipes to interconnect the whole system and the points to connect the sensors to send information to the farmhouse.

Figure 10.2: Aquaponics system simple floor plan.

The ideal scenario will allow for per-pound metrics, per-grow bed metrics, and per-filter metrics for each sensor available in the system, however, this represents a significant increase in price for the final product. This kind of system is conceptually viable for economically not affordable. Thus, the next step in the trade-off for accuracy/price would be the use of 4 sensors, i.e., $2 \times$ Type-A sensors, $2 \times$ Type B sensors, lately explained. The system will alert the farmer if there is an issue, the type of issue, and where it can be fixed, however, determining the best place to fix the issue might require an in-situ investigation out of the data monitoring health system. This is what we have coined as "ideal scenario". The "minimally suitable" deployment would be to make use of 2 sensors ($2 \times$ Type A+B sensors).

The Type A sensor is located immediately after the fishponds; thus, it measures the water parameters related to fish health. These parameters include the *pH*, *EC*, or *TDS*, *DO*, Temperature, NH_4^+ and/or NH_3 , and/or *ORP*, and these parameters should be measured in an ideal scenario. In a minimally suitable scenario, NH_4^+ and NH_3 could be substituted for *ORP* carrying out a trade-off between accuracy and cost. This minimally suitable scenario will allow the farmer to know if there is more NH_3 or NH_4^+ concentration. It is important to note that NH_3 is toxic for fish and can cause death but NH_4^+ is not as toxic and can only cause death at very high concentrations. Also, *EC* could be replaced by a cheaper and less accurate *TDS* sensor. *EC* measures the electrical conductivity of water whereas *TDS* measures the level of particles dissolved in water, and both are good estimators of the number of ions present in water. This sensor also ensure water reaching the fishponds is clear and compatible with fish health. Type B sensor is focused on providing the level of plan nutrients generated by the bio-filter to estimate the quality of the nutrients for the plants. Thus, it should provide *pH*, *EC*, NO_3 and NO_2 levels in an ideal scenario. In a minimally suitable scenario, NO_3 and NO_2 could be measured out of the data monitoring system while setting up the biofilter until it reaches expected levels of bacteria, then *EC* will be used to estimate the concentration of ions (nutrients) in water. This sensor is also focused on determining the quality of the water being provided by the grow beds.

Table 10.3 represents the different types of sensors and their associated monitoring parameters. The table also contains a combined sensor with all the parameters together to save manufacturing time. Table 10.3 shows the minimal viable set of metrics, and for the minimal viable set of metrics, there are other metrics indicated with *. The metrics indicated with * are metrics which should be measured using a cheap colorimetric test in providing NH_4 , NO_2 , and NO_3 measures during the establishment phase of the aquaponics system. After that establishment, they will need to be measured manually only if the *EC* and *ORP* values are not in a normal range.

Table 10.3: Sensor Types and Monitoring Parameters.

	Type A	Type B	Type A+B	Minimal A+B
<i>pH</i>	X	X	X	X
<i>EC</i>	X	X	X	
<i>DO</i>	X		X	X
<i>TDS</i>				X
<i>Temp</i>	X		X	X
NH_4^+	X		X	*
NH_3		X	X	X
<i>ORP</i>	X		X	*
NO_2		X	X	*

In terms of communication, the floor plan is extended within an area greater than $200m^2$, but the system should be designed to cover up to $1km^2$, as the farmers control room i.e., where the central system is located and where the sensors will be located cannot be assumed, thus, an average coverage of around $1km^2$ should be supported by the system.

The technical specifications for the sensors included in the node are shown in Table 10.4.

Table 10.4: Technical specifications for Sensors.

	Meas. Range	Resolution	Accuracy	Response time	Data protoc.	Function. Temp
DO (AtlasSci.)	0.01 – 100 mg/L 0.1 – 400 % saturat.	0.01 mg/L	± 0.05 mg/L	1 read per 420ms	UART/I2C	-40 to 85°C (Typ.25°C)
pH (AtlasSci.)	0.001 – 14.000	0.001	± 0.002	1read per 420ms	UART/I2C	-40 to 85°C (Typ.25°C)
EC (AtlasSci.)	0.07 – 500,000 uS/cm	0.07 uS/cm	± 2%	1 read per 420ms	UART/I2C	-40 to 85°C (Typ.25°C)
ORP (AtlasSci.)	-1019.9 – 1019.9 mV	0.9 mV	± 1 mV	1read per 420ms	UART/I2C	-40 to 85°C (Typ.25°C)
Temp (AtlasSci.)	-126,000 – 1254 °C	0.001 °C	± (0.1 + 0.002 x °C)	1 read per 420ms	UART/I2C	-40 to 85°C (Typ.25°C)
NO_2^- (Nico2000)	0.5 to 500ppm (10^{-5} to 0.01 Mol.)	0.5 ppm	Potential drift (in 1000 ppm)< 10s < 3 mV/day (8h)		I2C	0 to 50°C
NO_3^- (Nico2000)	0.3 to 6,200ppm (5×10^{-6} to 0.1 Mol.)	0.3 ppm	Potential drift (in 1000 ppm)< 10s < 3 mV/day (8h)		I2C	0 to 50°C
NH_4^+ (Nico2000)	0.03 to 1,800ppm (2×10^{-6} to 0.1 Mol.)	0.03 ppm	Potential drift (in 1000 ppm)< 10s < 3 mV/day (8h)		I2C	0 to 50°C

10.4 Proposed IoT System Architecture for Aquaponics Monitoring

The proposal and development of an IoT system architecture for monitoring aquaponics health is very useful for fishery farms industry as the automation in the fish care and exploitation allows an improvement in the production.

Figure 10.3: Proposed architecture for our Aquaponics Monitoring System.

Figure 10.3 shows the proposed IoT system architecture for aquaponics monitoring. This system is comprised of a farmhouse which houses a monitor, Wi-Fi link (or wireless technology), keyboard, mouse, and gateway box. The system also considers a growing bed, 1km^2 wireless link, a sensor box with a set of sensors deployed in the field according to the analysis in section 3.1, where different types of field sensors will be deployed in fishponds, sump, and filters to monitor appropriate metrics. The farmhouse (as explained in section 6) contains a gateway sensor, which forwards all the metrics from LoRa technology to other technologies and a monitoring station, which allows the first visualization and control of the metrics. The gateway sensor also allows the connection to other infrastructures through WiFi

or LTE-M/NB-IoT. This infrastructure allows the connection to the CORE and Cloud and the monitoring from a remote/house station.

LoRaWAN is the specification for Low-Power Wide Area Networks (LPWAN) in Low Radiation (LoRa) communications. From the LoRa protocol, LoRaWAN is a point-to-multipoint network layer protocol, full duplex, and with the best LoRa features, i.e. low-power extending battery duration and quality of service (with 3 modes), and uses FSK modulation. LoRa-based technology is able to achieve long ranges.

LTE-M (or LTE-MTC [Machine Type Communication]) including eMTC (enhanced Machine Type Communication), is a low-power wide area network (LPWAN) radio technology standard developed by 3GPP to enable a wide range of cellular devices and services (specifically, for machine-to-machine and Internet of Things applications). The specification for eMTC (LTE Cat M1) was frozen in 3GPP Release 13 (LTE Advanced Pro), in June 2016.

NB-IoT is also an LPWAN protocol, and it is a radio technology standard developed by 3GPP to enable high-end services for mobile devices. Previously, the 3GPP Release 13 (LTE Advanced Pro) specification was used until June 2016. NB-IoT uses an extension of the standard LTE network but limits bandwidth to a single 200kHz band. Uses OFDM modulation for communications with few connections between devices and uses SC-FDMA for communications with more connections between devices.

The advantage of LTE-M over NB-IoT is its comparatively higher data rate, mobility, and voice over the network, but it requires more bandwidth and is more costly. Compared to LTE Release 12 Cat-0 modem, an LTE-M model is claimed to be 80% less expensive, supports up to 18 dB better coverage, and has a battery lifetime that can last up to several years.

The data link from the node to the farmhouse is made using Message Queuing Telemetry Transport (MQTT) protocol. This protocol can be configured with 3 levels (i.e. 0, 1 and 2), but for our purpose, it has been configured with level 2 for both subscribers and publishers to ensure information delivery and no data duplication. The security issues were tackled by configuring the Transport Layer Security (TLS) encryption to ensure secure communication between clients and brokers.

For the sensor to monitor metrics, different water probes will be attached to the sensors. The design of the sensors should be flexible enough to allow the building of a system which can be customized with sensor combinations described in Table 10.3, as type A, type B, type A + B or a minimal type A + B, in order to control production costs. Each of these sensors has attached, a wireless link which is able to provide coverage of up to 1 km^2 in order to ensure that the solution is flexible enough to accommodate farmland extensions dedicated to aquaponics such that the farmer can have a view of all his/her farmlands on the same monitoring system. LoRa/LoRaWAN, NB-IoT (5G) and LTE-M technologies will provide the capabilities to support this coverage. In the farmhouse, a special sensor called the gateway sensor will be deployed. The main purpose of this sensor is to act as a receiver for all the metrics periodically sent by all other devices, and it is also responsible for sending the calibration information to the associated sensor deployed in the field. The gateway sensor is connected to two different wireless networks and it acts as a forwarder between them. Any information received by the LoRa / LoRaWAN network will be forwarded into the Wi-Fi network and vice-versa. Finally, a small computer with a monitor, keyboard, mouse, and Wi-Fi connection will be installed in the farmhouse to allow the farmers see the graphical interface where all the information is displayed in real-time.

In our proposed architecture, we have designed and prototyped both the device and gateway capabilities indicated in the IoT Methodology standardized by ITU-T under specification ITU-T Y.2060 [71]. However, at this stage, we have not specified the definition of the functional components defined in ITU-T Y.4115-2017 [72] as our IoT system is a industrially relevant lab-based development, so the IoT Device Capability Exposure (IoT DCE) is summarised in a Database and a Dashboard (in the Farmhouse subsystem), but could be replaced by a complete IoT ecosystem, such as Thingsboard, FIWARE or any other platform.

10.5 In-pond WaterMon Sensor Design and Feasibility

Sensors are devices deployed in the aquaponics system to collect real-time data on temperature, humidity, pH, dissolved oxygen, total dissolved solids, water level, etc. A detailed design of the sensors referred to as WaterMon has been carried out to achieve a step closer to the market.

10.5.1 Overview Design

The design of the monitoring system has been thought to be implemented on a 4 layer PCB board especially designed for the purposes of this work.

In Figure 10.4, the Fipy I2C connection is serially connected to the different sensors and the analog to signal converters. I2C or Inter-Integrated-Circuit protocol is a synchronous, multi-controller/multi-target, packet-switched, single-ended, serial communication bus. It is widely used for attaching lower-speed peripheral ICs to processors and microcontrollers in short-distance, intra-board communication. These devices have been configured by software to be switched on, read a measure from a sensor and switch it off to go to the next device to collect its measurement. The selection of the sensor is done by using a 74HC237 decoder multiplexer [73] and programmed in order to follow a specific order for the data collection within the sensors. The connection of the keypad to the I2C is oriented to write in the system the adequate calibration, which will be further explained in section 4.2. Also, the LCD connection will allow the visualization of the information for every step of the calibration or the monitoring process.

WaterMon allows the monitoring of 11 different water quality metrics, including all of those indicated in Table 10.3. WaterMon has been designed to provide connectivity to LoRa, LoRaWAN, and the new 5G networks by supporting the novel IoT technologies, LTE-M and NB-IoT, and low-profile technologies such as Wi-Fi and Bluetooth. For the implementation of the LoRa protocol, we have selected the parameters shown in Table 10.5.

Table 10.5: Parameters for LoRa configuration.

Parameter	Description
region=LoRa.EU868	Selection of 868MHz as carrier frequency, the default channel is established in 868.1 MHz
bandwidth=LoRa.BW_125KHZ	Selection of a bandwidth of 125 kHz
sf=7	Sets the desired spreading factor. Accepts values between 7 and 12
Device_class=LoRa.CLASS_C	Class C devices extend Class A by keeping the receive windows open unless they are transmitting. This allows for low-latency communication but is many times more energy-consuming than Class A devices
coding_rate=LoRa.CODING_4_5	The default coding rate is 4/5
power_mode=LoRa.ALWAYS_ON	LoRa protocol is always listening
rx_iq=False	The use of IQ inversion allows to mitigate interference between up- and downlink
LORA_PAYLOAD_SIZE=240	Payload size is configured at 240 bytes
LORA_TX_POWER=7	This value establishes a modulation FSK, with 2 dBm

The previous design has been originally prototyped in a lab-based implementation to test the feasibility of the sensor. Figure 10.5 shows an image captured with the easy prototype achieved in the context of the project where 5 different water monitoring probes has been implemented as an early-stage feasibility (DO, EC, Temperature, ORP and pH).

Figure 10.4: Overview Design of WaterMon System.

From this early prototype, a fully functional optimized version of the prototype in a printed circuit board (PCB) was designed to achieve a better performance and next to a final product. Figure 10.6 shows a screenshot of some of the layer available in the prototyped sensor. This board has been squeezed in 20x14 cm to minimize fabrication costs.

Furthermore, after testing the methodology using the virtualised 3D version of the PCB. The manufacturing was carried out by an external company, and the result is a fully functional sensor board.

Figure 10.5: Early Prototype.

Afterwards, all the sensor components were soldered into the PCB creating a fully functional prototype. The water monitoring probes were not attached before being physically inserted in liquid (as shown in the pictures) for it not to suffer any damage and thus, we put this on hold to perform the deployment of the probes in an industrially relevant scenario. The device allows the installation of 1 to 11 sensor probes, thus allowing for customization of 4 different types of field sensor considered in Table 10.3 of this document (Type A, B, A+B, minimal A+B).

Figure 10.6: 3D Representation of PCB.

With respect to the software governing the behaviour of the WaterMon board, there is no open-source initiative which could be used to have a starting point. Therefore, an implementation of the software has been carried out until a fully functional prototype is achieved. This prototype allows us to:

1. Perform the continuous monitoring of the 11 metrics supported in the board.
2. Perform the continuous reporting of the values retrieved from the probe using the NB-IoT, LTE-M, LoRa / LoRaWAN wireless connection
3. Perform the calibration of the water monitoring probes in a very intuitive way.

Figure 10.7: WaterMon Sensor.

The PCB has been designed with flexibility and extensibility in mind. Therefore, it allows for the attachment of more sensors and this would propel further research in this field. The PCB also allows for the extension of capabilities such as controlling for the sensor's energy consumption rate to enable future developments of battery-powered or a solar-powered versions, however, a software has not been developed to support such capabilities since this is out of the scope of this project. Finally, an enclosure has been designed to achieve a device ready to be deployed in an industrially relevant scenario.

Figure 10.8: Sensor Device.

Figures 10.7 and 10.8 show the whole sensor device, fully operative to be used in a fish farm, with proper communications.

10.5.2 Calibration Procedure

The calibration process is done using a one or two point calibration for each sensor probe. Figure 10.9 shows an illustration of the 2 point calibration procedure. Following this calibration process for each sensor, the first step is to put the probe into the corresponding calibrating liquid and press the corresponding button in the keypad which has been programmed to make the probe selection (for DO, EC, ORP, pH and Temp) and write the calibration into the corresponding device. In the case of the sensors connected to 16bits A/D converters ADS1115 (for NH_4^+ , NH_3 , NO_2 and TDS), the calibration is stored on the NVRAM in the Fipy.

Figure 10.9: Sensor Calibration.

Compensation

Once, every sensing probe is calibrated, the node has been programmed to consider measurement compensation for each parameter. Table 10.6 shows the parameter dependencies for some sensors (the other ones not appearing in the table does not need any compensation). This process needs a specific measurement collection order, which has been considered by programming the previously mentioned 74HC237 decoder multiplexer to make the sensor selection.

Table 10.6: Sensors Parameter dependencies for compensation.

Sensor	Parameter dependency
<i>EC</i>	Temperature (RTC)
<i>pH</i>	Temperature (RTC)
<i>DO</i>	Temperature (RTC), Salinity (EC), Pressure (Fipy)
NH_4^+	Temperature (RTC), Salinity (EC),
NO_3^-	Temperature (RTC) , pH
NO_2^-	Temperature (RTC) , pH

When compensation is required by a particular sensor, it has the purpose to provide the most possible accuracy in the measurement of the values measured by such sensor. Calibration, previously described, is the first approach towards the achievement of such accuracy by dealing with the aging of the sensor, the state of the chemical membranes and liquids used to carry out the physical measurement, and other aspect about the status of the sensor. After that, the compensation will allow to tweak the value readed from an already calibrated sensor in order to adapt it with the external factors that may affect on the reading of such value. Thus, for example EC in Table 10.6 is depending of water temperature. It means that the value read about the electrical conductivity in water directly is affected by the temperature of the water and thus by knowing that value in advance of the reading of EC values, it can be used to compensate the readed value in order to provided a much more accurate result.

10.6 Farmhouse System

10.6.1 Gateway Sensor

In order to extent the communication range as proposed in Figure 10.3, a gateway sensor has been proposed.

For the Gateway sensor, we will use a state-of-the-art ready-to-use sensor, specifically Pycom FiPy [74] with PySense 2.0 [75] extension boards. However, even if the hardware is currently mature enough, the software inside the sensor needed to perform the 'forwarding' capabilities between LoRa / LoRaWAN and Wi-Fi does not exist. This software has been fully developed in the context of this work to produce a fully functionally sensor. Figure 10.10 shows an image of the prototyped gateway. The prototype has two different antennas to connect two different wireless technologies and it has a USB cable mainly used to provide power to the device (and program the software when required). Figure 10.11 also shows the PyCase enclosure bought for the device to create a ready to deploy product.

Figure 10.10: Prototyped Gateway.

10.6.2 Monitoring Station

In terms of hardware, we are relying on a very cheap (70 GBP) commercially available mini-computer, Raspberry Pi 4B+ (RPi4) used together with an SD card, a keyboard, a mouse and a monitor to provide a fully functional computer with basic capabilities, which is more than enough to fully fulfil the requirement of the use case. Figure 10.12 shows an schema of the system located in the farmhouse and the connections for each subsystem oriented to the hardware deployment. This image is the setup achieved in our premises. This hardware will be situated on the farm's control and management centre, which consists of mini-computer,

Raspberry Pi 4 with an SD card, a keyboard, a monitor, and a mouse to monitor and control the aquaponics system remotely.

Figure 10.11: Gateway diagram.

In terms of the software to show the real-time data monitoring information of the whole system, several monitoring tools are available in the market. We have been customizing Grafana as the tool to display the sensor metrics on screen. Figure 10.13 shows the graphical interface shown to farmers on the minicomputer. Using displayed or obtained information the farmer decides whether to open the air pump, water pump, lights and feeder or make other changes required to sustain fish and plant health.

Figure 10.12: Farmhouse system schema.

Figure 10.13: Graphical interface on RPi4.

10.7 Results and Discussion

The development of this IoT-based aquaponic system allows a number of future applications in the fishery industry. One of the first tests done is the functional testing, which has allowed us to achieve good performance in a local and a networked environment. This testing has

been successful and has shown good performance for the communication and the sensing parts.

As a prove of functioning and performance, the first test of the WaterMon node is the time measurement for every sensor sending information to the farmhouse. Figure 10.14 shows that the most time consuming measurement is DO which takes an average time of 1.5s for every measurement and sending cycle, the pH and ORP sensors take an average time of 1.1s approximately and then EC and RTD sensors take 0.9s approximately. This fact is mostly due to the need of some compensations for the measurements. The analog sensors are more fluent in their measurements with 0.3s each.

Figure 10.14: Time Measurements of WaterMon. Sensors

In order to evaluate the whole monitoring cycle in the WaterMon node, a test with the node just collecting cycles of parameters has been done. Figure 10.15 shows a plot of the time used for each cycle, which takes in average 7430ms (with standard deviation of 1.6ms).

Figure 10.15: Monitoring Cycle Time.

Figure 10.16 shows the timing used to submit the information to the farmhouse from the values collected at the node. For a number of monitoring cycle submissions, the average value is 462.7ms (with a standard deviation of 56.9ms).

Figure 10.16: WaterMon Submission Time.

Figure 10.17: Power Consumption with and without IC 74HC237

Finally, an energetic consumption test has been done to assess the effectiveness of the energy-aware implementation done for this system. Figure 10.17 shows the power consumption measurement during 100 seconds of the WaterMon sensor. As it can be seen, the average power reduction for the situation with and without the IC 74HC237 is 0.76W in 100s, when we use the IC. This reduction allow us to extend the lifetime of the power-supply for this purpose. For instance, if the power-supply is made with batteries, a commercial power-bank with 20000 mAh will give the WaterMon sensor without the IC a lifetime of 41.2h, while if we consider the use of the IC the lifetime is extended up to 59.8h, an increase of the power-supply time of 68.9%.

10.8 Conclusions

This paper summarizes the work done in the development and test of a whole system for aquaponics health monitoring oriented to the fishery industry. We have checked that the existing monitoring systems in the state of the art does not fit the requirements for monitoring the complete aquaponics life cycle.

The proposed system improves the state of the art in terms of communication technology as it involves 5G communications, but for long-range communication uses LoRa in the nodes and Gateways with LTE-M/NB-IoT to reach the Internet connectivity.

For aquaculture purposes, the sensing layer has been improved to include a number of sensors to improve the performance in the fishery industry. The most time consuming processes are linked to the sensing and compensation processes, which range between 0.9s to 1.5s for the digital sensors and 0.3s for the analog ones. The whole sensing period takes around 7.5s in average, with 9 sensors. The mean time for each information packet to get the CORE from the sensing node is around 463ms.

Also the hardware architecture has been designed to improve the energetic performance and save power consumption, allowing an extension of the battery consumption time around 70%, with the inclusion of a switching IC for the sensors (74HC237) connected to the I2C line.

10.9 Abbreviations

The following abbreviations are used in this manuscript:

IoT	Internet of Things
pH	Potential of Hidrogen
NB-IoT	Narrow Band IoT
LTE-M or LTE-MTC	Long Term Evolution - Machine Type Communication
LoRa/LoRaWAN	Low Radiation/ LoRa Wide Area Network
WiFi	Wireless Fidelity
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
TLS	Transport Layer Security
I2C	Inter-Integrated Circuit
OTA	Over The Air
AI	Artificial Intelligence
GSM	Global System for Mobile communications
EC	Electrical Conductivity
TDS	Total Dissolved Solids
GPS	Global Positioning System
DO	Dissolved Oxigen
ORP	Oxidation Reduction Potential
TSS	Total Suspended Solids
WL	Water Level
WF	Water Flow
LI	Light Intensity
AT	Air Temperature
AH	Air Humidity
WDS	Wind Direction and Speed
SM	Soil Moisture
PCB	Printed Circuit Board

Chapter 11

Dynamic AI-IoT: Enabling Updatable AI Models in Ultra-Low-Power 5G IoT Devices

This chapter contains an exact copy of content present in the research paper [6], where Mohammad Alselek is the leading author and main contributor. It has already been peer-reviewed, accepted, and published.

Abstract

This paper addresses the challenge of integrating dynamic AI capabilities into Ultra-Low-Power (ULP) IoT devices, a critical necessity in the rapidly evolving landscape of 5G and potential 6G technologies. We introduce the Dynamic AI-IoT architecture, a novel framework designed to eliminate the need for cumbersome firmware updates. This architecture leverages Narrowband IoT (NB-IoT) to facilitate smooth cloud interactions and incorporates tailored firmware extensions for enabling dynamic interactions with Tiny Machine Learning (TinyML) models. A sophisticated memory management mechanism, grounded in memory alignment and dynamic AI operations resolution, is introduced to efficiently handle AI tasks. Empirical experiments demonstrate the feasibility of implementing a Dynamic AI-IoT system using

ULP IoT devices on a 5G testbed. The results show model updates taking less than one second and an average inference time of approximately 46 ms.

11.1 Introduction

The combination of 5G, IoT and AI technologies creates limitless possibilities for novel and future-proof communication systems. IoT devices are key sources of data in 5G and beyond systems, while AI goes hand in hand with IoT for smart pervasive services. When coupled together, AI and IoT reshape the digital transformation mechanisms. Making ultra-low-power 5G-enabled IoT devices smart has a significant impact in terms of a wide range of use cases such as improving prediction and automating new processes. Moreover, dealing with low-power and ULP devices means that we can maintain the power consumption at a lower level, resulting in more sustainable end products and/or applications.

The 5G architecture embraces IoT, allowing diverse vertical IoT applications, such as Industrial IoT (IIoT), Smart Agriculture, and Smart Cities, to be instantiated across a shared physical network and cloudified 5G infrastructure [76]. Such infrastructure allows AI models to be dynamically loaded and executed by low-cost, low-power, 5G-enabled IoT devices, and thus the technological game changes dramatically.

However, many current ultra-low-power IoT devices lack sufficient support for training and executing AI models. When such support is available, it is often fixed, making these devices vulnerable to obsolescence and inflexibility over time. Specifically, we are referring to real ultra-low-powered tiny IoT devices (less than 250mA) with limited resources, unable to accommodate an embedded Linux-based system. Instead, they utilize a tiny mini-OS embedded in an 8Mb-32Mb memory size. Updating these devices necessitates re-flashing the firmware, creating challenges for many use cases. This requirement demands either in-situ re-flashing or remote re-flashing via Over-the-air (OTA) technology [77]. Such a requirement presents significant challenges in various IoT scenarios, exemplified by scenarios where a timely and smooth update process is crucial, like in industrial automation or healthcare applications.

In response to the above gaps in the state of the art, this research has focused on allowing the execution and dynamic loading/updating of AI models into low-power IoT devices. The proposed new enabling architecture, referred to as Dynamic AI-IoT, will be based on an ESP32 microprocessor using Micropython as a scripting language to provide dynamic AI capabilities of the AI models.

The proposed system offers several advantages and contributions, which include:

- First, Dynamic AI-IoT enables the execution of AI models into ULP IoT devices, thereby removing a major barrier in today's AI-empowered IoT use cases.
- Second, Dynamic AI-IoT enables the dynamic updating and re-configuration of AI models without the need to re-flashing the IoT devices, enabling further development into more advanced AI approaches such as “online learning” and “federated learning”.
- Third, Dynamic AI-IoT enables the dynamic loading of different AI models to achieve a multi-proposed AI-empowered IoT device in 5G systems. Therefore, a single IoT device can be involved in multiple use cases depending on the loaded AI model.
- Forth, Dynamic AI-IoT enables connectivity with various networks such as Lora, LTE-M, or NB-IoT, among others. For example, we use a 5G network as a connection bridge between Mobile Edge Computing where the AI model is generated, and the ULP IoT devices where the transferred AI model is executed.
- Fifth, Dynamic AI-IoT has been prototyped to achieve a fully functional system. The system has been tested and empirically validated against two different AI use cases: hand gesture recognition and sine wave recognition.

The rest of the paper is laid out as follows. Section II presents the state-of-the-art. Section III outlines the proposed architecture of the dynamic AI-IoT system. Section IV explores the system's process and diagrams. Section V details the AI-IoT firmware development. Section VI showcases two validation use cases. Section VII summarizes experimental outcomes. Section VIII discusses limitations and challenges, and, finally, Section IX concludes the paper and suggests directions for future research.

11.2 Related Work

Table 11.1: Comparing Related Works

	Programmability Support		AI Support							Technology	Connectivity for AI					Power Consumption
	Remote Flashing	Dynamic Re-programming	Training	Execution	Reloading	Multiple AI Models	Dynamic Model Configuration	Dynamic Memory Optimization	Micropython		WiFi	Bluetooth	LTE-M	NB-IoT	Lora/Sigfox	
Shang et al.[78]	x	x	x	✓	x	x	x	x	x	✓	✓	x	x	x	x	
Zhang et al.[79]	x	x	x	✓	x	x	x	x	x	✓	✓	x	x	x	x	
Crocioni et al.[39]	x	x	x	✓	x	x	x	x	x	✓	✓	x	x	x	✓	
Dokic et al.[40]	x	x	x	✓	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	✓	
Hoang et al.[80]	x	x	x	✓	x	x	x	x	x	✓	✓	x	x	x	✓	
Spresense[41]	x	✓	x	✓	x	x	x	x	x	✓	✓	✓	✓	x	✓	
O' Cleirigh[81]	x	✓	x	✓	✓	x	x	x	✓	✓	✓	x	x	x	✓	
microAI[82]	x	✓	x	✓	✓	x	x	x	✓	x	x	x	x	x	x	
Yan[83]	x	✓	x	✓	✓	x	x	x	✓	✓	✓	x	x	x	✓	
OpenMV[42]	x	✓	x	✓	✓	x	x	x	✓	✓	x	x	x	x	✓	
Our Contribution	✓	✓	x	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	

Table 11.1 presents a comparison of the current state of Ultra-Low-Power (ULP) IoT devices and their AI capabilities, providing a basis for evaluating our contribution. The table enables readers to understand how our work contributes to the existing state of the art.

Recent efforts have been made to implement ML on IoT devices, marking advancements in both hardware and software domains [84]. On the software side, ML libraries like TensorFlow, Scikit-Learn, and PyTorch have been adapted for use on resource-constrained devices [85]. Simultaneously, hardware manufacturers are striving to improve chips by integrating advanced technologies. For instance, the incorporation of a dedicated co-processor, such as a Tensor Processing Unit (TPU), can effectively support the primary computing unit in ML tasks. While this approach enhances computational performance, it

is less common due to its significant impact on price, power consumption, and processing platform complexity.

Furthermore, the concept of Edge Intelligence, which represents the convergence of Edge Computing and AI [10], has emerged as a pivotal paradigm for extending AI capabilities to the network's edge. This extension empowers real-time decision-making while simultaneously reducing latency [9]. In the context of these developments, Edge Impulse Studio, a cloud-based platform dedicated to embedded machine learning, has played a vital role in facilitating model training, evaluation, and subsequent deployment on IoT devices at the network's edge [86].

Most IoT devices are designed to use low power, whether they are in idle or active mode. The primary chip in their architecture, referred to as a Micro Controller Unit (MCU) such as ESP32 and STM32, should have the capability to integrate low-power units. Developing applications on MCUs has led to the creation of compatible technologies. For instance, the term TinyML is used instead of ML when implementing AI on MCUs. Some AI frameworks have been adjusted, such as TensorFlow Lite Micro (TFLM), which is a modified version of TensorFlow. Concerning the programming language, Micropython has been developed to provide access to alternative Python libraries for interaction with MCUs.

TFLM simplifies the deployment of TinyML models on hardware with limited resources by prioritizing portability and flexibility [87]. A straightforward approach for creating a TFLM model is to convert an already trained TensorFlow model. The optimized models, supporting various algorithms from the Neural Network (NN) class, can operate on diverse platforms like smartphones, embedded Linux systems, and MCUs. Specifically for MCUs, the optimized code is written in C++ and is compatible with 32-bit processors. It has been successfully applied to devices such as the Arduino Nano, as well as other architectures like the ESP32 and ARM Cortex-M series processors [85].

Currently, there is a growing focus on investments in Low-Power IoT and TinyML. In this context, researchers have made significant progress by considering factors such as chip architecture, programmability support, AI support, programming language, connectivity for AI, and power consumption. These factors are the main elements of our comparison,

as illustrated in Table 11.1. To simplify, we have categorized this table into three groups, each representing recent AI-empowered IoT devices. The first group pertains to devices equipped with high computational processors, the second highlights low-power IoT devices, and the third category involves low-power/ULP Micropython-enabled IoT devices. Despite their differences, all these IoT devices share the common feature of efficiently executing AI models.

The authors in [78] and [79] fall into the first group, demonstrating the capability to deploy Deep Learning (DL) inference models directly on IoT end-nodes. Their focus was on reducing the size and compressing high-accuracy DL models to suit the characteristics of the target IoT devices. These devices have resources that enable them to smoothly run large AI models, regardless of their complexity. For instance, in [78], a TensorFlow AI model was deployed on Raspberry Pi 3 Model B+, and in [79], a PyTorch AI model was trained and executed on Raspberry Pi 4 Model B. While these efforts have made it possible to run AI models on IoT devices, real-time processing of large AI models is power-intensive and can consume several Watts. For example, in an empirical test on an RPi 4 with 4 busy cores, it was found to consume around 6 Watts of power.

In [39], [40], [80], and [88], the authors proposed generating pre-trained TinyML models and adapting them to the constraints of MCUs. They explained the tools that typically take inference engines from well-known ML libraries such as TensorFlow, Scikit-Learn, or PyTorch and adapted their code for execution. The results demonstrate the feasibility of running AI models on Low-Power resource-constrained IoT devices.

However, using the "train-then-deploy" approach raises uncertainties about how to manage the complete separation between the learning/training and runtime inference phases. Consequently, the second group of IoT devices resorts to using static AI models that cannot adapt to newly collected data without on-site data collection, analysis, and manual fine-tuning. If the edge has the necessary data to generate a new AI model, updating the AI model on an MCU requires manual intervention. Although the Spresense board used in [88] supports CircuitPython, providing some dynamic programming capabilities, this CircuitPython board does not support TensorFlow.

The third group aims to address the challenges identified in the second group. Researchers recognized the feasibility of achieving on-device TinyML inference and began exploring ways to dynamically interact with TinyML models. They realized that enabling Micropython in these devices could unlock various capabilities, particularly in supporting AI tasks like dynamic loading and execution of AI models.

Micropython implements a subset of Python functions and class libraries that directly replace Python libraries while considering the limitations of MCUs, such as RAM speed and size, process frequency, and the reduced number of cores. Micropython seamlessly handles TinyML functions, such as returning lists of data structures, iterating through lists, sorting, and filtering. These tasks can be instantly executed on the MCU. In contrast, using other languages requires users to delve deep, ensuring the code is correct, the firmware has been successfully built, and flashing it to the MCU has been executed smoothly.

There is currently no published paper detailing how to extend Micropython to incorporate AI. Nevertheless, some researchers have made progress on the technical aspects of this endeavor. For instance, in [81], [82], and [83], the integration of the TFLM library into Micropython has been implemented. They successfully compiled Micropython firmware, including a pre-trained TinyML model, which can be flashed into IoT Low-Power devices. These researchers drew inspiration from OpenMV projects, specifically Micropython-powered TFLM-integrated products [42]. OpenMV has been dedicated to developing machine vision modules for running machine vision algorithms on STM32.

While each of the existing studies offers distinct advantages, none has successfully addressed the challenges associated with the "train-then-deploy" design, resulting in static intelligence models. This static nature often impacts applications, making smart sensor platforms unreliable when deployed in the field. Additionally, the exchange of ML/TinyML models between the Edge and IoT devices remains unimplemented due to the requirement for a high-speed connection. Furthermore, none has developed dynamic AI model configurations, such as tensor arena size and AI operations resolving, leading to limited memory management.

Figure 11.1: Overview Architecture of a Dynamic AI-IoT in 5G infrastructure

Our contribution aims to provide a dynamic and robust solution to these challenges by leveraging 5G connectivity. This involves using 5G as a bridge between Edge and Low-Powered IoT devices, enabling the deployment of different TinyML models for various scenarios. The solution involves working with our implemented 5G infrastructure alongside our 5G-enabled, TFLM-integrated, and Micropython-powered IoT devices to facilitate dynamic exchanging and updating of AI models. Additionally, 5G offers an environment for seamlessly connecting a massive number of embedded devices by allowing scalability in data rates, power consumption, and mobility.

It is worth mentioning that none of the mentioned research endeavors can dynamically update AI models and optimize memory management with each update. Additionally, none of them have utilized cellular connectivity to enable Edge-to-IoT AI knowledge transfer. These advanced capabilities serve as the primary motivation for our contribution.

11.3 Proposed AI-IoT System for Dynamic AI Model Updates in Ultra-Low-Power 5G IoT Devices

5G, IoT, and AI can be integrated into end-to-end cloud-based scenarios, enabling rapid, distributed, and intelligent real-time decision-making. With IoT devices linked to the 5G edge, a single IoT device gains the intelligence to make predictions without relying on a central computing unit. Implementing AI technologies on IoT devices not only reduces latency but also enhances link capacity and network security [89].

The acceleration in the development of cellular IoT devices necessitates expandable and power-efficient communication technology. While 4G can connect around two thousand devices, 5G technology can support connectivity for up to one million devices over 1 Km^2 . Managing such density without proper oversight could significantly drain device batteries. To address this, Narrowband IoT (NB-IoT), a cellular low-power wide-area (LPWA) connectivity standard, is used. NB-IoT allows IoT devices to send data directly to the cloud without an intermediary gateway, improving power consumption in user devices. The need for intelligence in IoT devices becomes crucial, especially in scenarios with high traffic from all connected nodes. Therefore, incorporating an AI layer into the 5G-IoT architecture ensures the capability to process big data with minimal latency, reliability, and continuous network service accessibility [90].

Our novel contribution aims to offer a Dynamic AI-IoT solution for application on ultra-low-power 5G-enabled IoT devices. This represents a significant step toward implementing federated learning for constrained-resource devices.

11.3.1 Dynamic AI-IoT System Architecture

Dynamic AI-IoT is an approach to automatically utilize AI capabilities in IoT systems connected to a 5G network. This design aims to develop an AI-enabled IoT component that can communicate with the AI Development Engine in 5G environments. The general workflow of the proposed architecture is presented in Fig. 11.1. 5G network offers a high data rate, wide bandwidth, acceptable latency, and a massive number of connected IoT devices. The AI Development Engine is capable of designing, training, compressing, and converting AI models. The AI-enabled IoT component then can exchange data and make an inference on an IoT device associated with dynamic updates of AI models.

In the context of this design, it is essential to recognize that the forthcoming 6G connectivity era holds significant potential benefits for our system. With 6G's projected ultra-high-speed, low-latency connectivity, our architecture can achieve even faster response times, support more complex AI models, and offer improved efficiency and reliability. Moreover,

the expanded bandwidth and reduced latency characteristic of 6G networks can pave the way for new horizons in AI-powered IoT ecosystems.

In this design, a new IoT firmware has been implemented to support the Dynamic AI-IoT architecture by integrating Micropython, NB-IoT, AI capabilities and ULP unit. Flashing this firmware into IoT devices allows the tackling of the interactions with the AI Development Engine in a holistic manner. As depicted in Fig. 11.1, our proposed design shows that the AI Development Engine will be in the 5G edge computing. On the other hand, the IoT devices with the developed firmware can be connected to the 5G RAN, which oversees continuously receiving and sending the data to the 5G edge and then receiving and sending updates to IoT devices.

The proposed architecture in Fig. 11.1 shows how feasible it is to overcome the challenges raised in Section 11.2. This is a logical change that should be put in place to support federated learning in smart IoT applications. For example, the inference computing processes, AI model configurations, and AI model memory management should be done on IoT devices, resulting in a significant reduction in the communication overhead with the connected 5G Edge.

In the previous section, the architecture overview provided a better understanding of how our contributions add value to 5G networks. In this section, the internal components of our proposed AI-IoT architecture are explored. As shown in Fig. 11.2, there are three layers: the IoT Layer, AI-IoT Layer, and AI Layer. These layers are explained in the following subsections. It's worth mentioning that this figure, for all the layers, does not cover all the functional blocks but includes key components used in our design.

AI Layer

The AI layer belongs to 5G edge computing, where networking, computing, and storage services are offered with high availability and low latency. A substantial number of mobile and IoT devices can benefit from these services. On the other hand, the AI models are generated on this layer by our AI Development Engine which runs into multiple development

Figure 11.2: Proposed Dynamic AI-IoT Architecture

phases to eventually give different versions of TinyML models available for different AI-IoT use cases.

Data Generating: Predictive models are based on the collection of data, which can be gathered from a variety of sources. The more error-free the data collection is, the more accurate the predictive models are.

Data Splitting: Datasets are commonly divided into training, validation, and test subsets [91]. The validation dataset assesses model accuracy, while the test data evaluates model predictions against actual values.

Model Definition: Model development begins with neural network design, focusing on layer architecture and connectivity. The neural network should be designed to effectively capture patterns from the training data.

Model Training: Training involves setting various parameters, such as input-output pairs, epochs, and batch size. Validation data is used to monitor model performance during training.

Model Compression: Efficient network algorithms like MobileNets and SqueezeNet are used to reduce model size. MobileNets uses depth-wise and point-wise convolutions to build

lightweight deep neural networks, while SqueezeNet downsamples the data using special 1×1 convolution filters. Quantization [92] and pruning [93] techniques further enhance efficiency by reducing model weight size and computation [94].

Model Conversion: To make the model IoT-compatible, it needs to be converted to a suitable format, such as a C array [95] or serialized file. This conversion facilitates integration into IoT applications.

In the realm of developing efficient AI models for IoT devices, TensorFlow variants like TensorFlow Lite (TFLite) and TFLM have emerged as optimized frameworks for running models on small, low-powered devices such as mobile phones and microcontrollers. These variants offer compact binary sizes and minimal dependency requirements, making them ideal choices for resource-constrained IoT environments where standard C or C++ libraries may not be readily available [96].

AI-IoT Layer

This layer is a logical bridge between the AI and IoT layers with three main tasks.

Firstly, dynamic updating of TinyML models to improve the accuracy in real-time. After making an on-device inference and analyzing the model performance, there will be an option to send back some useful information from the IoT device directly to the AI Development Engine in the AI layer. Then, the AI Development Engine will consider the changes to re-train the model and ensure that the IoT device has an updated model.

Secondly, dynamic loading, reloading and executing multiple TinyML models to prevent any delay caused by adapting the IoT device to new models. The IoT device will be able to load multiple TinyML models and choose one of them to be executed at a time. Re-loading an updated model is done automatically so the IoT device can make new predictions. The only limitation would be the memory capacity of the IoT device. Therefore, the more available memory the IoT device has, the more TinyML models can be loaded at the same time. This seems to be an obvious capability but instead, it has not been yet achieved in the literature and we are proving the suitability of this approach.

Thirdly, dynamic memory optimization to enable efficient memory usage of IoT devices in real-time and without re-flashing the firmware. Three main key components can be optimized.

1. Memory alignment: Ensuring the starting memory address of the model is aligned correctly.
2. Tensor arena: Any model reserves only a required amount of memory regarding its size.
3. Registration of the model's operations: Only the operations used in the model's design are assigned to take memory space for execution.

In the context of the AI-IoT Layer described in Subsection 11.3.1, Micropython emerges as the best language for IoT devices to execute the three critical tasks:

1. Dynamic Model Updates: Micropython simplifies real-time model updates based on on-device inference, allowing for improved accuracy.
2. Dynamic Model Loading: It supports the dynamic loading and execution of multiple TinyML models, preventing delays during model adaptation.
3. Dynamic Memory Optimization: Micropython enables efficient memory usage without the need for firmware re-flashing, optimizing memory alignment, tensor arena utilization, and model operation registration.

Micropython's origin in Python 3.5 and its compatibility with various microcontrollers make it an ideal choice for IoT solutions. Its integration with IoT development tools like Atom further streamlines the development process.

IoT Layer

The IoT layer is the target environment for executing TinyML models, offering end-to-end AI solutions. At its core, the MCU handles inferences and data processing, utilizing RAM

and flash memory for storage. Networking and peripherals facilitate interactions with the environment, including other IoT devices, sensors, and actuators.

Furthermore, the Fipy platform, as depicted in Fig. 11.3 and powered by the Espressif ESP32 System-on-Chip (SoC), with its support for Micropython, an Ultra-Low-Power mode, and compatibility with five distinct network technologies, including NB-IoT cellular technology for direct cloud connectivity [97], has been selected as the foundation for our development. This choice is predicated on the platform's enhanced functionalities, rendering it particularly well-suited for the implementation of AI-IoT applications.

Figure 11.3: Fipy Features

11.4 Design of the Dynamic AI-IoT System

In this section, we delve into the intricate design aspects of an AI-IoT system that exhibits dynamic adaptability in response to changing conditions, facilitating real-time insights and actions. The subsequent subsections systematically dissect the various components of this system, unveiling its dynamic processes, interactive sequences, state transitions, and structural hierarchies.

11.4.1 Dynamic AI-IoT Process

Figure 11.4: Dynamic AI-IoT Process

In this section, we define the Dynamic AI-IoT Process, which is a framework for dynamically updating TinyML models on IoT devices efficiently and smoothly.

Let $M = \{L, C, W\}$ represent an AI model, where L stands for layers, C denotes connections between layers, and W represents the weights of artificial neurons within each layer. We distinguish two types of AI model updates:

1. $M_t = \{L', C', W'\}$ represents a total model update where all model components are updated, denoted as L' for layers, C' for connections, and W' for weights.

2. $M_p = \{L, C, W'\}$ represents a partial update, focusing solely on weight updates (W') as a result of further training.

Our proposal supports both types of updates: M_t and M_p . The algorithmic representation of these updates is provided in Algorithm (1). It outlines a process for dynamically and efficiently updating TinyML models on an IoT device. The following list describes the specific steps involved in this process:

1. **Initialization (Step 1):** The algorithm begins with the initialization of the IoT device, which is assumed to be equipped with an existing TinyML model and Micropython AI-supported Firmware.
2. **Firmware Flashing:** The algorithm proceeds by flashing the Micropython AI-supported Firmware onto the IoT device. This firmware contains the necessary infrastructure for handling TinyML models.
3. **Connecting to the AI Development Engine:** The IoT device establishes a connection to the AI Development Engine.
4. **Model Inference Loop (Step 2):** With the model configured, the algorithm performs an inference, which means it uses the model to make predictions or perform specific tasks based on incoming data.
5. **Data Transmission (Step 3):** After performing inference, the IoT device sends relevant data, which could include the results of the inference or other information, back to the AI Development Engine.
6. **Model Reception (Step 4):** Every N times (100 by default), The IoT device requests a model update from the AI Development Engine. The IoT device receives either an updated version of the existing TinyML model or a completely new one.
7. **Model Loading (Step 5):** The received TinyML model is loaded into the RAM of the MCU on the IoT device.

8. **Model Configuration (Step 6):** The algorithm configures the loaded model as needed. This step involves setting up the model's parameters, input/output formats, and any other necessary settings.
9. **Edge Reception (Step 7):** The AI Development Engine may generate a new TinyML model, possibly based on the data it has collected and processed.
10. **Model Generation (Step 8):** The AI Development Engine may generate a new TinyML model after N numbers of received values based on the data it has collected and processed or will load a completely new model if it has been requested by the administrator.

This algorithm enables an IoT device to continuously update its TinyML model, ensuring that it can adapt to changing data and requirements without the need for firmware re-flashing or significant device downtime.

11.4.2 Dynamic AI-IoT Sequence Diagram

The data flow in the system is illustrated by a sequence diagram in Fig. 11.5. The main components exchanging data in the system are the Firmware Development Engine, AI development Engine, Fipy as an IoT device, sensors and actuators. The data is propagated through the network from one component to another as follows:

1. The foundation for any IoT device to execute AI models and make predictions consists of two essential components: AI-supported firmware and an AI model. In our system, the Firmware Development Engine is where our customized Pycom Micropython firmware with TFLM extension has been developed and ensured to be executable on Fipy. Additionally, Fipy is equipped with the ability to update its firmware while still running, enabled by OTA update. The combination of OTA alongside NB-IoT provides Fipy with the capability to connect to 5G Edge through RAN and remotely update its firmware when updates in the capabilities of the AI IoT framework are required.
2. Meanwhile, the AI Development Engine generates AI models for various use cases, and only those TinyML models that can run on Fipy's MCU can be transferred. Transferring

Algorithm 1 Dynamic AI-IoT Model Updates**Require:** IoT Device, TinyML Model, Micropython AI-supported Firmware**Ensure:** Updating the IoT device with the new TinyML Model

```

1: IoT device: Initialize()                                ▷ Step 1
2: IoT device: Flash( $\mu$ Python Firmware)
3: IoT device: Connect(Edge), Inferences=0
4: while IoT device: True do                            ▷ Step 2
5:   Output=Infer(Inputs, Model)
6:   Inferences=Inferences+1
7:   Send(Edge, Output)                                  ▷ Step 3
8:   if Inferences % 100 = 0 then
9:     Model = Receive_Last_Model(Edge)                  ▷ Step 4
10:    Load(Model.L, Model.C, Model.W)                   ▷ Step 5
11:    Configure(Model)                                   ▷ Step 6
12:   end if
13: end while
14: Edge: Samples=0
15: while Edge: True do
16:   Store(Output)                                       ▷ Step 7
17:   Samples = Samples + 1
18:   if Samples % 100 == 0 then                         ▷ Step 8
19:     if Partial_Update() then
20:       LastModel=Train(LastModel,Output)
21:     end if
22:     if Full_Update() then
23:       LastModel=Load(Model.L,Model.C,Model.W)
24:     end if
25:   end if
26: end while

```

TinyML models is facilitated through RAN after enabling NB-IoT on Fipy. For simplicity, if Fipy is involved in two different use cases, two models (models A and B) are developed inside the AI Development Engine and then sent to Fipy.

3. To commence using the TFLM model, it needs to be loaded into Fipy's RAM, where the ESP32, the main chip of Fipy, can swiftly access the model's addresses. Loading the model into the RAM is one of the functions we developed to be executed from within Micropython. In Fig. 11.5, we illustrate the process of loading Model A into Fipy.

4. If Model A has been updated or there is a need to switch to Model B, the load function can reload the updated model or switch to a new model on demand. Importantly, this can be

Figure 11.5: Data Flow between the System Components

done without re-flashing the firmware; only the file of the new model needs to be transferred to the FiPy, providing a new level of flexibility.

5. Once the model is loaded, it should be configured dynamically. All the configuration functions were explained in the implementation section.

6. Sensors play a crucial role in enabling any IoT device to interact with the surrounding environment. In the case of Fipy, it is an extensible platform that allows connection to any sensor using widely supported buses. Several hats are available for Fipy, such as the

Pysense shield, enabling end-users to sense the environment using five different sensors: accelerometer, light, pressure, temperature, and humidity. Once the data is collected, it can be processed to obtain useful information for AI-IoT applications.

7. The next step is to prepare the model's input. Two essential methods have been developed to obtain the input's size and type from a dynamically updated model. These methods make it easy for Micropython to generate the input. The AI model may have a single input that can be stored in a variable, or multiple inputs that need another method to store them, such as arrays.

8. Once the model is loaded, and the input is defined, it is possible to insert the input into the model and make an inference. The model's output, whether it is a single prediction or multiple ones, can be obtained and saved for later use.

9. The ability to remake the inference is available. Enabling this functionality is significantly useful, especially when the model's input is a real stream, and the IoT device should keep predicting, creating an effective prediction pipeline.

10. For each prediction made, different actions can be taken. The AI-driven action could be as simple as changing an onboard LED's colour, and it could be as sophisticated as turning on a production line in a factory.

11. A dynamic AI-IoT system requires continuous improvements. Therefore, performance data and updates related to the model are sent to the AI Development Engine.

12. The AI Development Engine collects all the data coming back from Fipy and uses it to regenerate more accurate AI models.

13. Fipy will be waiting to receive the updated model or even a new one. This model shapes the purpose of the Dynamic AI-IoT application, whether it is only for continuous improvement or starting a completely new use case.

11.4.3 TinyML Model's State Diagram

The state diagram illustrated in Fig. 11.6 depicts how a TinyML model transitions from one state to another in a Dynamic AI-IoT application. For each state, there is a corresponding function designed to ensure seamless movement to the next state. These functions have

Figure 11.6: State Diagram

been detailed in the implementation section. The process begins with initializing the model, wherein sufficient memory space is reserved for the model to operate efficiently. Once reserved, the model enters the initialized state. Following this, the model is loaded into the IoT device's RAM. In this state, multiple models can be loaded, with consideration given to the latest one. The subsequent state involves configuring the model, and upon completion, the model transitions to the resolved state. After configuration, the interpret function ensures the model is ready for inference, moving it to the interpreted state. The invoked state is the subsequent logical state, occurring when the model has made predictions. This state can be revisited as needed, but only if the previous state was the interpreted state. The final state for any TinyML model is the freed state, where memory is cleared if there is no need to invoke the model any longer. In our Dynamic AI-IoT system, it is possible to load a new model or reload an updated model as needed. This capability is reflected in the state diagram, where the model can return to a loaded state from resolved, interpreted, or invoked states. This stands out as one of our key contributions.

11.4.4 Class Diagram

This section illustrates the design patterns applied in firmware development. Adapter and Façade designs have been combined to provide the user with an interface that grants access to all the implemented Micropython methods, whether from general Micropython modules, Pycom modules, or newly developed modules.

A façade pattern, as depicted in Fig 11.7, is a structural design pattern used as a wrapper to conceal the complexities of a large system by offering a simple interface to the client.

Figure 11.7: Façade and Adapter Diagram

In our development, the user can invoke a Micropython function from any subsystem without needing to know the implementation details behind it. Subsystems are hidden from the client, representing, for this paper, a comprehensive development of the TensorFlow module or any other built-in module. For instance, the user might wish to initialize or load a new TensorFlow model. In such cases, the Micropython interface acts as the façade, simplifying the user experience by shielding them from the complexities associated with Micropython objects and their bindings in Subsystem A.

On the other hand, our TensorFlow module, Subsystem A in Fig. 11.7, employs a C++ to Micropython adapter for every class in the TensorFlow library. When an adapter receives a call, it translates the incoming Micropython data into C++ and then passes the call to the appropriate methods for wrapping a TensorFlow object. Here is the process:

1. The adapter acquires an interface compatible with one of the Micropython objects.
2. Using this interface, the Micropython object can safely invoke the adapter's methods.
3. Upon receiving a call, the adapter transfers the request to the C++ object but in a format that the C++ object expects.

This approach enables the combination of statically compiled C++ functionality with the dynamically available capabilities provided by Micropython, facilitating the reprogramming of the device without the need for re-flashing.

11.5 Dynamic AI-IoT System Development

This section aims to highlight how to fulfill our four innovations mentioned earlier in the introduction section. To achieve this end, dynamic intelligent capabilities have been added to an IoT device to act as an independent smart device, and dynamically be adapted to the possible changes.

11.5.1 AI-IoT Firmware Development

The proposed design in Fig. 11.8 presents how to enable AI on ESP32 core devices using Micropython to achieve dynamic AI-IoT solutions. In other words, this section describes how

to compile MicroPython firmware after successfully porting external TFLM C++ modules. We have two frameworks and a compiler. The compiler used is the Xtensa GCC compiler that can be configured to report any error during the building process. The first framework is ESP-IDF in which TFLM C++ modules will be integrated and ready to be compiled, see (1) in Fig. 11.8. At this stage, a compiled TFLM C++ library would be generated and added to the MicroPython framework, see (2) and (3) in Fig. 11.8. After that, the TFLM C++ library will be linked and wrapped to MicroPython objects to create a new TFLM MicroPython library. The outcome of the second compilation is a binary file to be flashed into ESP32 core devices directly. The (4) and (5) steps in Fig. 11.8 show how to achieve this end. Next, TFLM C++ and MicroPython libraries will be explained to discuss how the work has been done.

Figure 11.8: Customized MicroPython Firmware with TFLM Extension

TensorFlow Lite Micro repository has the necessary functionalities to deal with a pre-trained TinyML model. From loading it properly to making an inference to get predictions. We have implemented a facade file with the key functions to be exposed to MicroPython. The following subsections explain each of those functions.

Initialization Functionality

The first function is the *initialize* function, responsible for allocating a specific amount of memory known as the "tensor arena." This memory allocation reserves space for the model's input, output, and intermediate arrays. It's crucial to note that the memory addresses for these arrays must align to 16 bytes, and the required size varies depending on the size of the AI model. Currently, there is limited documentation in the community on this process, making it valuable to provide detailed guidance on the procedure:

1. Get the size required to load the model.
2. Adding 16 extra bytes to guarantee we have enough space after the alignment. (0x10 in hex);
3. Round down to a 16 bytes dividable address by AND-ing 0x0F (last 4 bits to zeros);
4. The result is aligned to 16 bytes.

Loading Functionality

The following function is the *loading* of the model, which can be done in two ways: either as a compressed file or a compressed char array. In our proposed AI-IoT architecture, we have outlined how the model is compressed and converted after training. Subsequently, it becomes essential to develop the logic for handling the loading of the AI primitive functions for model execution. The *resolve* function is introduced to dynamically register only the operations utilized by the loaded model.

Our approach to this design has not been previously covered in the existing literature, and it is specifically optimized for memory-constrained IoT devices. Currently, developers typically use the *AllOpsResolver* to register all available operations in TFLM, resulting in a memory-intensive implementation. However, since a given model only utilizes a subset of these operations, developers have turned to the *MicroMutableOpResolver* to register only the necessary operations. The drawback of this approach is that developers must manually know and register all operations beforehand.

Our implementation of the resolve function incorporates an introspection capability, allowing it to query the AI model to determine the required operations. It then registers only

this subset, achieving a self-optimization of the memory footprint. This innovative approach enhances efficiency and addresses the limitations of the existing methods.

Interpreter Functionality

The next essential function is the *interpret* function. This function gathers the results of the preceding functions and combines them to create an object with complete access to the loaded model. For example, it retrieves pointers to the model's input and output tensors for later utilization, along with pointers to the model's input and output types and sizes. Once the input is ready, the interpreter is activated using the inference function to perform model inference and populate the predicted values in the output layer.

Inference Functionality

It executes the loaded model, utilizing the information available in the input and producing results accessible through the interpreter.

Generation of the Firmware

The TFLM project, along with our developed functions, can be integrated into the ESP-IDF framework and compiled using the Xtensa GCC compiler to generate the TFLM C++ library. However, directly flashing the compiled ESP-IDF as a binary file into Fipy, as done by other researchers, limits the AI capabilities of the device. This limitation arises because re-flashing the firmware is required every time a new model needs to be uploaded.

To overcome these challenges, the Micropython framework, implemented in native C, has been adjusted to incorporate the compiled TFLM C++ library. This modification enables the invocation of the previously described facade from C code, providing complete control over the model. The TFLM library can be imported, and its functions can be called within the Micropython scripting language. To achieve this, a Micropython object must be implemented, allowing the exposure of a Python library with all the functions described in the preceding subsections. These functions are, in turn, implemented using the native C language. Listing 11.1 provides an example of creating a Micropython object that calls the *interpret* function.

```

STATIC mp_obj_t interpreting()
{
    interprete();
    return mp_const_none;
}
MP_DEFINE_CONST_FUN_OBJ_0(interpreting_obj, interpreting);

```

Listing 11.1 Creating Micropython object

- Making the necessary bindings for new Micropython objects. This can be done in the same file or a separate file in the Micropython project. In both cases, a pointer to a new object should be added to the module's globals table, which in turn will be linked to the module globals dictionary, as shown in Listing 11.2.

```

STATIC const mp_map_elem_t microAIoT_module_globals_table[] = {
    { MP_OBJ_NEW_QSTR(MP_QSTR_interprete),          (
      mp_obj_t)&interpreting_obj },
};
STATIC MP_DEFINE_CONST_DICT(microAIoT_module_globals,
    microAIoT_module_globals_table);
const mp_obj_module_t microAIoT_module = {
    .base = { &mp_type_module },
    .globals = (mp_obj_dict_t *)&microAIoT_module_globals,
};

```

Listing 11.2 Micropython Bindings Example

- Compiling Micropython project to get the final firmware with TFLM capabilities.

Dynamic Usage of the Library in Micropython

Our AI-IoT Micropython module can be accessed from a Micropython program, similar to any other built-in module. The usage of the microAIoT module in Micropython is illustrated in Listing 11.3.

```

import microAIoT
microAIoT.initialize(tensor_arena_size)
microAIoT.load(TFLM_model_byte_array)
microAIoT.resolve()
microAIoT.interprete()
microAIoT.setValue(inputNumber, inputValue)
microAIoT.infer()
microAIoT.getValue(outputNumber)

```

Listing 11.3 New Module Usage in Micropython program

11.6 Validation Use Cases

Fig. 11.9 provides an overview of the different use cases used to validate our AI-IoT contribution. The following subsections elaborate on each of these use cases in detail.

Figure 11.9: Overview of Sine Wave Generation and Gesture Recognition Use Cases

11.6.1 Use Case A: Sine Wave Generation

This use case serves as a simple demonstration, illustrating the fundamental implementation of a fully dynamic AI-IoT application without introducing complex logic. This straightforward example highlights the basic utilization of TensorFlow Lite Micro. The 2.5 KB model is trained to replicate the mathematical sine function, capable of approximating

the sine of a number within the range of 0 to 2π . Subsequently, the model is converted for inference on a microcontroller. The primary aim of the initial experiment is to verify the feasibility of running the TinyML model on Fipy and dynamically interacting with it through Micropython.

The neural model's structure employed in this use case is outlined in Fig. 11.10, comprising three fully connected hidden layers designed for inferring the value of the sine function.

Figure 11.10: AI model structure used for Sine prediction

11.6.2 Use Case B: Gesture Recognition

Gestures, defined as meaningful movements used to interact with the environment, are recognized through a process known as gesture recognition. Embedded devices are increasingly incorporating emerging technologies to implement AI use cases involving gesture recognition. In the second experiment, a pre-trained TinyML model from TensorFlow is employed to recognize specific gestures. The model utilizes real-time data streaming from a 3-axis accelerometer as input, providing a classified set of recognized gestures as output. The source code for this project is available in the official TensorFlow repository, specifically the magic wand example.

For the implementation of this use case, Fipy is connected to Pysense, enabling the utilization of an integrated acceleration sensor. Data is streamed from the Pysense 3-axis accelerometer to feed the model's input. The magic wand TinyML model is trained to identify three gestures: a clockwise circle or "ring" gesture, a capital "W" or "wing" gesture, and a right-to-left "slope" gesture. When one of these gestures is detected, the onboard RGB LED will illuminate in green, blue, or red, corresponding to the performed gesture, serving as an example of AI application.

The model is a 20 KB Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) trained on a gesture dataset obtained from 10 individuals who performed four gestures (Ring, Wing, Slope, and an unknown gesture) fifteen times each. The model's input comprises raw accelerometer data in an array of 384 values, representing 128 times the real X, Y, and Z axes. The output provides probability scores for the three recognized gestures and an unknown gesture. The sum of these scores is 1, with a probability of 0.8 or higher indicating a confident prediction of a given gesture.

Figure 11.11: AI model structure used for Gesture recognition

The neuronal network structure for training the CNN model in this application is depicted in Fig. 11.11. In contrast to the first use case, this one involves more operations in building the model, including FullyConnected, DepthwiseConv2D, MaxPool2D, and Conv2D operations. The Pysense's built-in accelerometer was configured at 50Hz, and data was downsampled to 25Hz, aligning with the model's training rate. The software accumulates sensor readings until sufficient data (128 readings) is obtained to perform a prediction.

Dealing with accelerometer data can present variations and unexpected values. To enhance accuracy, the model is designed to consistently predict the same gesture multiple times, boosting confidence in predictions. In Micropython, the previous and current predictions are tracked. If a specific prediction persists for a defined number of consecutive times, it is reported as the detected gesture; otherwise, it is identified as an unknown gesture.

The two previously described use cases are evaluated to demonstrate the feasibility of Dynamic AI-IoT implementation. The focus of the test is on loading a TinyML model into Fipy and executing inference. The experimentation is divided into three parts: execution

time, memory usage, and power consumption. CPU usage is excluded from this test, as the CPU runs continuously, even in the absence of processing tasks, due to the "idle loop" code snippet. All experiments were conducted in a Micropython environment using Atom software with the Pymakr plugin.

11.7 Results

11.7.1 Model Loading Results

To assess the loading time, we conducted an experiment involving the consecutive loading of the sine AI model 100 times. After this continuous reloading, a deliberate switch occurred to initiate the reloading of the gesture recognition model, which was then reloaded another 100 times. As depicted in Fig. 11.12, the average loading time for the sine model was 0.69 ± 0.05 milliseconds. On the other hand, the average loading time of the gesture recognition model was 0.73 ± 0.03 milliseconds.

Figure 11.12: Loading Time

11.7.2 Model Inference Results

For evaluating the inference time, we loaded the sine model and then called its inference function 100 times to improve the accuracy of the inference time measurement. Following

that, we intentionally switched to calling the inference function of the gesture recognition model 100 times. As illustrated in Fig. 11.13, the results revealed that the average inference time for the sine model was 44.63 ± 0.08 milliseconds, whereas the gesture recognition model, on average, had an inference time of 48.05 ± 0.27 milliseconds.

It is worth mentioning that these results allow the tiny IoT device to provide more than 20 times per second the interface of the values which is a very decent real-time performance. It validates the suitability of the proposed approach for close to real-time applications using AI IoT architectures.

Figure 11.13: Inference Time

11.7.3 Memory Usage in Model Loading

The average allocated memory for loading our two different models was measured without using Micropython's available memory management garbage collector (gc) utility. We loaded each of the AI models 100 times. Surprisingly, it was observed that both models consumed the same amount of memory. More interestingly, the repetitive loading of both similar and dissimilar models resulted in a significant reduction in available memory, as shown in Fig. 11.14. This is because there is no automatic unloading of the previous model when loading a new one, impacting the available memory for subsequent model loading. Notably, the

standard deviation of the free memory is approximately 6.5 KB, reflecting fluctuations in the described mechanisms.

When we enable the Micropython garbage collector, as shown in 11.15, the results consistently follow a uniform distribution, with a standard deviation of 0 KB for free memory. This indicates that the garbage collector effectively clears 100% of the allocated memory. The garbage collector is employed just before and after loading our TinyML models.

Figure 11.14: Memory Usage for Loading without GC

Figure 11.15: Memory Usage for Loading with GC

11.7.4 Memory Usage in Inference

An analog experiment was conducted to assess memory consumption during the inference task. Without using a garbage collector, the average memory allocated for the sine model's inference is $0.21 \text{ KB} \pm 0.00$, and for the gesture recognition model, it is $0.26 \pm 0.00 \text{ KB}$, as depicted in Fig. 11.16. The significant change is evident in the fluctuation of free memory, which consistently decreases with each execution of the inference task. To be precise, there is a total decrease of 10.73 KB for each inference step with the sine AI model and 11.89 KB for the gesture recognition model. This continuous decrease is primarily attributed to the preparation of the input and output of the AI model, both directly handled by Micropython. Once ready, they are passed to the native C implementation, but this allocated memory is never freed. Consequently, in the next step, a new allocation in Micropython for the input and output is carried out.

The problem is resolved by enabling the Micropython garbage collector. This has a significant impact as it can free up all the memory allocated in the previous inference step, clearing 100% of the allocated memory. These outcomes are illustrated in Fig. 11.17.

Figure 11.16: Memory Usage for Inferencing without GC

This memory management technique ensures that the AI model can run for an extended period without experiencing memory shortages, validating the suitability of the proposed solution for the prolonged execution of AI models in IoT devices.

Figure 11.17: Memory Usage for Inferencing with GC

11.7.5 Model Update Time

In the context of dynamic TinyML deployment on IoT devices, it is essential to evaluate the time required to update and transmit TinyML models to these devices. To provide insights into this aspect, we measured the time it takes to transmit two different TinyML models to our IoT device, the FiPy. The first model, Sine Wave Generation, has a file size of 2.5 KB, while the second model, Gesture Recognition, has a larger size of 20 KB. These models represent typical use cases in the AI-IoT domain, with varying model sizes.

Our results reveal that transmitting the Sine Wave Generation model to the FiPy device requires approximately 0.068 seconds. In contrast, the larger Gesture Recognition model can be transmitted in roughly 0.545 seconds. These time frames account for the complete process of model transfer.

For updating the model, it is important to keep predictions running smoothly. Therefore, the system is designed to pause for less than 2 seconds during the update without requiring a FiPy re-flash or restart.

11.7.6 Power Consumption

One of the primary deciding factors for choosing IoT devices like these over more powerful options such as the Raspberry Pi 4 is mainly associated with power consumption. Therefore,

measuring power consumption provides insight into how long the IoT device can function on a given amount of energy or what power budget is needed for continuous AI IoT use cases. In this experiment, we utilized a USB Meter, illustrated in Fig. 11.18, to measure the device's current and voltage during a specific task. The power consumption in watts was calculated from these metrics.

The experiment proceeded as follows: first, the gesture recognition model was loaded 100 times, followed by 100 iterations of inference on the last loaded model. As shown in Fig. 11.19, the average power consumption for loading the gesture recognition model 100 times was 488.8 milliwatts, while inference consumed 485.89 milliwatts. Both exhibited similar and consistent trends, with standard deviations of just 27.44 milliwatts for loading and 31.95 milliwatts for inference.

These consumption results are notably more efficient than other devices like the Raspberry Pi, which consumes around 6 watts when using all available cores and almost 3 watts in an idle state. This key finding makes this architecture ideal for prolonged deployments where battery life and lasting performance are critical elements for the success of the use case.

Figure 11.18: Power measurements using USB Meter

Figure 11.19: Power Consumption

11.7.7 Overhead Time

To understand the cost of loading and executing AI models on IoT devices using Micropython, we measured the time required for these tasks without Micropython. Specifically, we used the original C++ implementation and compared the results. Table 11.2 demonstrates a noticeable difference for Model A (sine prediction) when loaded and executed in different languages. On the other hand, for Model B (gesture recognition), adding dynamic AI-IoT capabilities only increased the execution time by 6 ms. These values represent averages from 10 different executions.

It is important to note that as the size of the AI model increases, the difference in inference time between C++ and Micropython becomes smaller. This overhead adds value by allowing the uploading of multiple homogeneous and heterogeneous AI models in real-time without the need to update the device firmware. This capability is crucial for advanced use cases involving federated learning, online learning, and more.

11.8 Limitations and Challenges

The implementation of a Dynamic AI system on the FiPy device, while promising, presents a set of inherent limitations and associated challenges.

Table 11.2: Overhead time between C++ and Micropython

	C++	Micropython
Loading Time (Model A)	0.027ms	0.69ms
Inferencing Time (Model A)	0.226ms	44.63ms
Loading Time (Model B)	0.026ms	0.73ms
Inferencing Time (Model B)	42ms	48.05ms

Resource Constraints and Scalability: FiPy devices are characterized by limited memory and processing capabilities, which can include empirically validated limits such as the 2.4 Mb maximum model size allowed. This constraint necessitates careful consideration when dealing with larger and more complex AI models, thereby impacting scalability.

Energy Efficiency and Latency Optimization: Achieving energy efficiency and optimizing latency, especially in real-time applications, presents a dual challenge. Frequent AI model updates must be balanced to prevent excessive power consumption without compromising responsiveness.

Interoperability: FiPy devices are designed to adapt to various connection technologies. Ensuring smooth transitions between them can be complex in heterogeneous IoT environments.

Handling Large AI Models: Transmitting AI models exceeding 500 KB in size is a significant challenge. Memory allocation constraints on the FiPy device come to the forefront, requiring careful management when dealing with more extensive models.

11.9 Conclusion and Future Work

In this paper, we have introduced a groundbreaking IoT-based architecture designed to empower ultra-low-power and cost-effective IoT devices with Dynamic AI capabilities. Through the practical implementation of this architecture on a Micropython-enabled and AI-enhanced IoT device, we have successfully developed two distinct applications. Notably, our system demonstrated exceptional performance, with the ability to load a 20 KB TinyML

model for sine prediction over 136 thousand times in less than a second, while executing the same model over 2 thousand times within the same timeframe.

Our results unequivocally illustrate the transformative potential of our Dynamic AI-IoT system. It equips connected IoT devices with autonomous AI functionalities, encompassing self-configuration of internal AI models, memory management optimization, and dynamic loading and execution of multiple AI models. Furthermore, the utilization of Micropython enhances code reusability for AI purposes. Significantly, our system offers a dynamic solution for remote IoT device updates, with minimal impact on system performance, achieving near real-time inference with power consumption below 0.5 Watts. This outcome holds considerable promise for a wide range of practical applications.

The system has demonstrated significant potential across various domains, including industrial IoT, agriculture, smart cities, healthcare, retail, and environmental monitoring. It offers real-time data analysis, predictive maintenance, efficiency enhancements, safety improvements, and sustainability. The Dynamic AI-IoT system stands poised to bring transformative advancements, promoting efficiency and enhancing the quality of life in these diverse applications within 5G and beyond systems.

It is important to note that our current implementation follows a train-then-deploy approach. However, future work will explore the integration of the federated and transfer learning approaches, particularly suited for applications that do not necessitate full on-device training. Additionally, ongoing research will focus on incorporating dynamic switching among various connection technologies, such as Wi-Fi, LoRa, and Sigfox. This innovation will enable IoT devices to seamlessly transition between different use cases, thus expanding the operational scope and versatility of the Dynamic AI-IoT system.

Chapter 12

Transfer Learning-Enabled IoT System for Continuous Prediction of Vehicle CO₂ Concentration

This chapter contains an exact copy of content present in the research paper [7], where Mohammad Alselek is the leading author and main contributor. It has already been peer-reviewed, accepted, and published.

12.1 Abstract

In this paper, we present the design, implementation, and deployment of an IoT-based system for machine learning (ML)-based real-time prediction of CO₂ exhaust concentrations in road vehicles, by means of transfer learning. The system offers a scalable and cost-effective solution for monitoring and predicting CO₂ exhaust concentrations from a vehicle fleet. Moreover, the system is specifically designed to be installed in a low-powered microcontroller unit (MCU) to collect and process data from a CO₂ sensor, as well as to perform ML-based emission prediction without a sensor. To accomplish this, we have developed an artificial neural network (ANN) model able to generate training labels to further train subsequent ANN models via transfer learning mechanisms. The resulting models are sent to the IoT

devices installed in the vehicle to perform the on-board predictions. Empirical experiments show very promising results in terms of high prediction accuracy and satisfactory transfer learning loop execution time.

12.2 Introduction

The use of vehicles in urban areas is a major contributor to carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions, which have significant negative impacts on the environment and human health. CO₂ emissions from vehicles are a primary source of greenhouse gases, which contribute to global warming and climate change [98].

There are several solutions being developed and implemented to reduce CO₂ emissions from vehicles, and one particularly promising approach is the use of an internet of things (IoT)-based system for continuous prediction of vehicle's exhausts CO₂ concentration. This system addresses the limitations of traditional methods and offers a cost-effective and scalable way to monitor and reduce emissions [99].

In this paper, we propose a system that utilizes low-cost and energy-efficient IoT devices, such as the FiPy development board (ESP32), which can be easily installed in vehicles and used to collect and transmit data in real-time [100]. The system also employs a transfer learning algorithm, which allows for efficient and accurate prediction of CO₂ concentration based on limited data inputs. One of the key benefits of this system is its ability to continuously adapt and improve over time. By using machine learning (ML) algorithms to update and refine the model's accuracy, the system can provide more accurate predictions with fewer data, which makes it more cost-effective and efficient than traditional methods [98]. Additionally, because the system operates in real-time, it can provide immediate feedback to drivers and fleet managers, allowing for quick adjustments to be made to reduce emissions.

The proposed system architecture comprises a CO₂ sensor situated within the vehicle exhaust pipe that collects real-time measurements. The data is transmitted to an edge server to train the initial AI model, which serves as the baseline model generated from the physical

monitoring system. The transfer learning process is then initiated to enable the IoT devices to perform continuous CO₂ concentration prediction.

It is noteworthy that the system is scalable to be applied on multiple vehicles allowing for a highly adaptable environment and optimal results, where a seamless MCU model integration is successfully performed. The proposed system has several advantages and contributions, which include:

- A new IoT-based system to monitor and predict CO₂ concentration of vehicles in real-time.
- A novel approach that utilizes transfer learning to continuously enhance the system's prediction accuracy without requiring large amounts of data.
- The adoption of the FiPy, which represents the forefront of low-cost and energy-efficient IoT devices that can be effortlessly integrated into existing vehicle systems.
- The development of a communication middleware to enable exchanging data between the FiPy and the edge server.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 13.3 describes the proposed system architecture and introduces its components. Section 12.4 presents the development of the ground truth model. Section 12.5 details the design, implementation, and validation of the transfer learning-based IoT system. Section 13.5 discusses the findings obtained during this research, and Section 13.6 concludes the paper.

12.3 Proposed IoT-based system for Real-Time CO₂ Prediction

In this research, we have developed an IoT-based system that utilizes cutting-edge hardware and software technologies to monitor and predict CO₂ concentration in real-time. The system comprises a CO₂ sensor installed in the vehicle, a microcontroller unit (MCU) that reads

Figure 12.1: System diagram of the proposed IoT-based system for real-time CO₂ prediction for multiple vehicles.

sensor data and gathers some vehicle operational metrics from the Controller Area Network (CAN) bus, and then transmits them to an edge server for further processing.

For the initial CO₂ data collection process we have employed an NDIR-based SprintIR-R 20 CO₂ sensor to measure the concentration of CO₂ in the exhaust gases with an accuracy of ± 70 PPM, a resolution of 10 ppm (parts per million), and a maximum sampling frequency of 50 Hz. As for the IoT devices used, the system utilised a Pycom FiPy development board, which is based on the ESP32 MCU. It is specifically designed for IoT applications and highly optimized for low-power operation, making it ideal for integration into the existing vehicle system given its minimally invasive installation and energy-efficient usage. Furthermore, its use has been chosen based on its wireless communication capabilities, since it provides a wide range of wireless connectivity options, including Wi-Fi, Bluetooth, and LoRaWAN.

Fig. 12.1 depicts the system architecture, composed of four main components: the source vehicle, the target vehicles, the edge server, and the communication middleware. Firstly, the aforementioned physical CO₂ sensor was installed in the source vehicle as presented in [101], and used to measure and collect its exhausts CO₂ concentration alongside a set of vehicle operational parameters that conform to the main dataset, marked in red. Subsequently, a main model was trained and instantiated in the server edge upon the gathered dataset.

On the other hand, the target vehicles were provided with a FiPy programmed to continuously record the operational parameters present in the collected dataset. Thus, this collected data was sent periodically to the edge server, where the previously mentioned main model was used to generate AI-based labels, i.e., the corresponding CO₂ concentration, which coupled to the newly gathered data from the target vehicles, conformed new training and evaluation datasets.

Furthermore, a transfer learning algorithm was employed to train and create another ML model with the newly generated dataset. Lastly, the resulting transfer learning model was optimized and converted into an MCU-compatible model and subsequently sent to the IoT devices for continuous prediction of CO₂ concentration. The communication middleware facilitates communication between the Pycom FiPy development board and the edge server using RESTful API commands.

The proposed system architecture facilitates the real-time monitoring and prediction of CO₂ concentrations by utilizing a physical CO₂ sensor and the main model, as depicted in Fig. 12.1 via the red workflow. Additionally, transfer learning techniques have been employed to continually enhance the system's prediction accuracy without the need for large quantities of data without the use of any physical CO₂ sensor. By transferring the weights obtained from pre-trained models and continuously learning from new data, the transfer learning algorithms enable the system to adapt and improve its prediction accuracy over time, as illustrated in the blue workflow in Fig. 12.1. This approach ensures that the system delivers reliable and precise predictions even under dynamic driving conditions.

We have devised and implemented a comprehensive framework that facilitates the automatic uploading of data from the FiPy device, the creation of transfer learning-based dataset, the initialization of training, the optimization and the conversion of trained models, the retrieval of the model into the FiPy, and the execution of the model for generating predictions. This iterative process can be repeated as many times as necessary, with the best performing model being selected for deployment on the FiPy device. Furthermore, this framework is scalable to accommodate multiple vehicles, with each vehicle following its individual sequence of operations.

The combination of our innovative system architecture, revolutionary approach to transfer learning and adoption of the latest low-cost and energy-efficient IoT devices has enabled us to achieve our proposed contributions and provide a highly effective and efficient solution for continuously monitoring and predicting CO₂ concentration from vehicle's exhaust.

12.4 Main Model Development

The main model's network architecture used in this study is a modified version of the work presented in [43]. This work unveiled a recurrent long short-term memory (LSTM)-based artificial neural network (ANN) that utilized the following 8 vehicle operational parameters as input: vehicle acceleration (m/s^2), engine exhaust flow rate (kg/h), engine mode, engine speed (RPM), vehicle speed (MPH), mass air flow (g/min), engine coolant temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$),

and hybrid battery state of charge (%). In this study, the same set of input parameters was employed.

As for the model architecture, the network presents an input layer of dimensions 32x8, meaning that the model considers the previous 32 states of the inputs to perform the inference. Later on, the model features two stacked LSTM layers with 128 and 64 neurons, respectively. The second LSTM layer has a dropout layer with a dropout rate of 0.2. Moreover, a flatten layer after the second LSTM layer precedes another dropout layer with a dropout rate of 0.3 and dense layers with 8 neurons. Lastly, the model outputs the predicted CO₂ as a single value.

Furthermore, as for the model training, the dataset mentioned in the previous section was used to train and evaluate the model accuracy using a batch size of 32 for 50 epochs. The loss function employed was the mean squared error. To prevent over-fitting, we implemented a changing learning rate scheduler using Equation 12.1 to compute the learning rate at each epoch t . The model achieved an accuracy of 97.22% (as measured by the R2 score) during evaluation tests.

$$Lr_t = \begin{cases} 2 \times 10^{-5}, & \text{if } t < 10 \\ Lr_{t-1} \cdot e^{-0.1}, & \text{if } t \geq 10 \end{cases} \quad (12.1)$$

In order to facilitate the model convergence during training, we applied normalization to the dataset to rescale values between 0 and 1. We used Equation 12.2 to compute the normalized value for the i th feature. In this equation, \tilde{x}_i represents the normalized i th value, x_i is the original i th value, and x_{min} and x_{max} are the minimum and maximum values of the feature in the dataset, respectively.

$$\tilde{x}_i = \frac{x_i - x_{min}}{x_{max} - x_{min}}. \quad (12.2)$$

12.5 Transfer Learning-based Loop Development

This section outlines the process of developing a machine learning model for real-time prediction of vehicle CO₂ concentration using transfer learning. The goal of this implementation is to create an accurate model that can be easily updated on the FiPy board. The transfer learning development loop consists of several phases, which are numbered in Fig. 12.1.

The algorithm provided in Algorithm 2 outlines the functions and their dependencies used in each iteration of the transfer learning model development process.

Algorithm 2 Transfer Learning Model Development for Vehicle n

Require: Main Model, Vehicle n 's parameters

Ensure: C array model for integration into MCU

- | | |
|--|-------------|
| 1: Get parameters from OBDII data | ▷ Task 1 |
| 2: Label data for vehicle n using main model and OBDII parameters | ▷ Task 2, 3 |
| 3: Train the model using the main model's weights and the labeled data | ▷ Task 4, 5 |
| 4: Prune the model to reduce its size | ▷ Task 6 |
| 5: Convert the pruned model to TFLite format | ▷ Task 7 |
| 6: Convert the TFLite model to a C array format | ▷ Task 8 |
| 7: Send the C array model to the MCU | ▷ Task 9 |
-

The algorithm takes two inputs: the pre-trained main model and the parameters specific to vehicle n , which are collected from the vehicle's CAN bus through the OBDII port. The goal of the algorithm is to develop a model for vehicle n based on the pre-trained main model using transfer learning. At the end of the algorithm, the C array model is available for integration into the FiPy for use in vehicle n . The algorithm makes use of transfer learning and pruning to customize the main model for the specific vehicle, resulting in a more accurate and efficient model.

To begin the model development, we collect the necessary vehicle parameters from the OBDII port. The collected data is then segmented and transmitted to the edge server, with an

average transmission time of 3.69 seconds per segment. The following subsections detail the remaining steps required to complete the loop.

12.5.1 Transfer Learning Model Training

To create an LSTM model capable of predicting CO₂ emission concentrations, we employed a transfer learning algorithm. This technique allows the model to utilize the pre-existing weights and biases of a pre-trained main model and adapt to new data. By doing so, we can train the model with smaller datasets, making it quicker and easier to deploy on the FiPy board.

To evaluate the performance of the main model, we utilized a testing dataset for validation and compared its accuracy with the ground truth CO₂ concentration values. An example of the distribution of the ground truth and main model's CO₂ predicted concentration is visualized in the histogram shown in Fig. 12.2a. In this example, we observe that the predicted CO₂ concentration values closely align with the distribution of the actual values, achieving a similarity of 95.8% compared to the collected ground truth.

To assess the performance of the transfer learning model, we employed a testing dataset and compared its accuracy against the ground truth values. As shown in Fig. 12.2b, the transfer learning model achieved an accuracy of 97.62%, which surpasses the accuracy of the main model at 97.22%. These results indicate that while the main model achieved a high level of agreement with the ground truth, the transfer learning model outperformed it.

The transfer learning model was trained with carefully selected hyperparameters, including 15 epochs, an Adam optimizer, a learning rate of 0.00001, and a batch size of 64. These hyperparameters were fine-tuned to optimize the model's performance on the testing dataset. Remarkably, the transfer learning technique employed in the pre-trained model contributed to the computational efficiency of the training process by reducing the number of epochs required for training. Specifically, we only needed to train the model for 15 epochs, as opposed to 50 epochs applied for the main model training.

The transfer learning technique was effective in generating an accurate LSTM model for predicting CO₂ emissions. By using pre-existing weights and biases, the model could

adapt to new data and provide accurate predictions even with a smaller training dataset. The hyperparameters were carefully tuned to achieve the best performance, and the training process was computationally efficient. These findings contribute to the development of more accurate and efficient models for predicting CO₂ emissions in real-world scenarios.

12.5.2 Model Optimization and Conversion

Tasks 2 to 9 mentioned in Algorithm 2 were executed on a server equipped with a 16-core Intel Core i7 CPU clocked at 2.3 GHz, 32 GB of memory, and an NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3060 GPU. However, the target device, a FiPy board, has limited resources with an Xtensa® dual-core 32-bit LX6 microprocessor and only 4 MB of memory. Therefore, we optimized the transfer learning model developed in Task 6 by using model pruning to increase sparsity, reduce overfitting, and enhance generalization, leading to a model accuracy of 97.77%.

After optimization, we converted the model to TensorFlow Lite format and a C array to enable it to run efficiently on the FiPy board for real-time predictions of CO₂ concentration [100]. The final model size was 132.5 KB.

12.5.3 MCU CO₂ Emissions Concentration Prediction Process

Once the FiPy installed in the target vehicle is provided with an optimized and MCU-compatible ML model (seen at the bottom of Fig. 12.3), it is ready to perform the vehicle CO₂ exhaust concentration predictions. To be more precise, when the edge server sends the model in the format of a C array, this model is then received by the FiPy and dynamically loaded in the device memory without any human intervention nor process interruption.

As a result, when the FiPy starts over again its vehicle's operational parameters data collection process, the resulting metrics are later on used to perform the model inference. Seemingly to the way this data was initially collected, as expressed in Section 12.4, the 8 vehicle operational parameters are accessed from the CAN bus and requested via unified diagnostics services (UDS) protocol. One of the benefits of this connection is that it can be easily plugged in and out into the vehicle's OBDII port, which is present in any European

(a) Ground Truth Labeling vs Original Trained Model Labeling.

(b) Ground Truth Labeling vs Transfer Learning-based Model Labeling.

Figure 12.2: A comparison between the accuracy of the main model and the models generated before and after the transfer learning training.

Figure 12.3: Transfer learning-based CO₂ emission concentration prediction sequence diagram.

light-duty vehicle manufactured since 2003, which makes it compatible with almost every currently existing model.

After receiving all the necessary parameters from the CAN bus, the FiPy prepares an input array by normalizing the values as expressed in Equation 12.2 and allocating them in a buffer of dimensions 32x8. This ensures that the model recognizes the input parameters in the same format as it was trained. When the model performs the inference, the resulting values are then de-normalized to convert them to their original scale. It is noted that the experiments carried out during the execution of the ML model in the MCU averaged an execution time of 61.99 ms.

12.5.4 Model Update Frequency

The frequency at which the transfer learning loop needs to be executed for updating the model in the proposed IoT system for continuous prediction of vehicle CO₂ concentration is a critical aspect. To address this question, Fig. 12.3 outlines the necessary tasks for updating the model while ensuring the continuous operation of the system. The transfer learning loop is intended to keep running continuously, with a file received from the MCU serving as an event trigger for the update process (Task 1 in Fig. 12.1). The ideal time for executing the loop is calculated to be 399.54 seconds, which represents the time difference between preparing a new file (Task 1) and executing the remaining tasks of the loop.

Regarding the model update process, it is essential to ensure that the prediction of CO₂ concentration is not disrupted for an extended period. As a result, the system has been designed to pause for less than two seconds during the update process without the need to re-flash or restart the FiPy. The duration of the prediction interruption is determined by the time needed to replace the old model with the new one, which is the sum of the replacement time for the old model with the new one (0.05174 ms) and the loading time for a model of 132.5 KB, which is around 1125 ms, the time required to load the new model into the memory.

12.5.5 Communication Middleware Development

The system aims to enable continuous transfer learning model development and consists of two main components: the edge server and the FiPy board. To enable communication between the two, there are several communication mechanisms, including MQTT (Message Queuing Telemetry Transport) and REST (REpresentational State Transfer) protocols [102].

While MQTT is widely used for IoT applications, we chose to use REST protocol for our system. REST follows the request/response architecture and uses HTTP methods like GET and POST to exchange data. Unlike MQTT, it does not use a broker component, which simplifies the system architecture and reduces communication overhead. Furthermore, REST's bus-based architecture and low bandwidth usage make it ideal for IoT applications with limited resources [103].

To ensure seamless communication between the FiPy device and the edge server, our middleware uses RESTful API server technology and HTTP methods. The middleware collects and processes data from the FiPy device and sends it to the server for model training. Once the model is trained, the server sends back the updated model to the FiPy device. This continuous loop ensures that the model is constantly updated with new data, leading to higher accuracy and better predictions over time.

To support REST on the FiPy device, we customized its firmware to include the requests library. During testing and analysis of the uploading and downloading processes, we found that the middleware was able to transfer data between the FiPy and the edge server quickly and efficiently. The average time to retrieve the relevant segment of parameters from the FiPy using a POST request was approximately 3.69 seconds, while sending the generated model to the FiPy using another POST request took an average of 0.9 seconds.

12.6 Discussion

One of the questions that arose during the experiments carried out was the size of the file sent from the FiPy to the server containing the vehicle operational parameters. Given the resource constraints derived from the use of the FiPy, files larger than 500 kB represented

Figure 12.4: Accuracy and similarity of the models after labeling and after transfer learning training.

an issue when dealing with MCU memory allocations. On the contrary, small files would cause inefficient use of the communication middleware, leading to a further limitation of the number of model executions. The experience acquired from the experiments pointed out that files containing 2500 tuples of data would have an adequate trade-off between file size, being this approximately 135 kB of data. Therefore, the FiPys were programmed to send the collected data to the server once the file contained 2500 tuples of data, as depicted in Fig. 12.3.

Furthermore, a phenomenon identified during the experiments is that the resulting transfer learning model's accuracy is greatly influenced by the quality of the generated labels. Fig. 12.4 illustrates 10 different transfer learning model performance scores (orange line), each of them utilizing a different training dataset obtained from the approaches explained in Section 12.5. As can be seen in the picture, the green line represents the similarity percent (R2 score) of the labeling data generated with the main model compared to the ground truth CO₂ concentration. Despite the good accuracy exhibited during the validation of the main model (97.22%), it is obvious that the resulting generated labeling would imply a degree or error.

Table 12.1: Transfer learning loop average execution time per individual task.

Task id	Task name	Average execution time (s)
1	Fill in file to send with vehicle metrics	500.01
2	Send segment to edge server	3.69
3	Labeling	3.45
4	Transfer learning training	5.05
5	Model pruning	71.15
6	Model conversion	16.23
7	Send model from server to FiPy	0.9
Total		600.48

As a result, in some of the training segments shown, such as in segments 4 to 6, the similarity dropped below 97.22%, whereas in the rest of the segments, the similarity is greater. As a consequence, in most of the trainings, the generated model after the transfer learning showed a proportional accuracy to the similarity of the generated labeling.

In this case, the accuracy of the main model (represented with the blue line) can serve as a comparative mark to determine the suitability of a particular transfer learning model to substitute the model already present in the target vehicle's FiPy. This was the final criteria used, as depicted in Fig. 12.3.

Lastly, in order to provide insights about the total elapsed time for a single iteration of the proposed transfer learning loop, Table 12.1 reflects the average elapsed time per task. As seen, the task that takes the longest is the iterative FiPy data gathering process. This is due to the fact that the FiPy performs vehicle operational parameters collection at a rate of 5 Hz. Since the FiPys were programmed to send files with 2500 tuples, the resulting average elapsed time for recording and generating the segment is 500.01 seconds. The resulting total time was 600.48 seconds from the moment the initial gathering starts until the FiPy receives an MCU-compatible model.

Regarding the actual implementation, Fig. 12.5 illustrates the system installation as currently implemented. The figure showcases the connection between the MCU and the

Figure 12.5: System installation with CAN and Wi-Fi connections.

vehicle's CAN bus via the OBDII port. Furthermore, the MCU is linked to a Wi-Fi network to enable seamless communication with the edge server and initiate the transfer learning process. Notably, the MCU is housed in a 3D-printed compact box that features an OBDII interface and plug-and-play compatibility. This design ensures that the system can be quickly and easily installed in any compatible vehicle.

12.7 Conclusion

In this paper, we present an IoT solution for predicting CO₂ concentration in vehicles based on transfer learning. Our AI-IoT system design, implementation, and deployment demonstrate the possibility of generating an accurate AI model that can be executed on low-powered microcontrollers with limited computational resources. The system is scalable, allowing for dynamic updating of AI models on n number of vehicles. We developed a transfer learning algorithm that takes advantage of our pre-trained model, generated using a physical CO₂ sensor, and significantly improves its accuracy.

Our experimental findings demonstrate that the accuracy of the transfer learning model closely approximates the ground truth accuracy, with a deviation of no more than 2%, as illustrated in Fig. 12.4. The main model maintains a consistent accuracy of approximately 97%, while the transfer learning model's accuracy ranges from 95% to 99%. Moreover, the system is designed to determine when to update the model on the MCU, ensuring the highest possible accuracy is always maintained. The complete transfer learning-based loop takes around 600.48 s (10 minutes).

The proposed AI-IoT system is designed to operate seamlessly by updating the model in real-time. The model update process is triggered by the arrival of a new file from the MCU, and the loop is executed every 399.54 seconds. The prediction is stopped for less than two seconds during the model update process by replacing the old model with the new one and loading it into the memory. Our work lays the foundation for future research in this field as we continue to refine our model and improve the accuracy and efficiency of our AI-IoT system.

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Chapter 13

Agile AI and Firmware Management in IoT: DevOps for Low-Power Microcontroller-based Platforms

This chapter contains an exact copy of content present in the research paper [8], where Mohammad Alselek is the leading author and main contributor. It has already been peer-reviewed, accepted, and published.

13.1 Abstract

In this paper, we introduce a Development and Operations (DevOps)-based IoT system tailored for the dynamic management of firmware and AI models across distributed IoT environments. The system offers scalability, resource efficiency, and cost-effectiveness for updating the AI model and firmware on the IoT devices without a need for human intervention. To accomplish this, we have developed a continuous integration and continuous deployment (CI/CD) pipelines that operate across multiple platforms, leveraging the capabilities of Kubernetes and GitLab-Runner. Moreover, the system is specifically designed for Microcontroller-based low-power devices capable of running tiny AI models. The new deployment is sent to the IoT devices despite their location to start interacting with

the surrounding environment and perform predictions regarding its application. Through empirical experiments, we demonstrate the system effectiveness with promising results in terms of scalability, resource utilization, and deployment efficiency.

13.2 Introduction

The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) applications with Internet of Things (IoT) devices is rapidly gaining momentum. Projections indicate a staggering rise in the global count of IoT devices, expected to reach nearly 30 billion by 2030 [2], alongside significant annual growth in the AI market size, projected at 15.83% between 2024 and 2030 [3].

There are ongoing efforts within the domain of DevOps to automate the implementation and delivery of AI models, while initiatives in DevOps for IoT focus on automating the deployment of microservices across distributed IoT networks, leveraging technologies such as Kubernetes [104], Docker [105], Helm [106], and others. This approach offers a promising solution to dynamically updating multiple AI models and firmware within distributed cloud-native ecosystems by integrating DevOps practices for AI. It can enhance cost-effectiveness and operational efficiency compared to traditional methodologies [107]. However, agile AI and firmware management in IoT devices remain insufficiently explored.

In this paper, we present a new system utilizing CI/CD pipelines powered by GitLab-runners. These pipelines automate essential processes, including building, testing, packaging, releasing images, and deploying final applications into a distributed IoT cluster. The system comprises four GitLab repositories: Firmware Development, Data Acquisition, AI Training, and AI Optimization. Notably, the firmware development repository can independently run its pipeline. During the AI model update process on an IoT device, data collection begins with the IoT device, transmitting data to the AI training repository for dataset curation. Subsequently, the AI optimization pipeline refines the trained AI model, preparing it for direct deployment to the target IoT device.

The proposed system has a structure based on a Kubernetes cluster, where a master manages workers installed on mini-PCs, i.e. Raspberry Pi 4 Model B. This setup handles

tasks such as collecting data, deploying AI models, and updating firmware. Workers handle updating IoT devices with data and AI models using RESTful API, while firmware updates use RESTful API along with Over-The-Air (OTA) mechanism. IoT devices are Pycom FiPy motes.

The proposed system can easily scale to work with multiple IoT devices in different places. It also provides feedback to developers through logs, making it easier to fix problems quickly and avoid deployment failures. The proposed system offers several advantages and contributions, including:

- **Cost-effective software lifecycle:** Embracing DevOps practices for continuous updates of AI models and firmware.
- **Highly adaptable environment:** The system allows multiple IoT devices to be deployed in various locations.
- **Optimized resource utilization:** The system enables dynamic scaling of deployments, efficiently allocating resources based on demand.
- **Distributed OTA Firmware Updates:** Leveraging Kubernetes workers to facilitate the deployment of OTA firmware updates on IoT devices.
- **Distributed AI Model Updates:** Utilizing Kubernetes workers for the deployment of AI model updates within a distributed IoT ecosystem.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: Section 13.3 outlines the architecture and components of the proposed system. Section 13.4 details the system's development. Section 13.5 presents research findings and discusses implications, while Section 13.6 offers concluding remarks and suggests potential future research directions.

Figure 13.1: Proposed DevOps-Based IoT System for Continuous Firmware and AI Model Updates.

13.3 Proposed DevOps-Based IoT System for Continuous AI Model and Firmware Updates

In this research, we introduce an IoT-centric system empowered by advanced DevOps practices and modern software technologies to automate the firmware and AI model updates into resource-constrained devices. The system's architecture revolves around a central server, acting as a hub for developers to design, create, and initiate CI/CD pipelines. This server oversees the deployment process, ensuring efficient and automated updates. Additionally, the system incorporates a network of Raspberry Pis forming a Kubernetes cluster, crucial for managing and orchestrating AI models and firmware across distributed IoT devices.

The system architecture, depicted in Fig. 13.1, consists of four main components: two virtual machines (VMs) within the central server, namely the GitLab VM and the Kubernetes Master VM, along with Kubernetes Workers and IoT Devices. The GitLab VM serves as the host for all our repositories. We have developed three distinct CI/CD pipelines, each containing multiple jobs for execution. For instance, when the firmware pipeline is activated, the initial job compiles the firmware using the ESP-IDF and Micropython frameworks. Subsequently, the binary firmware file is incorporated into a docker container in the container registry during the second job. Finally, the last job deploys this container onto the target IoT device. Executing the CI/CD pipeline across various platforms is facilitated by GitLab-Runner, which needs to be installed and configured on all machines involved in the pipeline. The same logic can be applied within the other pipelines.

On the other hand, the Kubernetes master VM manages the deployments to target Raspberry Pi devices. As illustrated in Fig. 13.1, there are various deployments for Firmware updates, AI model updates, and Data collection. Depending on the CI/CD pipeline in operation and utilizing a specific GitLab-runner for this machine, a corresponding deployment is applied according to the configuration in the deployment file. This file contains numerous parameters, such as the deployment name, image URL, container name, and port. The worker node where the deployment will be implemented can be specified in the deployment file. Otherwise, it will be automatically selected based on Kubernetes' internal load balancer.

After the deployment is executed, it signifies that an application is active and functioning on the worker node. Each application is essentially a Python script with the Flask library imported to create a RESTful API, which listens on a specific port. In the case of firmware deployment, we have devised an endpoint where the firmware file is stored and can be requested. Similarly, for AI model deployment, the application includes an endpoint that can be accessed by IoT devices to request an AI model update.

Furthermore, we have chosen the Pycom FiPy development board as the primary IoT device in our system, harnessing the capabilities of the ESP32 Microcontroller Unit (MCU). Tailored for IoT applications, the ESP32 MCU excels in low-power operation, aligning perfectly with the energy-efficient demands of our Kubernetes cluster. Additionally, we have selected the Pycom FiPy development board for its exceptional wireless communication capabilities, offering various connectivity options such as Wi-Fi, Bluetooth, and LoRaWAN.

For example, we have configured the FiPy to connect to a Wi-Fi router to request firmware updates using the requests Micropython library. Once the updated firmware is saved in the FiPy's memory, the previous version can be replaced through OTA updates, ensuring that devices are consistently equipped with the latest features and security enhancements. Moreover, the FiPy actively checks for AI model updates. Once received and loaded into its memory, this resource-constrained IoT device becomes capable of performing inferences and generating predictions specific to the designated use case. This systematic approach ensures that the IoT devices are consistently outfitted with the most recent firmware and AI model versions, enabling them to effectively execute inference tasks despite the resource limitations inherent in such devices.

It is crucial to note that Kubernetes deployments consist of a specific number of replicas, referred to as pods or containers. In essence, each pod represents a container housing our application, which can be deployed on a worker node selected by the master. The scalability of these pods, meaning their ability to be increased or decreased in number, is significant. This scalability enhances availability and performance, especially concerning the resources available on the worker node, as elaborated in the subsequent section.

13.4 DevOps-based IoT System Development

This section presents the key components and repositories within the proposed system, aiming to smoothly integrate, continuously improve, and efficiently manage AI models on IoT devices. Each component plays a vital role in the development and deployment process, contributing to the system's robustness and scalability.

13.4.1 Hardware Setup

The hardware setup for our DevOps-based IoT system consists of an Ubuntu 20.04 virtual machine for GitLab, equipped with 8 CPUs and 18 GB of memory, and a Kubernetes master with 3 CPUs and 3 GB of RAM. We employ various IoT devices, including the Pycom FiPy for lightweight AI tasks and the Raspberry Pi 4 Model B for more demanding computational tasks. Communication between IoT devices and cloud services is facilitated through HTTP, ensuring efficient data transmission and updates.

13.4.2 Software Setup

Our software setup revolves around key components, including GitLab, Kubernetes, and GitLab-Runner, crucial for enabling CI/CD pipelines in our DevOps-based IoT system.

We deployed GitLab version 16.1.0, leveraging its robust features for version control and CI/CD automation. The installation process involved setting up GitLab on a dedicated Ubuntu 20.04 virtual machine. Following installation, we configured GitLab to enable CI/CD pipelines, ensuring automated testing and deployment of IoT applications.

For IoT application management, we deployed Kubernetes v1.21.0 using kubeadm. We set up a master node on an Ubuntu 20.04 VM and integrated Raspberry Pi 4 Model B devices as worker nodes. Kubernetes organizes containers into clusters, overseen by essential components: API Server, Scheduler, Controller Manager, and etcd for data storage. Within these Kubernetes clusters, the fundamental unit of deployment is the Pod. Pods host containerized applications and are allocated a unique IP address. The Kubelet, a critical component of Kubernetes, is responsible for overseeing container execution within Pods on

each node. It ensures that containers are launched and managed correctly, maintaining the desired state of applications. Moreover, the Kube Proxy is another essential element that aids in network routing within Kubernetes clusters. It directs incoming traffic to the appropriate containers.

We configured GitLab-Runner v16.3.1 to run CI/CD pipelines in both GitLab and Kubernetes environments. Instances were deployed on GitLab and Kubernetes master VMs, with additional ones on Kubernetes worker nodes. This setup ensured resource efficiency and scalability of CI/CD processes.

13.4.3 Network Design

Our system is engineered for portability and scalability. Fig. 13.2 depicts the network configuration, which includes a router for internet access. The GitLab and Kubernetes master virtual machines are configured with bridged network interfaces, connecting to the router for internet access. Additionally, Raspberry Pi devices, acting as Kubernetes worker nodes, connect to the router via Ethernet for internet access and communication with the Kubernetes master. These Raspberry Pi devices are also equipped with Wi-Fi interfaces configured to connect to an access point, enabling communication with end FiPy IoT devices.

13.4.4 Firmware Update Process

The Firmware Update Process is crucial in the IoT ecosystem, focusing on developing reliable and resource-efficient firmware for integrating AI applications into resource-constrained IoT devices. This involves iterative steps such as code composition, testing, and deployment, to ensure smooth operation across diverse hardware configurations and meet stringent performance criteria. For detailed firmware development processes, refer to [6], which explains MicroPython firmware with TensorFlow capabilities for AI model execution.

Algorithm 3 outlines the systematic approach for updating firmware on end IoT devices, integrated with the CI/CD pipeline.

Figure 13.2: Network Diagram of the testbed

Algorithm 3 Firmware Update Methodology

- 1: Fetch latest firmware updates (F_{latest})
 - 2: Build firmware image: $F_{build} \leftarrow \text{BuildFirmware}(F_{latest})$
 - 3: Store firmware artifacts in registry: $F_{artifacts}$
 - 4: Deploy firmware to Kubernetes cluster: $D_{cluster} \leftarrow \text{DeployCluster}(F_{artifacts})$
 - 5: Initiate firmware deployment on IoT devices: $D_{deployment} \leftarrow \text{StartDeployment}(F_{artifacts})$
 - 6: Choose worker node for firmware pull
 - 7: Transfer firmware to FiPy via HTTP REST API
 - 8: Update firmware via OTA updates
 - 9: Restart FiPy
-

This methodology ensures a systematic firmware update approach. It begins by fetching the latest firmware updates from the version control system (GitLab) and triggering the pipeline for automated build. Then, the resulting firmware artifacts are stored in the container registry and deployed to the Kubernetes cluster. The deployment process is initiated on end IoT devices through the Kubernetes worker node. Leveraging Over-the-Air updates and HTTP REST API, the new firmware replaces the existing one, ensuring successful completion of the update process. Finally, the FiPy device undergoes a restart to apply the updated firmware.

13.4.5 Data Acquisition Process

The Data Acquisition Process focuses on collecting, preprocessing, and transmitting data sourced from IoT devices, crucial for AI training procedures. As depicted in the system architecture diagram, Figure 13.1), the data acquisition repository adopts a comprehensive approach, encompassing three distinct types of data collectors: gesture recognition, aquaponics, and CO₂ concentration prediction.

Notably, while the gesture recognition and CO₂ datasets have been curated and validated previously in [6] and [7] respectively, highlighting the role of existing research in providing essential datasets for AI model training, challenges persist in acquiring data for the aquaponics domain, as outlined in our previous work [5]. The intricacies of this domain necessitate a nuanced approach, considering diverse environmental conditions for comprehensive data collection.

Regarding CI/CD integration, gesture recognition, CO₂ concentration prediction, or aquaponics data collectors can be developed and committed to GitLab. These collectors are dockerized and stored within the container registry. The deployment process is initiated through the REST API to apply the requested data collector to the end devices. Once running on the FiPy, the data collector gathers specific data to form the dataset. This automated approach facilitates the deployment process onto targeted IoT devices.

13.4.6 AI Training Process

The AI Training Process is dedicated to creating and refining machine learning models tailored for deployment on IoT devices. Commencing with the dataset collated by the data collector, the training process embarks on various phases to ultimately yield the TensorFlow AI model. For instance, the CO2 concentration prediction model utilizes a long short-term memory (LSTM) architecture [7].

However, it is imperative to note that the resultant model may not be inherently suitable for execution on microcontroller-based IoT devices due to resource constraints and architectural limitations. Hence, there arises a need to delve into the realm of AI model optimization, as expounded in the subsequent section.

13.4.7 AI Model Update Process

The AI Model Update Process involves the creation and refinement of specific AI models optimized for deployment on IoT devices. This includes designing lightweight model architectures, optimizing model parameters, and evaluating performance metrics under resource-constrained environments.

Our AI model update methodology is outlined in Listing 1:

```
# Input: Latest TensorFlow model (M_latest)
# Output: Updated deployed model (M_deployed)

def AIModelUpdate(TensorflowModel):
    M_latest = FetchLatestModel(TensorflowModel)
    # Step 1:
    M_pruned = PruneModel(M_latest)
    # Step 2:
    M_tflite = ConvertLiteModel(M_pruned)
    # Step 3:
    M_c = ConvertCModel(M_tflite)
    # Step 4:
    M_deployed = DeployModel(M_c)
```

```
    return M_deployed

# Call the function with the latest model
M_deployed = AIModelUpdate(TensorflowModel)
```

Listing 13.1 AI Model Update Methodology

The AI model update methodology involves several key steps:

Input and Output Declaration

The algorithm begins by taking the latest TensorFlow model, referred to as M_{latest} , as input. It then produces the updated deployed model, denoted as M_{deployed} , as output.

Fetch Latest Model Updates

This step involves retrieving the most recent updates of the TensorFlow model using the `FetchLatestModel` function.

Triggering AI Model CI/CD Pipeline for Model Optimization

The CI/CD pipeline for model optimization is initiated in this step. It comprises the following sub-steps:

Step 1: Prune the Model: The model pruning process entails removing unnecessary weights or connections to reduce its size. To achieve this, the `PruneModel` function is invoked.

Step 2: Convert the Pruned Model to TFLite Format: The model undergoes conversion to the TFLite format using the `ConvertLiteModel` function.

Step 3: Convert the TFLite Model to a C Array Format: The TFLite model is further converted to a C array format using the `ConvertCModel` function. The resultant C array model (M_C) is MCU-compatible and able to run efficiently on the FiPy board.

Step 4: Deploy Updated Model: Finally, the updated model, now in the C array format, is deployed to the target FiPy board utilizing the `DeployModel` function.

The AI model deployment process mirrors the firmware deployment. Once the newly updated AI model is built and stored, it is deployed to the Kubernetes cluster. Upon successful deployment, a container containing the updated AI model is initiated on the designated Kubernetes worker node. Subsequently, the REST API application, responsible for managing communication with IoT devices, begins the process of updating the AI model on the FiPy device.

Table 13.1 summarizes the average time required for each task in the end-to-end process, from the moment the developer does a push of a new AI model into the Git repository until its successful deployment onto IoT devices. The total average deployment time, obtained by summing the durations of all individual tasks, amounts to 376.18 seconds. Notably, the most time-consuming task is building the docker image, primarily due to the download time of the base image (python-alpine) and the subsequent push of the built image to the GitLab container registry. However, the AI model can be updated in approximately 5 seconds when requested from the FiPy board.

13.5 Discussion

The experiments covered deployment scaling, stress testing, and resource utilization, offering insights into the system's performance across different workloads and deployment scenarios. Fig. 13.3 depicts the system's worker nodes alongside the FiPy board, indicating our experimental setup.

Deployment scaling experiments, depicted in Fig. 13.4, examined deployment times for varying numbers of containers (pods) on a single worker node. We observed a nonlinear increase in deployment time as the number of containers increased. For instance, deploying 10 pods averaged 10 seconds, while 100 pods took around 121 seconds. Kubernetes faced challenges deploying over 110 pods efficiently. Therefore, any deployment should not exceed the 110 pods.

Stress tests, illustrated in Fig. 13.5a, evaluated response times for downloading AI models to FiPy devices under varying request loads. With 1, 10, and 100 concurrent requests,

Table 13.1: AI model deployment average time taken per job.

Job id	Job name	Average time (s)
1	Clear previous deployment	1.48
2	Build AI model docker image	338.24
3	Deploy into Kubernetes worker	31.41
4	Worker to FiPy	5.05
Total		376.18

response time increased as request load intensified. Interestingly, we found that the number of pods running on the worker node impacts response time. For example, with 10 concurrent requests, the best average response time (6.7 seconds) occurred when the worker had 2 pods, showcasing an 86% increase in response time (12.45 seconds) with 100 concurrent requests.

To determine the optimal number of pods for Raspberry Pi 4, we conducted resource utilization tests, monitoring CPU and RAM usage under different request loads. Fig. 13.5b illustrates that as the number of pods increased, CPU and RAM usage also rose, indicating resource saturation under heavy loads. For instance, with 100 pods, CPU usage reached 100%, while RAM usage peaked at 45%.

Depending on the workload, we recommend adjusting the number of pods accordingly. For light to moderate loads (up to 10 requests), having up to 10 pods yields optimal performance. However, for heavier loads, fewer pods are recommended to ensure resource availability and timely request processing.

A critical aspect is verifying if the downloaded file is an updated version. To address this, we employ hash functions computed within the FiPy and sent along with the request to the worker node. Upon reception, the application compares the hash code with the one generated on the worker node to determine file integrity.

Furthermore, building docker images for IoT devices, especially Raspberry Pis, requires special tools like buildx with architecture parameters to ensure compatibility with the target device's architecture.

Figure 13.3: Experimental Setup: System's Kubernetes Worker Nodes and FiPy Board

Figure 13.4: Deployment Experiments Results

(a) Stress Experiment: Response time Vs Number of Requests per Number of Containers

(b) Resource Utilization Experiment Results

Figure 13.5: Comparative Analysis of Response Time, CPU Usage, and RAM Usage with Varying Request Loads and Container Numbers on a Worker Node.

13.6 Conclusion

In this paper, we introduce a DevOps solution for automating AI model and firmware updates across distributed IoT devices. Our approach utilizes DevOps principles to streamline updating low-powered microcontrollers with limited computational resources, addressing a critical need in IoT ecosystems.

Central to our system is the utilization of Kubernetes, which orchestrates containerized applications across distributed environments, ensuring efficient resource allocation and scalability. Through the design, implementation, and deployment of our DevOps-based IoT system, we demonstrate the importance of Kubernetes in enabling continuous updates and optimizing system performance.

Our system boasts scalability, offering flexibility to adjust the number of worker nodes, Pods on the worker nodes, and IoT devices as needed. The development of CI/CD pipelines further enhances efficiency, ensuring that updated models and firmware are readily available for download upon request, minimizing downtime and optimizing system performance.

Our research sets the stage for further exploration into AI model optimization strategies, scalability enhancements, and innovative approaches for real-time model updates. Future studies could delve into the integration of advanced transfer learning techniques for adaptive model updates in IoT environments.

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